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PhD Thesis

A HOLISTIC PERSPECTIVE ON
DESIGNING AND EVALUATING
EXPLAINABLE AI MODELS:
FROM WHITE-BOX ADDITIVE
MODELS TO POST-HOC
EXPLANATIONS FOR BLACK-
BOX MODELS

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Alla mia famiglia

*It's not unusual for science to catch up with
art eventually, nor it is unusual for art to
catch up with the spiritual*

Rick Rubin

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The production of this thesis marks the end of a significant journey but at the same time also delineates the beginning of a new one, in the larger scope of the journey of life. It feels both like yesterday when I started the PhD programme and yet it also feels that the person that I am now is very different.

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*Adiós ríos, adiós fontes
adiós, regatos pequenos;
adiós, vista dos meus ollos,
non sei cándo nos veremos.
Adiós, casa donde viví,
adiós, techo que me cubrías,
adiós, ¡ay!, los que me querían,
adiós, ¡ay!, los que me olvidan.*

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Resumo

A integración cada vez máis profunda da Intelixencia Artificial (AI) nas nosas vidas cotiás e no tecido das diversas industrias representa unha nova era na que a tecnoloxía está a redefinir os límites do posible. Esta revolución tecnolóxica, mentres abre un abanico de oportunidades sen precedentes, tamén nos confronta con desafíos éticos e técnicos de gran importancia. Un dos aspectos máis críticos que emerxen neste contexto é o denominado problema da “caixa negra”, que fai alusión á falta de transparencia nos mecanismos de decisión dos sistemas de AI. Esta opacidade suscita serias preocupacións respecto á xustiza, ética e fiabilidade das tecnoloxías implicadas, subliñando a necesidade imperativa de abordar esta cuestión para fomentar a confianza nas decisións automatizadas.

A falta de entendemento claro de como as máquinas chegan ás súas conclusións crea unha barreira significativa para a aceptación e integración plena da AI na sociedade. É aquí onde a Intelixencia Artificial Explicable (XAI, polas súas siglas en inglés) se posiciona como unha solución esencial. A XAI busca abrir os sistemas de AI ao escrutinio, proporcionando visibilidade sobre o proceso de toma de decisións e facendo estas tecnoloxías accesibles e comprensibles para os usuarios finais. Este enfoque non só é crucial para construír unha relación de confianza entre a tecnoloxía e os seus usuarios, senón tamén para asegurar que a implementación da AI se realice de maneira xusta e ética.

A relevancia da XAI esténdese a través de múltiples sectores, onde a capacidade para explicar e xustificar as decisións tomadas por sistemas automatizados pode ter impactos significativos. No ámbito financeiro, por exemplo, a explicación das decisións sobre concesións de crédito ou hipotecas pode axudar a construír confianza entre as entidades financeiras e os seus clientes. No contexto xurídico, os veredictos asistidos por AI poderían ser feitos máis transparentes, facilitando unha maior comprensión das bases das decisións legais e promovendo a xustiza. Na saúde, as explicacións detalladas dos diagnósticos e tratamentos recomendados pola AI poderían mellorar significativamente a calidade da atención ao paciente, permitindo aos profesionais médicos unha maior comprensión das recomendacións automatizadas. Ademais, no ámbito do cambio climático, a XAI podería desvelar patróns complexos en grandes conxuntos de datos ambientais, axudando a informar mellor as estratexias de mitigación e adaptación.

A explicación na XAI é, por tanto, unha ferramenta poderosa que permite non só desentrañar

as historias causais detrás das decisións da AI, senón tamén adaptarse á capacidade de comprensión e ao contexto específico de cada receptor. Este proceso de explicación require unha preparación e organización coidadosas, co obxectivo de presentar a información dunha maneira que sexa tanto comprensible como relevante para as necesidades e o coñecemento previo dos usuarios.

A tarefa de explicar modelos de intelixencia artificial complexos encóntrase no delicado equilibrio entre manter a simplicidade e preservar a precisión. As explicacións deben ser deseñadas de tal maneira que sexan accesibles e comprensibles para un público xeral, sen obviar a riqueza e a profundidade dos procesos subxacentes que guían as decisións da AI. Este equilibrio non só fai as explicacións máis efectivas, senón que tamén serve como unha ponte para conectar os usuarios cun entendemento máis profundo dos sistemas automatizados, reforzando a confianza e facilitando unha maior transparencia.

Un aspecto fundamental na creación de explicacións efectivas na XAI é a necesidade de personalizar estas explicacións para atender aos diferentes niveis de curiosidade e coñecemento técnico dos usuarios. Recoñecer que non todos os usuarios requiren ou desexan o mesmo nivel de detalle é crucial para evitar a sobrecarga de información e, ao mesmo tempo, proporcionar a profundidade necesaria para aqueles que buscan un entendemento máis profundo. Isto significa que as explicacións deben ser adaptativas e flexibles, capaces de satisfacer unha ampla gama de necesidades e preferencias.

Ademais, o deseño de explicacións na XAI debe ter en conta o enfoque centrado no usuario, onde a comprensión e as necesidades informativas dos destinatarios son consideradas prioritarias. A identificación precisa dos interesados e a comprensión dos seus intereses específicos son elementos clave para desenvolver explicacións que non só informen, senón tamén que capte o interese e satisfagan as distintas necesidades dos usuarios. Este enfoque require unha análise detallada e a consideración de diferentes perspectivas para crear solucións efectivas que se axusten de maneira óptima ás demandas variadas da audiencia.

A clasificación das explicacións en locais, globais e de grupo serve como unha ferramenta vital para axustar o nivel de detalle e enfoque das explicacións, garantindo que se adecúen perfectamente ás necesidades e ao contexto de cada individuo. Este marco permite a adaptabilidade das explicacións, tendo en conta non só o tipo de decisión ou proceso que se está explicando senón tamén a singularidade da situación e os requisitos do usuario. Considerar o contexto específico no que se solicitan as explicacións, incluíndo as limitacións de tempo e espazo e as actividades en curso do usuario, é esencial para deseñar explicacións que sexan verdadeiramente efectivas e relevantes. Os factores contextuais, como o entorno no que se usa a tecnoloxía ou as capacidades cognitivas do usuario, desempeñan un papel crucial na forma en que a información debe ser presentada.

Avaliar a calidade e efectividade destas explicacións require unha consideración detallada

tanto da comprensibilidade e utilidade como da fidelidade á realidade do modelo subxacente. É fundamental que as explicacións non só sexan intelixibles e informativas senón tamén precisas e representativas dos mecanismos complexos que describen. Isto destaca a importancia de desenvolver sistemas de XAI que podían xerar explicacións xenéricas altamente personalizables, capaces de ser adaptadas para atender ás necesidades individuais de cada usuario, incluíndo aquelas persoas con discapacidades. Este enfoque non só promove a inclusión senón que tamén asegura que os avances na AI sexan accesibles a unha audiencia máis ampla, independentemente do seu nivel de coñecemento técnico ou habilidades específicas.

Por tanto, a avaliación dos sistemas de XAI debe ser abordada desde unha perspectiva holística, combinando métricas obxectivas con avaliacións centradas no usuario que poidan capturar efectivamente a comprensión, a satisfacción e o valor práctico das explicacións. Os sistemas de XAI, neste contexto, deben asumir o papel de educadores, esforzándose non só por transmitir información de maneira comprensible senón tamén por facer que esa información sexa accionable e relevante para as necesidades individuais de cada usuario. Adaptar o contido e a forma das explicacións ás circunstancias únicas de cada individuo é clave para maximizar a súa efectividade e impacto.

Esta orientación cara á personalización e inclusión nos sistemas de XAI reflicte un compromiso profundo coa creación de tecnoloxías que non só son avanzadas e potentes senón tamén accesibles, comprensibles e, fundamentalmente, máis humanas. Encarna a aspiración de avanzar nunha sociedade na que a tecnoloxía, especialmente a intelixencia artificial, se integre harmoniosamente coas necesidades e expectativas humanas, facilitando unha interacción máis rica e significativa entre os usuarios e as máquinas.

Nesta tese, establecemos o obxectivo de explorar a capacidade dos modelos de XAI para mellorar a comprensión e a confianza nas decisións tomadas por sistemas de IA, particularmente aqueles que son intrinsecamente opacos e complexos. Ao facelo, formulamos a seguinte hipótese: os modelos de IA transparentes, tamén coñecidos como modelos de caixa branca, poden desempeñar un papel crucial tanto como sistemas comprensibles de forma autónoma como ferramentas para explicar as accións de sistemas máis complexos e menos transparentes en diversos campos. Esta hipótese central serve de guía para o noso traballo, argumentando que unha mellor comprensión dos modelos de IA pode conducir a unha maior confianza e eficacia nos sistemas de IA en xeral.

Para dar soporte e validar esta hipótese, abordamos unha serie de obxectivos específicos na nosa investigación, cada un deseñado para superar os desafíos teóricos e prácticos dentro do campo da XAI. Estes obxectivos son:

- Comprender a Paisaxe da XAI: Propoñemos ofrecer unha revisión exhaustiva da literatura actual no campo da XAI, encapsulando unha gama ampla de puntos de vista e traballando para distinguir claramente entre os modelos de IA de caixa negra e caixa branca. Este

obxectivo inclúe a exploración do papel que xogan os diferentes tipos de datos e as variadas modalidades de explicación, establecendo unha base sólida sobre a cal construír o noso traballo.

- Construír Modelos Interpretables por Deseño: Enfocámonos especificamente nos modelos aditivos, debido ás súas prometedoras propiedades de interpretabilidade inherente, examinando os compromisos involucrados.
- Xerar Explicacións Post-hoc para Modelos de Caixa Negra: Exploraremos métodos para xerar explicacións despois do feito para sistemas de IA que non foron deseñados coa interpretabilidade en mente. Este traballo implica a introdución a técnicas como os puntaxes de atribución de características e a súa aplicación a datos tabulares, imaxes e textos, buscando entender a súa fidelidade e aplicabilidade en escenarios do mundo real.
- Comprender as Implicacións da XAI para a Industria: Finalmente, propoñemos unha ponte entre a teoría e a práctica, colaborando con entidades do sector industrial, como INDITEX, para demostrar o impacto tanxible da XAI nas industrias. Este obxectivo está orientado a comprender os desafíos e beneficios que a XAI pode aportar ao ecosistema corporativo, aplicando a nosa investigación a casos de uso industriais reais e avaliando a súa influencia.

Con estes obxectivos en mente, a nosa tese aspira non só a avanzar no coñecemento teórico dentro do campo da XAI, senón tamén a demostrar o valor práctico da XAI en aplicacións do mundo real, abordando a necesidade crítica de sistemas de IA máis transparentes, comprensibles e, en última instancia, confiables.

Na continuidade dos nosos obxectivos e aspiracións, esta tese introduce o Modelo Aditivo de Caixa Branca Neural (CNAM, polas súas siglas en inglés), unha innovación deseñada para equilibrar a interpretabilidade e o rendemento nas tarefas de IA. Este modelo representa unha confluencia única entre a interpretabilidade inherente aos modelos de caixa branca e a robustez en rendemento característica dos sistemas de IA avanzados. A CNAM, fundamentada na arquitectura das redes neuronais, distínguese pola súa estrutura interpretable de funcións de forma aditivas, un avance que alenta a ponte entre a complexidade computacional e a transparencia cognitiva.

As funcións de forma de CNAM, construídas a partir de funcións escalonadas diferenciables, permiten unha inicialización arbitraria, ofrecendo unha flexibilidade notable na configuración inicial do modelo. Isto fai posible que CNAM se inicialice para coincidir cunha solución case óptima dunha máquina de potenciación explicativa (EBM), establecendo un punto de partida sólido no espectro da interpretabilidade. Mais aínda, CNAM posúe a capacidade de diverxir desta solución inicial de EBM de maneira controlada mediante a regulación, un mecanismo que refina a súa adaptabilidade e eficacia.

A introdución de termos de regulación específicos dentro de CNAM abre un abano de posibilidades para explorar directamente o equilibrio entre interpretabilidade e rendemento. Por exemplo, a imposición de escaseza como criterio de regulación potencia a interpretabilidade, aínda que isto poida implicar certa renuncia en termos de rendemento. Este axuste fino permite aos usuarios personalizar CNAM segundo as súas prioridades, equilibrando as demandas de máxima eficacia contra a necesidade de claridade explicativa. Ao contrario das EBM, que teñen un desempeño fixo, CNAM permite un axuste preciso entre interpretabilidade e precisión mediante a regulación de hiperparámetros específicos.

A avaliación de CNAM a través de 56 conxuntos de datos de clasificación revela o seu excepcional desempeño, superando ás EBM a través do espazo de compromiso entre interpretabilidade e rendemento. CNAM demostra consistentemente a súa capacidade para atopar modelos cunha interpretabilidade significativamente mellor que a das EBM mantendo un rendemento similar, así como modelos cun rendemento superior ao das EBM a niveis comparables de interpretabilidade.

Dous exemplos ilustrativos subliñan a habilidade de CNAM para navegar con destreza entre os obxectivos de equilibrio. Nunha tarefa de clasificación, CNAM iguala o rendemento da EBM cunha maior interpretabilidade. Noutra de regresión, equipara a interpretabilidade dun modelo lineal cun rendemento un 25% mellor. Esta descomposición aditiva en funcións de forma non só facilita a inspección e comprensión do modelo, senón que tamén permite a imposición de restricións de interpretabilidade, como a monotonicidade e a suavidade.

CNAM é ofrecido como un software de código aberto, promovendo a súa adopción máis ampla e facilitando o seu uso na comunidade científica e industrial. As futuras ampliacións do modelo poderían incorporar explicacións en linguaxe natural e bucles de retroalimentación do usuario, aumentando así a súa accesibilidade e eficacia. A posibilidade de habilitar interaccións de características de orde superior podería impulsar aínda máis o rendemento de CNAM nas tarefas asignadas, marcando un novo hito na nosa busca por sistemas de IA que non só sexan poderosos, senón tamén plenamente comprensibles e confiables.

Na continuidade da nosa exploración sobre os sistemas de XAI e a súa aplicación práctica, os Valores Shapley emerxen como unha metodoloxía clave para medir a complexidade dos modelos e a fidelidade das explicacións subrogadas. Esta aproximación non só enriquece a nosa comprensión sobre como as decisións son tomadas polos sistemas de IA, senón que tamén subliña a insuficiencia de maximizar unicamente a precisión para alcanzar unha IA confiable e ética.

Entre estas métricas, os valores de Shapley destacan como un método prometedor para medir a complexidade dos modelos e a fidelidade das explicacións subrogadas. A través da utilización dos valores de Shapley, é posible asignar unha medida de importancia a cada característica dunha predición específica, facilitando así a comprensión dos factores que contribúen ás decisións do modelo. Non obstante, maximizar a precisión por si só resulta insuficiente para alcanzar unha

IA de confianza e ética. É aquí onde entran en xogo as métricas propostas de Lonxitude SHAP e Lonxitude de Interacción SHAP para a complexidade do modelo.

A Lonxitude SHAP e a Lonxitude de Interacción SHAP baséanse na carga cognitiva asociada ás distribucións dos valores de Shapley. Canto menos valores SHAP non cero haxa, menor será a complexidade e, por tanto, máis comprensible será o modelo. Esta relación directa entre a cantidade de valores SHAP non cero e a complexidade do modelo correlaciónase ben coas métricas de complexidade estándar para árbores de decisión, ofrecendo así unha forma de comparar o compromiso entre rendemento e comprensibilidade a través de diferentes modelos. Este enfoque facilita a optimización multiobxectivo da precisión e a comprensibilidade, avanzando cara a modelos de IA máis equilibrados e éticos.

A fidelidade das explicacións, por outro lado, é crucial para asegurar a xustiza, a responsabilidade e o consentimento informado dentro dos sistemas de IA. As explicacións subrogadas infieis non só son perigosas por perpetuar prexuízos, senón que tamén poden minar a confianza na IA. A métrica ShapGAP aborda esta cuestión ao avaliar a fidelidade dos modelos subrogados respecto aos modelos orixinais de caixa negra. Ao comparar as distribucións dos valores SHAP entre os modelos subrogados e os orixinais, utilizando distancias L2 ou de coseno, ShapGAP axuda aos desenvolvedores a crear modelos subrogados máis fiables e comprensibles.

Ao integrar estas novas métricas e enfoques na avaliación de modelos de IA, poderíamos avanzar significativamente na nosa capacidade para crear sistemas que non só sexan tecnicamente competentes, senón tamén transparentes e xustos. Así, a adopción de técnicas como a Lonxitude SHAP, a Lonxitude de Interacción SHAP, e ShapGAP pode marcar un novo fito na nosa busca por unha IA ética e comprensible, ampliando a súa adopción e eficacia na comunidade científica e industrial.

Ademais de medir a complexidade e fidelidade dos modelos, é fundamental avaliar a fidelidade dos métodos de explicación post-hoc, especialmente para redes neuronais nos dominios da visión e a linguaxe. A fidelidade, neste contexto, prioriza a alineación co comportamento do modelo por riba da plausibilidade humana, desafiando así a noción de que as explicacións deben ser intuitivamente comprensibles para os usuarios finais.

Introdúcese o marco Focus, unha innovación deseñada para construír mosaicos de imaxes e avaliar a fidelidade das explicacións. Este enfoque permítenos crear mostras de datos sintéticos, combinando elementos visuais da clase obxectivo e clases non obxectivo, co obxectivo de avaliar se os métodos de explicación asignan correctamente a importancia aos elementos adecuados. A extensión deste marco mediante a introdución da Matriz de Confusión de Atribución, con métricas como a precisión e a exactitude, representa un paso adiante na cuantificación da fidelidade dos métodos de explicación.

Ademais, a adaptación do marco Focus ás tarefas de procesamento de linguaxe natural (PLN) marca un avance significativo. Ao construír mosaicos textuais que combinan frases das clases

obxectivo e non obxectivo, propónse a puntuación TextFocus para cuantificar a fidelidade dos métodos de explicación en PLN. Esta metodoloxía permite avaliar varios métodos de atribución de características, como LIME, LRP, GradCAM e Gradientes Integrados, investigando o impacto dos hiperparámetros e as liñas base no rendemento destes métodos de explicación.

Ao recoñecer as limitacións de TextFocus, incluíndo a evidencia compartida e a ausencia de evidencia, ofrécese unha perspectiva equilibrada sobre as capacidades e restricións destas ferramentas. Non obstante, a utilidade de TextFocus para descubrir prexuízos descoñecidos nos modelos e conxuntos de datos de PLN sinala o potencial transformador destas metodoloxías.

En esencia, Focus e TextFocus seguen unha aproximación similar, aínda que aplicada a diferentes modalidades de datos: Máis xeralmente, a idea fundamental detrás de Focus e TextFocus é a construción de mostras de datos sintéticos, sexan mosaicos de imaxe ou textuais, que conteñan elementos coñecidos tanto da clase obxectivo como das clases non obxectivo. Estes mosaicos utilízanse logo para avaliar a fidelidade de diferentes métodos de explicación na atribución de importancia aos elementos correctos da clase obxectivo. Asumíndose que, para unha clase obxectivo dada, un método de explicación fiel debería asignar atribucións positivas (importancia) principalmente aos tokens ou frases que pertencen a esa clase obxectivo dentro do mosaico, mentres que debería asignar atribucións negativas aos elementos das clases non obxectivo.

Ao cuantificar canto ben un método de explicación cumpre con esta suposición nos mosaicos construídos, Focus e TextFocus ofrecen unha maneira de avaliar a fidelidade do método sen depender de anotacións humanas ou suposicións sobre a plausibilidade.

Mentres que os marcos Focus e TextFocus permiten avaliar a fidelidade dos métodos de explicación, é igualmente crucial demostrar o valor práctico da XAI en aplicacións industriais reais. Para ilustrar a aplicación práctica da XAI, exploramos varios casos de uso na empresa líder do sector téxtil INDITEX. Esta colaboración brinda unha oportunidade única para demostrar o impacto transformador da XAI nas operacións empresariais, revelando patróns complexos nos datos e mellorando a eficiencia e transparencia nos procesos de toma de decisións.

No primeiro caso de uso, centrado na reposición de inventario, a XAI demostra o seu valor mediante a aplicación de EBM e GAMs. Estes modelos ofrecen un rendemento comparable aos modelos caixa negra, destacando polas súas funcións de forma interpretables que proporcionan explicacións tanto globais como locais sobre o comportamento do modelo. Esta claridade nas decisións de xestión de inventario é crucial para optimizar os procesos de reposición, asegurando que as tendas manteñan un stock adecuado para satisfacer a demanda dos consumidores.

Continuando coa predición de vendas semanais, o uso de Random Forests complementados con explicacións SHAP revela unha variable proxy con significativo poder predictivo. A agrupación de características semanticamente relacionadas ofrece unha visión simplificada da súa importancia, facilitando unha comprensión profunda dos factores que impulsan as vendas. Esta transparencia permite axustes precisos nas estratexias de vendas e marketing.

O terceiro caso de uso analiza a relación entre prezos e vendas para explorar o impacto do prezo na demanda. Utilizando Random Forests con explicacións SHAP, este caso manexa eficazmente a distribución de cola gorda da variable obxectivo, revelando que a relación entre prezo e vendas mostra unha tendencia negativa que se estabiliza en niveis de prezo máis altos. Este patrón subliña a necesidade de estratexias de prezo equilibradas para maximizar os ingresos sen desincentivar o consumo.

En contextos de alta relevancia, modelos interpretables como EBM constrúen confianza e alíñanse cos modelos mentais dos interesados, xogando un papel crucial na adopción e aceptación das solucións baseadas en IA. Paralelamente, modelos caixa negra con explicacións post-hoc, como as proporcionadas por SHAP, brindan percepcións valiosas que permiten unha comprensión máis profunda dos datos subxacentes para predicións precisas.

A sinerxia entre a IA e a expertise humana, facilitada pola XAI, transforma as operacións empresariais facéndoas máis orientadas a datos, eficientes e transparentes. As percepcións obtidas nos casos de uso en INDITEX abren camiños para futuras aplicacións de XAI en diversas industrias, evidenciando o seu potencial para revolucionar a maneira na que as empresas entenden e interactúan coa complexidade dos seus datos e procesos. A XAI non só facilita a toma de decisións informadas senón que tamén promove a innovación continua, mantendo ás empresas na vangarda nun mundo cada vez máis orientado a datos.

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1 Introduction

In our current digital age, data surrounds us. From online clicks to in-depth system analysis, this data explosion has ignited massive changes, especially in areas like machine learning and Artificial Intelligence (AI). And it is clear: AI is becoming more and more a part of our daily lives, from our smartphones to critical industry operations. However, as much as AI has revolutionized our world, there is a challenge. Many AI systems are “black boxes”, giving results without clear explanations. This makes trust issues emerge as crucial issues. How can we trust something if we do not see how it works? And how can we ensure it is making choices that are fair and ethical?

For example, take the banking and financial sector. A mortgage application gets denied. With current black-box models, the potential homeowner is left questioning their financial health and the bank’s decision-making process. Perhaps it was a matter of credit history length, a forgotten bill from years ago, or decisions based on protected attributes such as race or gender. Transparency not only aids the individual but strengthens trust in the financial system, encouraging more people to navigate and engage with it confidently.

These challenges brings forth the need for Explainable AI (XAI). XAI seeks to open up these AI systems, making their workings transparent to us. it is about making sure that we know how AI thinks and decides. Organizations are also joining the mission for more transparent AI. DARPA, for instance, has launched an XAI program aiming for transparency in AI models without compromising their performance [58, 59]. Laws like the European Union’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [43] and the European AI Act, across its progressive drafts [103, 104, 105], emphasize AI’s need to be both clear and trustworthy.

Venture into the complex realm of law, where AI tools are increasingly assisting in determining verdicts [88]. For example, in a scenario involving an autonomous vehicle in a accident, pinpointing liability is vital. Traditional systems might produce a verdict, but XAI offers a rationale. It can shed light on whether it was the autonomous software’s decision or external factors like unpredictable pedestrian movements. The implication? A fairer justice system where technological determinations can be clearly understood and, if necessary, contested. Healthcare is another crucial arena [25]. An AI diagnostic tool suggests an unconventional treatment for a patient. Instead of blindly following this advice, the medical team, armed with XAI, can under-

stand the reasoning. Maybe it is a recommendation based on recent research or specific genetic markers in the patient. By knowing the ‘why,’ healthcare professionals can combine their expertise with AI’s insights, ensuring more comprehensive and personalized patient care.

In tackling global challenges like climate change, AI’s potential is undeniable [29]. As models sift through vast environmental data, they might flag unusual correlations, say between deforestation rates and certain marine life behavior. But to act on these findings, researchers need to understand the connection. XAI provides this bridge, transforming insights into actionable strategies, leading to innovative approaches to environmental conservation.

1.1 HYPOTHESIS AND OBJECTIVES

We formulate the main hypothesis tested in the present thesis as follows: *Transparent AI models (known as white-box models) can help us understand and trust the decision-making processes of non-transparent AI models (known as black-box models). These white-box models could either be used as clear, interpretable systems on their own or as tools to explain the actions of more complex, opaque systems in various fields.*

To validate this hypothesis, we have to advance both theoretical foundations and real-world applications in the XAI research field. Specifically, we address the following challenges:

- **O1. Understanding XAI Landscape:** To offer a comprehensive update on the current literature in the field, revisiting the works done on the topic in the academic literature, and encapsulating broad viewpoints. This includes distinguishing between ‘black-box’ and ‘white-box’ AI models, understanding the role of data types, and exploring different explanation modalities.
- **O2. Building Interpretable-by-design Models:** To delve into models that are intrinsically interpretable, weighing the trade-offs between clarity of understanding and performance. Special attention will be paid to additive models because they have shown promising properties.
- **O3. Generating Post-hoc Explanations for Black-box Models:** Dive into methods that generate explanations after the fact. This involves an introduction to feature attribution scores and their applications to tabular, image, and textual data. The focus is on understanding the nuances of these techniques, how to measure their faithfulness, and how to apply them in real-world use cases.
- **O4. Understanding XAI Implications for Industry:** This is a crucial dimension, where the theoretical meets the practical. In collaboration with INDITEX, we aim to showcase the tangible impact of XAI in industries, understanding the challenges and benefits that

it brings to the corporate ecosystem. This involves taking actual industry use-cases and evaluating the influence of our research.

1.2 CONTEXT

Within the landscape of European scientific innovation, this research is sited as part of the “Natural Language for Explainable Artificial Intelligence” (NL4XAI) project [5], a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action. The aim of NL4XAI was training 11 creative, entrepreneurial and innovative early-stage researchers (ESRs), who faced the challenge of making AI self-explanatory and thus contributing to translate knowledge into products and services for economic and social benefit, with the support of XAI systems. The structure of the NL4XAI project, according to its work packages and the early-stage researchers working on them, is depicted in Figure 1.1. The Project consortium consisted of 10 beneficiaries and 9 partner organizations.

Figure 1.1: The NL4XAI project structure showcasing its work packages and the associated early-stage researchers, setting the stage for the research explored in this dissertation.

This thesis was developed by ESR1 with the guidance of two professors: José María Alonso Moral from the University of Santiago de Compostela and Albert Gatt from University of Malta and Utrecht University. Their co-supervision provided a rich academic backdrop for the investigation into the convergence of XAI and Natural Language Processing (NLP).

The research work was further enriched by academic secondments, including a month-long stay in Malta and a five-month period in Utrecht, coupled with a three-month industrial secondment at INDITEX, a leading entity in the fashion industry. These secondments were invaluable in understanding the practicalities of applying XAI and NLP in both academic and commer-

cial contexts. They gave ESRs the opportunity to collaborate among them and with senior researchers from different institutions.

It is worth noting that the NL4XAI project was organized into four pivotal scientific work packages (WPs), each targeting a specific area of XAI research:

- WP1: XAI Models — aiming to generate AI systems that can explain their reasoning in natural language. The involved ESRs were: ESR1 (CiTIUS-USC, Spain), ESR2 (CiTIUS-USC, Spain), ESR3 (UNIABDN, UK), and ESR4 (UU, The Netherlands).
- WP2: NL Technology for XAI — focusing on enhancing the natural language technology that underpins the communicative aspect of XAI. The involved ESRs were: ESR5 (UM, Malta) and ESR6 (CNRS, France).
- WP3: Argumentation Technology for XAI — diving into the methodologies for structuring arguments that AI systems can use to justify their decisions. The involved ESRs were: ESR7 (WUT, Poland) and ESR8 (IIIA-CSIC, Spain).
- WP4: Interactive Interfaces for XAI — aiming at crafting user interfaces that facilitate seamless interaction with the explanatory mechanisms of AI systems. The involved ESRs were: ESR9 (UTWENTE, The Netherlands), ESR10 (TU Delft, The Netherlands), and ESR11 (INDRA, Spain).

The body of work presented here was developed within the context of WP1, which is at the heart of the project’s goal to develop transparent AI models. Collaboration with fellow ESRs in the same and different WPs, in the same and different institutions through secondments was pivotal, leading to joint publications with ESR3 (Adarsa Sivaprasad) and ESR5 (Michele Cafagna) and contributions to various project deliverables.

This research, therefore, is not only a reflection of personal academic endeavor but also a collaborative effort, illustrating the communal and pioneering ethos of the NL4XAI project.

1.3 METHODOLOGY

In this dissertation, our methodology takes cues from the agile framework, particularly drawing parallels with the SCRUM approach. It is tailored to uphold scientific rigor while remaining sufficiently flexible to navigate the dynamic landscape of XAI. Our process is inherently iterative, where each phase—akin to a SCRUM sprint—has specific deliverables and is subject to review and refinement as new insights emerge. The methodology unfolds as follows:

1. **Problem Identification (Preliminary Sprint):** The initial step involves a deep dive into the core objectives and challenges associated with demystifying black-box AI models. It sets the stage for a clear direction and helps to fine-tune the focus of the research.

2. **Literature Review and Gap Analysis (Exploratory Sprint):** A thorough examination of the existing body of work in XAI follows, where we assess the state of the art, pinpointing strengths and identifying crucial gaps that need addressing. This sprint fosters an understanding of where the field stands and where it is headed.
3. **Focused Development (Innovation Sprint):** Guided by insights gained from the previous steps, we move to design and prototype new methods and strategies aimed at bridging the identified gaps. This stage is characterized by development and testing, iterating on feedback and findings.
4. **Community Engagement and Validation (Outreach Sprint):** In this final sprint, we validate our proposed techniques through case studies and empirical evidence, gauging their efficacy and practical application. Subsequently, we engage with the academic and industrial communities to present and discuss our contributions.

This structured yet adaptable methodology not only aligns with scientific principles but is also reflective of the dynamic nature of the field we are investigating. Each phase represents a building block that contributes to a robust, evidence-based, and impactful body of work that resonates with both academic and industrial spheres. In collaboration with industry partners such as INDITEX, we ensure that our research has tangible implications, bringing theoretical concepts into the practical realm, thus, offering a method that is as innovative as the solutions it aims to create in the realm of XAI.

1.4 DISSERTATION STRUCTURE

This dissertation offers a multi-faceted approach to XAI, addressing both the theoretical frameworks and the practical challenges of making machine learning models understandable and accountable. The subsequent chapters are organized as follows:

- Chapter 2 lays down the basics of XAI, discussing what an explanation is and why it is important, the user-centric perspective of XAI, who the users are, methods for providing explanations adapted to the given context, communication of explanations, and evaluating XAI.
- Chapter 3 provides a technical walkthrough of the XAI landscape, discussing the types and roles of XAI models, when to opt for black-box or white-box models, data types in XAI, a simple taxonomy of XAI, black-box post-hoc explanations, overview of post-hoc explanation methods, popular feature attribution scores, and a roadmap for upcoming discussions.

- Chapter 4 delves into interpretable-by-design models, particularly generalized additive models. This chapter explores the potential and limitations of Constrainable Neural Additive Models, examining the delicate balance between model transparency and performance.
- Chapter 5 focuses on the utilization and assessment of post-hoc explanations for black-box models. Specifically, it introduces Shap Length Complexity, a novel measure of black-box complexity, and ShapGap, a metric for evaluating the faithfulness of surrogate models that approximate complex black-box models within a certain domain.
- Chapter 6 examines the assessment of the faithfulness of post-hoc feature attribution methods, first in the vision domain and subsequently in the language domain.
- Chapter 7 presents case studies of XAI’s concrete applications in the industry, featuring projects completed during a three-month secondment at INDITEX, a major player in the fashion industry.
- Chapter 8 provides concluding remarks and future work.

1.5 MAIN CONTRIBUTIONS

The research findings of this dissertation have been articulated in the subsequent publications:

Journals:

Ettore Mariotti^a, José María Alonso Moral^a, Albert Gatt^b. *Exploring the balance between interpretability and performance with carefully designed constrainable Neural Additive Models*. Information Fusion, 2023. ISSN: 1872-6305, 1566-2535. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2023.101882>.

^aCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

^bUtrecht University.

- **Quality indicators:**¹ Journal’s H-INDEX: 136. Impact Factor: 18.6 (2022-2023). CiteScore: 38.6. Information Fusion’s distinguished rankings in various computer science categories include :
 - Hardware and Architecture: Q1, 1/167 (99% percentile)
 - Information Systems: Q1, 3/353 (99% percentile)
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- Software: Q1, 4/398 (99% percentile)
- **PhD candidate contribution:** Undertook the entirety of the research process, from conceptualization, design, coding, testing, to the composition of the manuscript. Supervisors provided guidance, with inputs on evaluations and the writing process.
- **Openly Accessible Software:** In alignment with the spirit of open science and accessibility, the software developed as part of this research is freely available for use and adaptation. This constitutes a significant contribution to the field, enabling broader application and advancement of the research findings. The software can be accessed at <https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/ettore.mariotti/cnam>.
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Ettore Mariotti^d, Anna Arias-Duart^d, Michele Cafagna^d, Albert Gatt^d, Dario Garcia Gasulla^d, Jose Maria Alonso Moral^d. *TextFocus: Assessing the Faithfulness of Feature Attribution Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Submitted and under review for IEEE Access, 2024.

^aCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes (CiTIUS), Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

^bBarcelona Supercomputing Center.

^cUniversity of Malta.

^dUtrecht University.

- **Quality indicators:**³ Journal's H-INDEX: 242. Impact Factor: 3.9 (2019-2022). CiteScore: 9.0. SCImago journal rank (SJR) of 0.926. IEEE Access's distinguished rankings in various categories include:

- Engineering: Q1

³Quality indicators sourced from: <https://www.scimagojr.com/journalsearch.php?q=21100374601&tip=sid&clean=0> <https://ieeaccess.ieee.org/about-ieee-access/learn-more-about-ieee-access/>

- Computer Science: Q1
- Materials Science: Q1
- **PhD candidate contribution:** Undertook the conceptualization, execution, coding, and result analysis for the research. Supervisors provided guidance and input throughout the process.
- **Openly Accessible Software:** In line with the principles of open science and accessibility, the code developed as part of this research is freely available for use and adaptation. This contributes to the field by allowing wider application and further development of the research findings.
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^aCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

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- **PhD candidate contribution:** Complete ownership from research conceptualization, design, execution, testing, evaluation, to manuscript writing. Supervisors offered guidance, feedback on evaluations, and reviews of the manuscript.
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Towards Harnessing Natural Language Generation to Explain Black-box Models

Ettore Mariotti, Jose M. Alonso, Albert Gatt

Abstract

The opaque nature of many machine learning techniques prevents the wide adoption of powerful information processing tools for high stakes scenarios. The emerging field eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) aims at providing justifications for automatic decision-making systems in order to ensure reliability and trustworthiness in the users. For achieving this vision, we emphasize the importance of a natural language textual modality as a key component for a future intelligent interactive agent. We outline the challenges of XAI and review a set of publications that work in this direction.

Anthology ID: [2020.nl4xai-1.6](#)
Volume: [2nd Workshop on Interactive Natural Language Technology for Explainable Artificial Intelligence](#)
Month: November
Year: 2020
Address: Dublin, Ireland
Editors: [Jose M. Alonso](#), [Alejandro Catala](#)
Venue: [NL4XAI](#)
SIG: [SIGGEN](#)
Publisher: Association for Computational Linguistics
Note: –
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URL: <https://aclanthology.org/2020.nl4xai-1.6>
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Ettore Mariotti^a, Albert Gatt^a, Jose M. Alonso-Moral^a. *Prometheus: Harnessing Fuzzy Logic and Natural Language for Human-centric Explainable Artificial Intelligence*. Proceedings of the XX Spanish Congress on Fuzzy Logic and Technologies, 2021. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5878570](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5878570)

^aCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

^bUtrecht University

- **PhD candidate contribution:** Primary author. Conceptualized the main ideas, conducted experiments, and wrote the majority of the paper. Feedback and refinements in

the manuscript were provided by co-authors Albert Gatt and Jose M. Alonso-Moral.

- **Software availability:** In line with commitments to open science and reproducibility, the software ‘Prometheus’ utilized in the research is made available for public access and use. The code repository can be found at <https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/ettore.mariotti/prometheus>.
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September 23, 2021 (v1) Conference paper Open

Prometheus: Harnessing Fuzzy Logic and Natural Language for Human-centric Explainable Artificial Intelligence

Ettore Mariotti

Prometheus is an interpretable model which is suitable for the generation of visual and textual explanations grounded in common sense knowledge. This model can be seen as a special case of generalized additive models, which can be also interpreted as a list of (fuzzy) rules. The goodness of the model is illustrated with one benchmark dataset fr...

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Figure 1.5: Open Access status of the publication *Prometheus: Harnessing Fuzzy Logic and Natural Language for Human-centric Explainable Artificial Intelligence*.

Ettore Mariotti^a, Jose M. Alonso^a, Roberto Confalonieri^b. *A Framework for Analyzing Fairness, Accountability, Transparency and Ethics: A Use-case in Banking Services*. IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE), pages 11-14, Luxembourg, Luxembourg. IEEE, July 2021. DOI: [10.1109/FUZZ45933.2021.9494481](https://doi.org/10.1109/FUZZ45933.2021.9494481).

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^bUniversità degli Studi di Padova.

- **PhD candidate contribution:** Full involvement spanning from research conceptualization, design, execution, testing, evaluation, to manuscript writing. The supervisors provided feedback, guidance, and reviews of the manuscript.
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^bUtrecht University

- **PhD candidate contribution:** Full involvement spanning from research conceptualization, design, execution, testing, evaluation, to manuscript writing. The supervisors provided feedback, guidance, and reviews of the manuscript.
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^aBarcelona Supercomputing Center.

^bCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

- **PhD candidate contribution:** Jointly conceptualized the primary contribution with Anna Arias-Duart. Worked on the design, theory, and co-writing the paper. Anna conducted the experiments using existing code. Feedback and guidance were provided by the other co-authors.
- **Publication Venue Quality:** The paper was presented at the Workshop on Explainable AI for Computer Vision (XAI4CV), part of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR). According to the CORE 2023 ranking, CVPR was rated as ‘A*’. The high rank of the conference highlights its prestige and impact in the field of computer vision and multimedia computation.
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Ettore Mariotti^a, Adarsa Sivaprasad^b, Jose Maria Alonso Moral^b. *Beyond Prediction Similarity: ShapGAP for Evaluating Faithful Surrogate Models in XAI*. Presented at the first World Conference on Explainable Artificial Intelligence, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-44064-9_10](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-44064-9_10).

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- **PhD candidate contribution:** The primary investigator leading the research initiative, responsible for developing the core methodology, writing the code, conducting the experiments, and authoring the manuscript. The collaboration with Adarsa Sivaprasad was instrumental in ideation and conceptual discussions, enriching the research’s framework. The advisory team provided cursory approval with minimal involvement.
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1.6 VISUAL SUMMARY OF THE THESIS

In this section, we introduce a visual summary that serves both as a schematic representation of the thesis and a navigational tool. This overview not only mirrors the logical flow and thematic progression of our work but also provides a consolidated understanding of its structure and

content. Starting from the central hypothesis, it branches out into our key objectives and corresponding research questions, linking each to the chapters where they are extensively examined. This approach offers a clear roadmap, guiding the reader through the interconnections between our hypothesis, objectives, research questions, and their outcomes, ensuring an enhanced comprehension of the thesis.

The purpose of this visual summary is not only to offer a snapshot of the thesis's layout but also to highlight the coherence and interconnectedness of its various components. By illustrating how each part contributes to the overarching narrative and goals of the research, this summary aims to enhance the reader's comprehension and appreciation of the work's depth and breadth.

Figure 1.11: Visual summary with the main research questions and answers in this doctoral dissertation.

2 Preliminary Concepts

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning have transformed numerous industries, offering innovative solutions to complex problems. With this transformation, however, has come a critical concern: the need to make these intelligent systems accountable, fair, and transparent. This prompted the development for Explainable AI (XAI), a field dedicated to making machine learning models more interpretable and understandable, not just to researchers and practitioners, but importantly, to non-technical users too.

In addition to making AI understandable, the push for is also driven by practical needs. Beyond AI ethics and self-regulations, laws are starting to require that automated decisions can be explained, and people want to know how AI affects them [43]. So, XAI is not just something desirable; it is becoming a must-have, influenced by legal rules and public opinion.

Therefore, XAI is not merely about increasing transparency in AI; it signals a shift in our perspective towards AI. We are moving away from treating AI as inscrutable “black boxes” that deliver remarkable results without providing insight. Instead, there is a growing emphasis on understanding the internal mechanics of these models, allowing us to discern the ‘why’ behind their decisions.

In the following sections, we will explore XAI from a human-centric perspective, identifying crucial components for crafting user-oriented XAI systems. Our aim is to equip the reader with a holistic overview of XAI, setting the stage for deeper explorations in future chapters.

2.1 WHAT IS AN EXPLANATION?

The topic of what constitutes an explanation has long been the subject of debate among philosophers, psychologists, and social scientists. As one delves into this complex dialogue, it becomes evident that while ‘explanation’ might seem like a straightforward term, its precise definition can be elusive.

Ultimately, an explanation is something that allows the user to have a better understanding of a system or event. For the purposes of our discussion, let us consider an explanation as a story that narrates the most relevant parts of the causal history leading to a particular event or phenomenon [89]. The utility of an explanation goes beyond its factual content. It should

be adaptable, designed not only to generalize understanding to similar instances but also to accommodate the specific needs and existing knowledge of the audience. A good explanation strikes a balance between accessibility and fidelity to the subject matter, considering both the methodology of delivery and the context in which it is presented.

At this juncture, it is worth introducing the concept of ‘propedeutics,’ which focuses on the art and science of preparing and arranging instructional materials or methods to assist understanding. In simple terms, propedeutics is about how we prepare and organize explanations to make them understandable. Whether it is between a teacher and a student, or a computer algorithm and a human user, the effectiveness of an explanation relies heavily on the needs and existing knowledge of the receiver. In other words, propedeutics emphasizes that the methodology of delivering the explanation is just as crucial as its content.

To illustrate more concretely the ideas of explanations and propedeutics, imagine standing in front of Picasso’s series of “The Bull” lithographs, as depicted in Figure 2.1. You might view that art piece as an endeavor to capture the essence of what a “bull” truly is, progressing through increasingly abstract levels until only the core essence of what Picasso perceived the animal to be remains. Each frame tells you something different about the bull, yet none give you the full story.

Figure 2.1: Picasso’s “The Bull” series, could be seen as a suggestive metaphor for the art and science of crafting explanations in XAI. The series showcases the progressive simplification and abstraction of a bull, illustrating the trade-offs between complexity and understanding, simplification and generality, between the objective reality and the observer’s interpretation. ¹Image courtesy of DrawPaintAcademy (<https://drawpaintacademy.com/the-bull/>). ²

²In some versions of Picasso’s series, the final frame is not another rendition of the bull, but rather Picasso’s own signature. As if the true final essence of what does it mean to be a bull is Picasso himself. This raises a curious and provoking interpretation: could the ‘true’ essence of the bull—or indeed any complex system—reside in the mind of its observer?

²The use of Picasso’s “The Bull” series in this manuscript is permitted under Article 32, Section 3 of the Spanish Intellectual Property Law (TRLPI), as it constitutes an act of reproduction, distribution and public communication of isolated works of a figurative artistic character, carried out solely for the illustration of educational activities, without a commercial purpose, using works that have already been disclosed, and including the name of the author and the source.

Viewing it in reverse (e.g., from right to left), the artwork serves as a masterclass in propeutics, with Picasso as the instructor. He shows us how to move from a simple, essential depiction to a richer, fuller one that increasingly approximates the experiential perception of a real bull. This parallels the approach often required for effective explanations: starting with a simplified version of reality and progressively refining it until we achieve a satisfactory level of faithfulness. This introduces the notion of ‘faithfulness,’ where we ask ourselves the question: “How well does a simplified representation capture the true essence of the subject?” In XAI, we battle with similar issues, striving to create explanations that balance accessibility with fidelity to the complex workings of the algorithm. The method of delivery, the utility of the explanation for specific questions, and the existing knowledge of the receiver all play a role here.

We therefore strive for descriptions that encapsulate the essence of a specific behavior the user is keen to understand, while allowing for varying degrees of granularity and detail in the communication. The objective is to find which information is requested and to tailor it in such a way that it not only enlightens but also educates. This way, we avoid overwhelming the user with excessive information while still providing the depth and nuance required to satisfy different levels of curiosity and expertise. This balancing act enables us to cater to a broader audience, from novices seeking a general understanding to experts requiring intricate details.

There is in fact no ‘one-size-fits-all’ explanation, and the bulls in the series can be suggestive of the fact that different versions serve different purposes. Imagine for example wanting to understand the anatomical or physiological details of a bull for a biological study. Picasso’s most abstract form, just a few lines, would be entirely inadequate. Similarly, if a machine learning model is employed for clinical diagnosis, a highly abstracted explanation might gloss over essential variables that could be pivotal for patient care.

Conversely, the most abstracted version of Picasso’s bull captures something that more detailed depictions do not: the essence of the bull distilled to its most elemental form. Likewise, in the context of machine learning and XAI, the most abstracted explanations can provide a high-level overview that allows for quick, intuitive understanding. For stakeholders who are not domain experts, such an abstracted explanation might be far more useful than a detailed, technical one. For instance, consider a machine learning model designed for customer segmentation in a retail setting. On the one hand, data scientist might want a full breakdown of the model’s decision-making process to fine-tune its performance. On the other hand, a marketing executive may prefer a simple, abstract explanation that highlights the key customer archetypes the model has identified, alongside any potential fairness or bias issues that could impact the brand’s reputation. For the executive, this abstracted yet comprehensive explanation could be more insightful, allowing for quicker, more informed strategic decisions.

In our exploration of explanations, we have acknowledged the diversity in users’ needs, which naturally points us to a user-centric approach in XAI. This perspective underscores that

Figure 2.2: A human-centric taxonomy of XAI.

explanations should be crafted with the user’s comprehension as the focal point. We will proceed by grounding our discussion in this pragmatic framework, striving to ensure that explanations in XAI are not only effective but also precisely attuned to the audience they are meant to serve. By doing so, we aim to provide insights that are both accessible to non-experts and sufficiently detailed for specialists, thereby facilitating understanding and application across a broad spectrum of users.

2.2 THE USER-CENTRIC PERSPECTIVE OF XAI

XAI is a relatively new field, but it is growing and evolving at an impressive pace. The landscape is filled with a wide range of techniques and needs, making it both broad and deep. What sets XAI apart from the more general realm of machine learning is the active role of the human user. In other words, the focus is not solely on the algorithms themselves but also on how humans can engage with these systems.

This shift in focus has led to the emergence of “user-centric computing”, a concept that prioritizes the human element in machine learning interactions and aligns with the Phenotropic approach (from Greek ‘phainomenon’ for ‘appearance’ and ‘tropos’ for ‘way’), focusing on intuitive, user-friendly interfaces and prioritizing user experience [32, 61, 126].

Given this context, we aim to present a framework for understanding XAI from a user-centric viewpoint. Specifically, we propose to structure the field around a set of essential questions that arise when developing user-focused XAI systems (see Figure 2.2). These questions will be instrumental in identifying key aspects of XAI systems and understanding how the field has evolved to address them.

So, let us start by considering these fundamental questions, which will help us gain a clearer understanding of what user-centric XAI truly entails.

Q1. What Do You Want to Know? (Inquiry - “Understanding User Needs”)

It may seem like an obvious point, but the first critical step in delivering a useful XAI system is to understand what the user wants to know. The challenge here is that different users have diverse needs, curiosities and backgrounds. Identifying these can be less straightforward than one might initially think.

To effectively address this challenge, it is vital to identify the stakeholders and understand their interests in the XAI system. Recognizing the different types of information they require allows us to tailor the explanations accordingly. Aligning with Miller’s framework [89], it is essential to consider who requires the explanation and for what purpose, which often depends on the task at hand and the stakeholders’ needs.

At a high level, explanations in XAI can be divided into two major categories based on their scope: local and global. Local explanations delve into individual predictions, shedding light on the reasoning behind a single data point’s outcome. Global explanations, in contrast, provide a comprehensive view of the model’s overall logic and functioning. There’s also an intermediary category, “group explanations”, which addresses how subsets of data with common features are treated or categorized by the model.

Q2. When/where the explanation is required? (Context - “Understanding Spatio-Temporal Constraints”)

The context in which an explanation is required, encompassing both the spatio-temporal constraints of location (*where?*) and timing (*when?*), can greatly influence its design and delivery. For instance, in time-sensitive situations like decision-making during emergency response, explanations need to be swift and to the point. Conversely, in a more relaxed academic or research setting, detailed and expansive explanations are more feasible and beneficial. Let’s consider a situation where a user is driving a car; in this scenario, the only feasible option may be to listen to the explanation. This condition emphasizes the need for XAI systems to be adaptable, providing explanations through accessible means that suit the user’s current activity or limitations.

Accessibility extends this need further; it is essential to cater to users with disabilities, ensuring that the means and channels of communication are tailored to their requirements. For instance, a visually impaired user would benefit from an audio explanation, while someone who is hearing-impaired might need a text-based or visual representation.

The “when” and “where” aspects of explanation demand also play a significant role. The urgency of a situation may dictate the level of detail and the speed with which an explanation is delivered. For example, real-time decision-making processes require succinct and immediate explanations, while a more relaxed setting allows for detailed and expansive elucidation.

In essence, the context—capturing the “when” and “where”—is as critical as the explanation’s content. It shapes the manner in which the explanation should be crafted and conveyed, ensuring it is not only understood but also practical and applicable in the given situation.

Q3. How Can the System Address Your Question? (Methods - “Explanation Backend”)

With a better understanding of the user’s needs (as discussed in Q1) and the context in which explanations are needed (outlined in Q2), we can now consider the “explanation backend” of an XAI system. This is the part of the system that deals with executing the algorithms responsible for providing the explanations users request. It is a critical component because it directly

affects the system's effectiveness and efficiency in delivering insights. To address the variety of questions from diverse users, XAI systems utilize a range of backend methodologies. These typically fall into two broad categories: model-agnostic and model-specific approaches.

Model-agnostic methods are versatile; they can be applied to almost any system. However, this flexibility comes at a cost: they usually require more computational resources because they operate without any specific assumptions about the model they are explaining. On the flip side, model-specific methods can only be applied to certain types of models, but they offer advantages in computational efficiency. They can leverage the known structure of the model to expedite calculations significantly. This tradeoff between model-agnostic and model-specific methods is not merely a technical detail. It has real implications for how quickly and effectively users can get the explanations they're seeking. Understanding these trade-offs helps in selecting the most appropriate method for a given task, thus making the XAI system more user-centric.

Q4. How Can the System Communicate the Answer? (Interface - "Explanation Frontend")

Once we've settled on the backend method for generating explanations within an XAI system, the next step is to consider how these explanations are communicated to the user. This is where the "explanation frontend", or the interface of the system, comes into focus. The interface involves choosing the modality of the explanation, which refers to the format in which the information is presented. The common modalities include numerical, visual, and textual explanations.

The choice of modality is a crucial one. It needs to resonate with the user's level of expertise, cater to their needs, and fit within the specific context they are operating in. For example, visual or textual explanations may be more accessible and immediately clear to non-technical users, allowing them to grasp complex information more intuitively. These modalities align with the desired granularity of the explanation, providing just the right level of detail to be informative yet comprehensible.

Conversely, users with deeper technical expertise might prefer numerical explanations, which can provide a more precise and detailed quantification of the model's behavior. These users can handle more granular information and often require this level of detail to satisfy their understanding of the system.

But the implications of modality selection go beyond just user preference and extend into inclusivity. A well-designed explanation frontend should consider users with special needs, such as those who are visually impaired, ensuring that the system is accessible to a wider audience. For instance, textual explanations could be accompanied by audio descriptions to cater to users who are visually impaired.

By carefully selecting the modality of the explanation frontend with an eye towards the granularity of the information and the inclusivity of the format, we ensure that the XAI system

is not only informative but also user-friendly and accessible to all potential users. **Q5. Are You Satisfied with the Results? (Evaluation - “Assessing the Goodness and Effectiveness of Explanations”)**

The final step involves evaluating the quality and effectiveness of the explanations provided. This is a non-trivial task that raises important questions: How do we measure “understandability” or the overall usefulness of an explanation? How faithful is the explanation to the underlying model? What metrics should we use to evaluate different types of explanations?

Addressing these questions is crucial as it shapes both how the AI system generates explanations and how those explanations are conveyed to the user. Moreover, it informs the evaluation process, ensuring that the explanations produced are not just technically accurate but also useful and satisfactory to the end user.

In the sections that follow, we will dig deeper into each component of this taxonomy. We will start by exploring the different types of XAI models and their roles in various systems (Section 2.3). From there, we will examine how different data types are managed and delve into strategies for effectively presenting (Section 2.4) and communicating (Section 2.5) explanations. Then, we will go in depth with evaluation strategies (Section 2.6) and the chapter will end with some concluding remarks (Section 2.7).

2.3 WHO ARE THE USERS OF XAI?

As hinted before, recognizing user diversity is not just advantageous; it is a necessity. Users bring a range of questions, levels of technical expertise, and learning styles to the table. Given this diversity, generic explanations are unlikely to serve everyone effectively. XAI systems should also be designed with inclusivity in mind, accommodating users with disabilities to ensure equitable access to explanations.

This variation among users complicates the task of evaluating XAI systems. Traditional metrics, often focused on technical aspects like model accuracy or explanation fidelity, fall short of capturing other critical elements such as user comprehension, satisfaction, and the practical utility of the explanation.

In essence, XAI takes on a role similar to that of an educator. Its goal is not merely to provide information, but to ensure that the information is both understood and actionable for the user. Thus, an efficient XAI system functions much like an automated teacher, adapting its content and presentation style to meet individual user needs.

To be truly effective, the system needs to consider several user-centric factors: the users’ preferred method of communication, prior knowledge, and specific questions or concerns. By doing so, the system not only maintains technical robustness but also resonates with each user, fulfilling the core objective of transparency and usability.

2.3.1 Stakeholders Analysis

Now that we have established the significance of tailoring explanations to the user, it is time to get specific. Who exactly are these ‘users’ in the context of XAI? Different stakeholders bring their own unique questions and challenges. Below, we categorize and describe key stakeholder groups, highlighting the types of questions each is likely to pose.

- **Individuals Impacted by Autonomous Decisions:** These users are directly influenced by the decisions made by AI models. They often seek to understand the rationale behind these decisions and may inquire their fairness. A typical question they might pose is: “Is this decision fair, and how can I change an unfavorable outcome?” Counterfactual explanations respond to such queries by suggesting ways in which altering certain input factors could lead to a different, potentially more favorable decision. This kind of explanation is crucial as it provides actionable insights that can help users feel a greater sense of equity and influence over the outcomes that affect them [18].
- **Domain Experts:** These professionals are chiefly concerned with how well the model’s decisions or recommendations align with established guidelines, norms, and best practices in their specific fields. They value explanations that provide a blend of methodological rigor, operational efficiency, and long-term viability, often seeking to understand how the model complements or challenges existing domain knowledge [18, 144].
- **Workers at Regulatory Entities:** Regulatory bodies require explanations that meet the rigor of legal standards. Their questions may focus on compliance, such as “Is the model in line with existing laws?” Detailed, exhaustive explanations are paramount in offering a comprehensive understanding of the model’s operations, ensuring they adhere to lawful principles. This deep insight is crucial in reducing the risk of legal actions, as it demonstrates due diligence in aligning the model’s functionality with regulatory requirements [18].
- **Data Scientists and Developers:** These stakeholders are primarily interested in the model’s internal coherence, generalizability, and potential for knowledge discovery. They ask questions like, “Is the model making decisions for the right reasons?”, “Are there any spurious correlations that need to be pruned?”, or “Has the model uncovered any insights that were previously invisible using traditional tools?”. Feature importance scores and sensitivity tests are pivotal for debugging and refinement, while XAI provides an avenue for new discoveries and validation against common or expert knowledge. This aids in both their technical work and in broadening the understanding of the model’s capabilities and limitations [144].

- **Managers and Executives:** This group takes a broader view, questioning the overall implications of the AI governance for the organization. They might inquire, “What are the larger organizational impacts of this model? Does it operate within legal and business boundaries?” Furthermore, they are also concerned with ethical considerations and potential biases within the model, posing questions like, “How does the model handle ethical considerations? Are there biases we need to be aware of?” These users seek explanations that offer both technical depth and a broader business perspective, ensuring the model’s operation is strategically aligned and ethically sound [18, 144].

This broad spectrum of user needs and questions highlights the need for a tailored approach for each stakeholder. It emphasizes the flexibility that must be built into both the content and delivery strategy of explanations. We will delve deeper into how this tailoring can be effectively implemented in subsequent sections.

2.3.2 Scope of Explanation

The scope of an explanation determines the breadth and depth of the information it will contain, setting boundaries for its content and the approach taken to provide it. Essentially, this “scope” tackles the crucial question: “What range of detail is necessary for this explanation to be considered complete?”

- **Local Scope:** Here, the focus is on individual, context-specific decisions [77]. Local scope addresses the extent to which specific features or decisions in a given situation contribute to the model’s output. It is like looking at a single piece of a puzzle to understand its specific role. This is particularly useful for stakeholders who are directly impacted by specific model decisions or who need to understand the model’s behavior in very particular contexts. They may want to know, for example, “Why was my loan application denied?”
- **Global Scope:** In contrast, the global scope is more about general patterns, trends, or biases in the model across a wide range of contexts [37]. It is like viewing the entire puzzle to understand the overarching theme. This is vital for stakeholders who are interested in the model’s overall performance or who are assessing its general impact. They might ask, “Is this model fair across different demographic groups?”

By defining the scope, we establish the “reach” of our explanations, making sure that they are neither too narrow to be unhelpful nor too broad to be overwhelming. Understanding the scope is a foundational step in creating explanations that are both meaningful and manageable.

2.4 METHODS FOR PROVIDING EXPLANATIONS

Once we have a clear understanding of the user’s needs and the scope of the task, the focus shifts to pinpointing the specific “content” that will meet those needs. This is a critical juncture where we delve into the algorithms capable of generating the information the user seeks. Essentially, we are tasked with calculating the **content** of an explanation—the nuts and bolts of the information to be conveyed. This might include technical elements like feature importance scores, or more intuitive components like counterfactual cases and prototype examples. The term “Content” encapsulates the core of the message we are delivering. It answers the “what” and “why”, offering the exact details that the user is looking for.

We can distinguish between two general categories of methods for achieving this: model-agnostic and model-specific methods. Model-agnostic methods are versatile, applicable to a wide variety of models. However, their generality often requires higher computational resources. On the other hand, model-specific methods are tailored for specific types of models, which allows for more efficient computation by taking advantage of model-specific characteristics.

This topic will be elaborated on in greater detail in the technical taxonomy later in the next chapter.

2.5 COMMUNICATION OF THE EXPLANATION

While crafting the content is often given significant attention, the step of devising an effective communication strategy should not be underestimated, as it is essential for ensuring the system’s utility and effectiveness. To accomplish this, we need to carefully consider not only the types of modalities available for delivering the content but also a strategic plan for employing them. Additionally, the structure of the content—or set of contents—must be carefully planned to optimize understanding and utility.

By giving due importance to the communication strategy, we set the stage for the explanation system to be not just technically sound but also practically effective through a user-friendly interface.

2.5.1 Explanation Modalities

Explanation modality serves as the critical interface between machine logic and human intuition. In this subsection, we explore the different formats or channels through which explanations can be conveyed, ranging from visual graphics to natural language descriptions.

1. **Numerical:** This modality involves presenting explanations through numbers, percentages, and mathematical expressions. Its strength lies in precision and quantifiability.

However, its effectiveness can be limited by the user's comfort with and understanding of mathematical concepts.

2. **Visual:** The visual modality excels in rich informational content by leveraging the human capacity for high-bandwidth visual processing. It can communicate complex relationships, trends, and patterns effectively. However, this richness can be a double-edged sword. It introduces the challenges of interpretation variability and an expertise barrier. Different viewers may focus on different elements within a visual representation, which can lead to varied interpretations. Moreover, a specialized level of understanding is often required to decode visual data effectively.
3. **Textual:** The strength of textual modality lies in its explicitness. Messages are well-defined and straightforward, requiring no additional inference from the user. However, this modality also presents its own set of challenges, such as balancing information density and narrative structure. While it is crucial to provide enough details to avoid misinterpretation, excessive information can overwhelm the user. Textual explanations must also be logically organized to avoid vagueness and ambiguity while ensuring. The creation of such explanations can involve two primary techniques: template-based and generative methods.

Template-based methods rely on predefined text structures that are populated with data relevant to the specific case at hand. These templates are consistent, ensuring that the explanation is clear and reliable each time. The limitation here is in the lack of variability; the explanations can become repetitive or may not capture the nuances of different scenarios effectively [113].

Generative methods, on the other hand, produce language that can dynamically adjust to the given context, potentially offering more expressive and varied explanations. These methods can be designed in modular or end-to-end formats. Modular approaches segment the explanation generation into distinct steps, such as content determination and linguistic realization, which allows for fine-tuned control over each aspect of the output. End-to-end methods, in contrast, take a holistic approach, generating explanations from input data in one go without distinct intermediate steps [60, 36]. Despite this flexibility, they come with significant drawbacks. There is less control over the exact content generated, which can sometimes result in explanations that are less precise or even misleading. Additionally, generative methods can produce errors or “hallucinations,” where the generated text includes plausible-sounding but incorrect or unfounded information. This issue necessitates careful oversight and potentially more rigorous validation to ensure the accuracy and trustworthiness of the explanations.

Both template-based and generative models aim to create understandable and relevant textual explanations for users, but they differ significantly in their approach to flexibility and naturalness of the generated language.

Unlike the traditional modalities enumerated above, there is one that is not properly a modality but can be extremely useful in the context of XAI: Interactive interfaces [31]. Tools like dashboards, sliders, and widgets function as a composite layer, amalgamating elements from numerical, visual, and textual modalities. This allows for real-time engagement and immediate feedback, fostering a more nuanced and adaptive understanding of the system. This approach's efficacy is underlined by a study where a dynamic visual interface improved satisfaction among non-expert healthcare users, suggesting its potential to democratize AI understanding [66]. As such, Interactive interfaces can be considered a *meta-modality* that enriches and augments traditional forms of explanation.

2.5.2 Strategy

Having explored the various modalities for explanation, the next step is to focus on the strategy that ties them together. Choosing the right modality or a combination of modalities is just the beginning. The order in which this information is presented is equally critical.

Propaedeutics, offering principles that are particularly useful in this context, suggests starting with the most essential information and then gradually adding more layers. This approach is supported by research such as that of [74], who found that propaedeutic learning in elementary mathematics education leads to significantly better results compared to students who do not use this method. The study highlights the effectiveness of introducing fundamental concepts first, thereby enhancing overall comprehension and learning outcomes.

Interactive systems can also benefit from a feedback loop of questions and answers to adjust the information in real-time. This can be particularly effective when combined with a propaedeutic approach, as it allows for the continuous assessment of the user's understanding and the adaptation of content accordingly.

When multiple contents are available, the strategy also involves deciding what to present initially and what can be introduced later. An often-overlooked aspect of this strategic layer is the need to gauge the user's level of understanding. A mental map or model of the user's mind can be invaluable for optimizing communication, ensuring that the strategy is tailored to meet the user's specific comprehension needs.

2.6 EVALUATING XAI: CHALLENGES AND APPROACHES

Evaluation is crucial in science, and it is no different in the field of XAI. But when it comes to assessing the goodness and effectiveness of explanations, the task is not trivial. The complexity

arises from the multiple parts that make up an XAI system: the machine learning model that processes data, the logic that decides what information gets presented as an explanation, and the interface that displays this information to a user [148].

As we said before, different users may have various goals based on their roles and responsibilities, further complicating the evaluation process. For example, someone in regulatory compliance may focus on model transparency, while a data scientist may be more interested in the model's predictive accuracy. Thus, it is clear that evaluating an XAI system is not a one-off task but a multi-layered process that demands careful thought and planning.

If we are serious about improving these systems, evaluation cannot be an afterthought; it must be an integral part of development. The end goal is not just to assess parts of the system in isolation but to understand how effective the whole system is in practical, real-world applications. This brings us to a key point: while individual metrics can give us some valuable insights, they are not enough by their own. Objective, automated metrics are a good starting point, but they have their limits and need to be supplemented by human-based evaluation methods to get a comprehensive view.

In the next sections, we will dig deeper into the specifics of objective evaluation methods, discussing their advantages and disadvantages, to build a full understanding of how they fit into the broader XAI evaluation landscape.

2.6.1 Objective Evaluation of Interpretability Metrics

Objective evaluation methods offer a straightforward, often cost-effective way to assess the interpretability of an XAI system. These methods can be standardized and are therefore highly repeatable, allowing for consistency in measurement across different setups and timeframes. The quantitative nature of objective metrics also lends itself to precision, providing detailed insights that can be easily compared or scaled up as needed.

While objective metrics are indispensable for initial evaluations and for setting up performance baselines, they are not the final arbiter of a system's interpretability. These metrics should be considered as part of a broader evaluation strategy that also incorporates human-centric evaluations for a more comprehensive view. For an in-depth understanding of the strengths and limitations of these objective metrics, see Table 2.1, which outlines the pros and cons of various properties of objective evaluation methods.

2.6.2 Human Evaluation

Evaluating XAI from a human-centric perspective takes on heightened importance because, at its core, the utility of XAI hinges on its comprehensibility and usefulness to people [41]. Audience type plays a central role in this evaluation process. For instance, a domain expert immersed in

Table 2.1: Objective Evaluation of Interpretability Metrics: Pros and Cons.

Property	Pros	Cons
<i>Cost-Effectiveness</i>	Economical due to minimal computational resource requirements, making them feasible for large-scale evaluations.	Initial setup can be complex and, in some cases, may incur additional costs.
<i>Precision and Granularity</i>	Offers high accuracy and detail in what they measure, providing clear, quantifiable insights.	May focus too narrowly, missing broader context and qualitative factors, such as human understanding.
<i>Repeatability and Consistency</i>	Allow for consistent application and comparison across various systems and at different points in time.	Can be inflexible, not adapting well to evolving evaluation requirements or contexts.
<i>Quantitative Nature</i>	Facilitates straightforward comparison and statistical analysis, making them ideal for standardized evaluations.	Quantitative focus may overlook essential qualitative aspects, especially the lack of alignment with human context and expectations.
<i>Scalability</i>	Suitable for both small and large-scale projects without significant changes to the evaluation process.	Scaling up can sometimes miss specific nuances or complexities of larger, more intricate systems.

data science may appreciate a detailed breakdown of feature contributions to an AI decision, whereas a layperson might just need a simpler, more intuitive explanation. In essence, knowing your audience allows you to tailor the evaluation metrics and methods accordingly [33].

For both human and automatic evaluations, methodologies can be broadly classified into intrinsic and extrinsic types. Intrinsic evaluations examine the quality of the explanation itself, focusing on the internal mechanics and faithfulness of the system or model—does the explanation accurately reflect the model’s operations? Extrinsic evaluations, on the other hand, measure the impact of the explanation on the user’s ability to perform real-world tasks, emphasizing a task-oriented or task-embedded perspective.

When it comes to metrics, the game changes yet again. Qualitative metrics like believability, usefulness, and clarity enter the arena. These are the subtle, often intangible, aspects that objective metrics struggle to capture. To make things more complex, one could introduce quantitative measures like time spent on the task or the accuracy with which tasks are completed following the explanation. While these add an additional layer of rigor, they also introduce more variables to consider.

However, human evaluations are not without their difficulties. They are time-consuming and resource-intensive, which makes them less than ideal for quick, iterative developments—a luxury that objective evaluations often afford. Moreover, setting up a methodologically sound human evaluation is easier said than done and can introduce its own biases or limitations. A critical concern, as noted in [21], is the reproducibility of human evaluations. Their study found that only about 5% of human evaluations in NLP are repeatable, with worryingly low degrees of reproducibility in terms of both similarity of scores and supported findings, highlighting the challenge of ensuring consistent and replicable results in human-led assessments.

In high-stakes applications like healthcare, these human-centric evaluations become not just beneficial but essential [147, 50]. The cost of an error here could be a matter of life and death, making the investment in human evaluation a non-negotiable. Crucially, in this context, it is not enough to just evaluate; what is needed is a detailed “Error Analysis.” This process is focused on dissecting and understanding specific mistakes made by the system, rather than merely aggregating error rates. Such an analysis is key to identifying why and how individual errors occur, enabling targeted improvements and fixes [19, 134].

2.6.3 Challenges in XAI Evaluation

Evaluating XAI systems presents multiple hurdles, each with its unique nuances. A primary obstacle is the tendency to simplify test environments, which may not capture the full range of complexities that models will face in real-world applications.

Another common issue is the introduction of biases in the evaluation, which could be in the form of favoring specific models or use-cases. Such biases can severely limit the applicability and generalizability of the evaluation results.

One particularly deceptive pitfall is the over-optimization for specific metrics. This is problematic because an overemphasis on a single metric can lead to a model that performs exceptionally well in that particular aspect but falls short in other important areas. It can cause developers to produce models that are highly specialized but lack versatility and broad applicability. Therefore, a more holistic evaluation strategy that accounts for multiple facets of explainability is recommended.

Lastly, human evaluations can often introduce inconsistencies due to a variety of factors such as differing interpretations, cognitive biases, or even the sample size and demographic of the study group. These inconsistencies make it difficult to draw robust conclusions based on such evaluations.

In summary, the evaluation of XAI systems is fraught with challenges that necessitate a careful, balanced, and multi-faceted approach.

2.7 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This chapter has taken a human-centric perspective on XAI, an essential stance to ensure the transparency and relevance of AI technology to all users. By shifting from opaque AI systems to transparent AI systems, we meet not only ethical and regulatory needs but also foster greater trust and collaboration across various user groups. We have focused on adaptable explanations that resonate with different levels of user knowledge and curiosity, emphasizing the importance of context and the variety in communication of explanations. Balancing the depth of explanations to be both meaningful and comprehensive has also been a key topic, alongside the imperative of developing robust evaluation methods that integrate objective analysis with subjective human judgment.

As we move forward, the next chapter will pivot to a more technical perspective on XAI, exploring the mathematical and computational foundations that enable these systems. We will dissect the contrast between black-box and white-box approaches, examine different data types, and dedicate a significant section to the most influential post-hoc methods of feature attribution importance. This will provide a foundation for understanding the intricate mechanics that make XAI work from a developer's viewpoint. By exploring these technical details, we will illuminate how they influence the user experience, aiming to equip readers with a nuanced understanding of XAI. This knowledge is vital for developers who are constructing these systems and for end-users who seek to understand the foundations of the AI decisions that increasingly affect their lives. Bridging the gap between the human and technical narratives, we strive for a holistic understanding of XAI, ensuring that the systems we rely on are not only intelligent and efficient but also aligned with our values and comprehensible in their actions and judgments.

3 A Technical Overview of the XAI Landscape

Having revisited the field from the perspective of the users and having understood their central role in shaping the final system, it is now appropriate to dive deeper into the technical view of XAI. For doing so we will introduce some models, data and explanation methods that are to be used later in the rest of chapters of this doctoral dissertation

3.1 TYPES AND ROLES OF XAI MODELS

AI models, particularly those designed with machine learning algorithms, can be broadly categorized into two types based on their interpretability: black-box models and white-box models. Each type plays specific roles within XAI and comes with its own set of benefits and limitations.

3.1.1 Black-Box Models

In both engineering and machine learning, the concept of the ‘black box’ serves as a useful abstraction for systems whose internal complexities are either irrelevant or too intricate to comprehend fully. Take the example of an automobile: one does not need to understand the intricate thermodynamics or engineering behind the engine to know that pressing the accelerator propels the car forward. If one is interested in understanding the causal relationship between accelerator and the car moving, one have to ‘open the black box’, studying how different subsystems achieve a specific aim and how systemically they whole work to produce the desired effect. Similarly, machine learning algorithms such as Random Forests are often dubbed ‘black boxes’

Figure 3.1: A black-box system is one in which the internal mechanics are either unknown or deliberately obscured. This focuses attention solely on the relationship between input and output, disregarding the complexities within. While this approach can make the system easier to use or analyze from an external perspective, it also limits the ability to fine-tune or troubleshoot the system's internal behavior.

Figure 3.2: A white box system is characterized by its transparency in internal mechanics, thereby allowing for predictable and comprehensible collective behavior. This is in contrast to a black-box system, where the internal workings are unknown or obscured. The clarity in a white box system fosters ease of analysis, modification, and troubleshooting.

not because their mechanisms are unknown—we are fully aware they comprise an ensemble of decision trees and we know how each tree works—but because the sheer complexity makes it practically impossible to read through all the decision trees and form a coherent narrative. While one could note that the mechanism of a car moving could be better understood than the behaviour of a random forest, the main point is that every system has some inherent complexity and when we refer to them as black boxes what we are doing is ignoring many of the details of their inner working, focusing only on the fact that the ‘box’ has some input and responds with some output. The ability of ‘making sense’ of a black box is dependent on both in the complexity of the underlying system and on the computational and cognitive capacity of the observer who seeks to understand the system.

From a pragmatic standpoint, models are labeled as ‘black boxes’ when their construction and decision-making process are far removed from what a human would consider intuitive or interpretable. Such models include, but are not limited to, Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, Convolutional Neural Networks, Transformers, Generative Adversarial Networks and Long Short-Term Memory networks. Additionally, it is worth noting that some models, like deep neural networks, reside in a realm of complexity where even though we could inspect every parameter and intermediate activation, we would still be far from a comprehensive understanding of the model.

3.1.2 White-Box Models

In stark contrast to black-box models are ‘white box’ models, designed with the explicit intent of interpretability and transparency. Classic examples include linear regression, logistic regression, decision trees, and rule-based methods—where the model is essentially a well-defined set of rules. In these models, each parameter, rule, or decision node is directly interpretable, often mapping neatly onto human-understandable concepts. This 100% faithfulness in the explanation is particularly crucial in high-stakes scenarios like healthcare and banking, where model errors can have immediate and profound impacts on human life and societal structures. Importantly, the explanation is not an approximation but a direct reflection of the model’s decision-making

process.

However, it is worth mentioning an interesting ‘grey zone’: even models that are fundamentally interpretable can become practically uninterpretable when applied to large datasets. For example, a linear model with millions of features becomes incomprehensible, not because of its structure, but due to the cognitive limitations of human observers. Here, the notion of ‘interpretability’ gets blurred, showing that the line between black and white boxes may sometimes be a shade of grey, influenced not just by model architecture but also by the scale at which it is applied.

3.2 WHEN TO GO FOR BLACK-BOX OR WHITE-BOX MODELS

We have already covered the features and behaviors of Black Box and White Box models. But a pressing question remains: Which model is right for your specific task? The answer is often task-specific, contingent on the stakes involved, and pivots on the performance of the models in question. There is no one-size-fits-all solution, and the best practices are largely dependent on the nuances of the task at hand. To help navigate this choice, refer to the decision chart in figure 3.3 based on the following guidelines:

Figure 3.3: A decision chart to assist practitioners in choosing the most suitable modeling approach.

1. **High Stakes vs. Low Stakes Contexts:** The most foundational question in choosing between black-box and white-box models is what is at stake. When the consequences of a wrong decision have far-reaching implications—financial, societal, or even life-altering—the demand for full transparency and understanding of the model becomes of paramount relevance. In such high-stakes scenarios, a white-box model gains precedence, not just for its predictive abilities but also for its “faithfulness”, the term often used to indicate how closely an explanation mirrors the actual model mechanics. A useful question

to ask for sensing how important is explainability for a given task is: “What are the implications of a mistake on the behalf of the model?”

- *Example of high stake*: In healthcare, if a model incorrectly predicts patient outcomes and those outcomes have life-threatening consequences, the cost of an error is immeasurably high. The model is not just making a recommendation; it is essentially making an automated decision that can have irreversible outcomes. Here, a white box model is critical for risk management, ethical compliance, and informed decision-making. With such high stakes it would be not advisable to rely on accurate black box, even if one have very faithful post-hoc explanations available, because by definition such post hoc explanations are *approximations* that need to be interpreted, and this could lead to potentially dangerous misinterpretations. Conversely with a white-box model, one gets an explanation that is exactly how the model processed the data.
- *Example of low stake*: In a music recommendation system, the consequences are minimal if the model selects a less-than-ideal song; the user can simply skip it. In this case, the white box model’s transparency is not a crucial factor, allowing you to move on to other considerations in your decision-making process.

2. **Comparable Performance**: If white-box models perform on par with black-box models, the logical inclination would be toward the white boxes. This is because they offer an additional layer of assurance through interpretability without sacrificing performance. On the other hand, there may be scenarios where predictive performance of the black-box model is significantly higher and so critical that a black-box model becomes a more suitable option, especially if white-box models fall short of achieving satisfying results. In such a case, a white-box model is not admissible. Conversely, a black-box model becomes the smart choice, even if it means that the explanations are approximate rather than fully faithful.

- *Example of comparable performance*: For instance, in credit scoring, if a logistic regression (a white-box model) performs as well as a neural network (a black box), the former would be the best choice for its comprehensibility and ease of validation.
- *Example of black box being better*: In real-time fraud detection, speed and accuracy are of the essence. If a black-box model can identify fraudulent transactions with higher accuracy in milliseconds, its use could be justified even if it lacks full interpretability.

The journey of choosing between a black-box and a white-box model is multifaceted. It is not a binary choice but a nuanced one that balances technical efficiency, ethical considerations,

and real-world consequences. While the reflection points above provide a guide, it is essential to remember that these are not hard rules but guiding principles, adaptable according to the specific nature of the problem at hand.

3.3 DATA TYPES IN XAI

Data, the lifeblood of machine learning systems, can present itself in various forms—each raising unique challenges and opportunities for XAI. This data universe can be broadly classified into three foundational categories, each encompassing a range of data types with shared characteristics. Firstly, **Relational/Structured Data** is exemplified by structured, rectangular database-like data. It is characterized by its organized, tabular format and strict adherence to schema. Secondly, **Spatial Data** is where the physical arrangement and proximity of data points are paramount. While vision data, such as images and videos, is a prominent example, this category extends to include geographical information systems (GIS) data, LiDAR data, and even 3D modeling data. These types share key features like spatial relationships, matrix-like structures, and the importance of spatial invariance. Lastly, **Sequential Data** emphasizes the significance of order and sequence. Natural language data is a notable example, with its sequential arrangement of words and phrases. This category also embraces time series data, which, like language, unfolds over time and reveals patterns and dependencies in its progression. Genetic data, with its complex sequences, also fits well within this category, highlighting the shared attribute of sequentiality across diverse domains.

Of these broad categories there are mainly three types we will focus on: structured data, vision data, and natural language data.

3.3.1 Relational/Structured Data

Structured data are commonly found in tabular form, being prevalent across various domains such as industry, healthcare, finance, and criminal justice. Each column in the table typically represents a specific feature, which can be either continuous or categorical. While it is often assumed that these features are independent of each other, real-world datasets frequently demonstrate correlations between features in the distribution from which the data can be assumed to have been generated.

This data modality is especially popular in industries and process-oriented businesses due to its compact and easily manageable format. When the features are interpretable, it is possible to build a model that not only identifies relationships but also provides a narrative explanation. However, if the semantics of the features is unknown, the explanatory power of XAI methods is limited to identifying relationships between features, without the ability to craft a comprehensive narrative.

Commonly used XAI techniques for structured data include white-box models like decision trees, non-gradient-based feature attribution scores, prototype example-based explanations and counterfactuals. Challenges in applying XAI to structured data involve crafting appropriate similarity or perturbation functions for differing features and addressing the limitations of gradient-based methods for features like ZIP codes, which do not have a meaningful gradient.

Understanding the characteristics and limitations of structured data is crucial for selecting and implementing XAI techniques that provide meaningful and accurate explanations.

3.3.2 Vision Data

Vision data, primarily composed of images (and their progress through time, videos), presents a unique landscape for XAI that diverges significantly from structured data. One of the most distinguishing characteristics of vision data is that it consists of pixels with various intensity values. More critically, these pixels exhibit a high degree of local correlation, meaning the value of a pixel is often closely related to its neighboring pixels.

This local correlation poses a challenge to many traditional XAI methods that operate under the assumption that features are independent and identically distributed (IID). When these IID-based methods are applied to vision data, they may yield misleading or uninformative results, as they fail to account for the interdependence of pixels.

However, this limitation has led to the development and application of more sophisticated XAI techniques that can handle such local correlations. Concept-based explanations, for instance, focus on higher-level constructs in the image rather than individual pixels [44, 51]. Additionally, specific feature attribution methods have been designed to consider not just individual pixels but local regions, thereby providing a more accurate and interpretable explanation.

Commonly used XAI methods for vision data include feature importance scores, concept-based explanations, and, more recently, mechanistic explanations that aim to model the underlying mechanics or structures inherent in the visual data.

3.3.3 Natural Language Data

Natural language data, typically represented as text, is fundamentally different from structured and vision data in several key ways. Unlike the continuous pixel values in images or the numerical and categorical values in structured data, text is tokenized into discrete units such as words or smaller components (sometimes called subwords).

One of the most noteworthy features of natural language data is its variable length, which stands in contrast to the fixed dimensions usually observed in images and tables. Additionally, text data exhibits complex correlations that are not only local but also long-range, spanning from grammatical conventions to more abstract structures like chains of reasoning.

Figure 3.4: From a technical point of view, XAI can be seen as the effort to understand the inner workings of white-box models, or the set of techniques that allow us to draw conclusions from the output of black-box models (post-hoc explanations).

The realm of natural language processing has been greatly influenced by neural network approaches, particularly transformer architectures. These models aim to hierarchically capture the relationships between tokens by utilizing a quadratic attention map, offering a robust method for dealing with both local and long-range dependencies. Although neural networks often map these discrete tokens into a continuous embedding space to facilitate modeling, the native discreteness of text data poses unique challenges and opportunities for XAI.

This native discreteness, along with the variable lengths and complex dependencies, not only influences the construction of machine learning models but also the strategies for XAI. Gradient-based explanations, commonly used for continuous data types, are not directly applicable due to the discrete nature of text. Moreover, the intricacies of text data make it challenging to develop universal similarity or perturbation functions for explanations.

Understanding these distinct properties is crucial for developing XAI strategies that deliver meaningful and accurate explanations in natural language processing.

3.4 BLACK-BOX POST-HOC EXPLANATIONS

Given the different data and tasks and models, XAI can be seen from a technical perspective as in Figure 3.4. As we have previously noted, there are fundamentally two types of models: white-box and black-box models. XAI aims to extract explainable content from these models in distinct ways. For white-box models, explanations can be drawn directly from their internal structures, whether that involves a list of rules, a set of coefficients, or other mechanisms. On the other hand, for black-box models where the internal workings are not directly accessible, the focus is on perturbing the input and observing the resulting output to generate explanations.

In this section, we will go deeper with how to explain black-box models, regarding their unique challenges and opportunities.

Black-box models are prevalent across numerous domains, often due to their competitive predictive performance. As we discussed in section [3.1.1](#), black-box models are complex in a way that often defies easy or exact explanation. At the heart of this complexity is the fact that these models can have millions of parameters, non-linear transformations, and intricate decision boundaries that cannot be easily distilled into simple terms. This complexity often mirrors the complexity of the phenomena they are modeling, but it also creates a barrier to understanding the model itself. In other words what can often happen is that these models have a behavior that is so rich that it can not be captured perfectly in a simpler, easily understandable explanation. This can be seen as a consequence of the principle of “computational irreducibility”, [\[67\]](#), [\[138\]](#) which states that some systems have a behavior that is so complex that you can not shortcut the computational process to predict their outcomes—you have to go through every computational step. In the context of black-box models, this means that there may not be a “simpler” way to fully understand the model; you would have to go through all its complexities to get a complete picture, which is not practical or feasible for human understanding. This means that we will most likely need approximations when we try to explain them. However, every approximation comes with a cost: the simpler we make the explanation, the less precisely it describes the model’s actual behavior.

This naturally leads to the following question: How true is this simplified version to the model’s actual behavior? This quality measure, known as “faithfulness”, is particularly relevant for black-box models. Faithfulness assesses the degree to which an explanation reflects the true reasoning process of the model. It is not a binary attribute; instead, it exists on a spectrum. In light of this discussion one could make the point that every explanation for black boxes is in some sense unfaithful by definition, given the potentially complex, non-linear nature of these models. This said, more often than not, appropriate approximations are sufficient to satisfy most needs and for being effective. Therefore, the challenge is not to achieve perfect faithfulness, but rather to determine an acceptable degree of unfaithfulness for each specific task. This degree of acceptable faithfulness may vary across different models, tasks, and even specific instances within those tasks. Where to place this threshold and how to measure it quantitatively are open questions; later in this manuscript, we will explore studies that propose methods for assessing and measuring faithfulness in a more structured manner.

Despite these challenges, there is a sustained interest in developing effective post-hoc explanation methods for black-box models. These models have been integrated deeply into machine learning practices and may sometimes be indispensable for certain complex tasks.

When dealing with black boxes, the only real option is to look at the relationship between the inputs you feed into the system and the outputs it generates. Approaches that focus solely on these input-output relationships are known as Post Hoc methods. In the following subsections, we will delve into various post-hoc explanation methods.

3.4.1 Model Surrogation

The idea of model surrogation is creating an interpretable model $g(\cdot)$ that behaves as closely as possible to the black box we want to understand $f(\cdot)$ and then inspect this interpretable model. By examining this surrogate model, we can get insights into the original black-box model, as illustrated in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: A Visual Depiction of Model Surrogation: Creating an Interpretable Surrogate to Understand a Black-box Model.

There are two types of surrogate models: global and local. A global surrogate seeks to approximate the black-box model across its entire data distribution, whereas a local surrogate focuses on approximating the model’s behavior around specific data points. This strategy is particularly useful when the original black-box model is inaccessible due to security or logistical reasons, and is only available for use at a specific inference point. Importantly, it is not necessary to have the original training data of the black-box model. Let’s assume we have a model f (let the task be classification without loss of generality, similar considerations can be done for regression). One can generate a new dataset, denoted as \mathcal{B} , which could be random or task-specific, and then apply the black-box model f to produce labels. Formally, this can be expressed as:

$$y_{blackbox} = f(\mathcal{B}) \quad (3.1)$$

The surrogate model is then trained using \mathcal{B} and $y_{blackbox}$. While having access to the original data distribution would enable a more accurate approximation, this method remains effective even when only a dataset and corresponding labels generated by the black-box model are available.

TREPAN [34, 35] is a model surrogation approach where the black box f is surrogated by a decision tree. Specifically the training algorithm populate appropriate data samples and labels (thanks to f) whenever a decision branch is populated.

3.4.2 Feature Impact Scores

Within the realm of Post-Hoc Explanation methods, another particularly useful family of methods focuses on what is called “feature importance.” These methods aim to assign a score to each input feature, quantifying its impact on the model’s output. This is where Feature Impact Scores come into play (also called feature importance scores, feature attribution attribution scores). These scores measure the influence of each feature on the outcome, and the best part is that you can apply this method across a wide range of models and data types.

However, there is a subtlety: the term “impactful” or “important” is not straightforward to define because its meaning can be formalised in different ways. Various mathematical methods can be employed to calculate these scores, and each method may lend a different semantic meaning to the terms “impactful” or “important.” So, if one uses Feature Impact Scores to interpret a model, it is crucial to be clear about what kind of “impactfulness” is computed.

This ambiguity notwithstanding, Feature Impact Scores have demonstrated their usefulness in practical scenarios. They have been especially effective in debugging algorithms and identifying biases in data. For example, in a classification task considered very challenging—specifically, differentiating between pictures labeled “husky” and “wolf”—practitioners discovered that the model was capitalizing on an unintentional bias in the dataset (see Figure 11 in [114]). Huskies were consistently photographed in domestic settings, whereas wolves appeared with snowy backgrounds. Consequently, the classifier effectively became a “snow detector”, a much simpler task that yielded surprisingly accurate results on that particular dataset [114]. In another work [122], a broad array of other success stories is presented, such as the revelation that models trained on the IMDB-WIKI dataset to predict a person’s age from a photograph were treating the presence of a smile as an indicator of youth.

3.4.3 Computational Trade-offs in Post-Hoc Explanations

Although the definition of a black box that we propose implies complete ignorance about the type and inner workings of the model (at least from the user’s perspective), this assumption can be relaxed to create post-hoc explanation *tools* that are either **model-agnostic** or **model-specific**. This means that even though the model remains a black box in the sense that its inner workings are not yet interpretable, by specifying a particular class of models, we can find more computationally efficient ways to calculate Feature Attribution Scores.

There exists a trade-off between the computational requirements of Feature Attribution Scores methods and the level of assumptions we make about a specific model. On one end of the spectrum, there are model-agnostic methods, which apply universally and make no assumptions about the model’s behavior. While these methods have the advantage of broad applicability, they often come with heavy computational costs because they must, in essence, ‘learn’ the model

from scratch. On the opposite end, there are model-specific methods designed for certain types of black boxes. These methods leverage the known structures and components of particular models to generate explanations more efficiently.

Often, it is the latter class of methods that yield the most meaningful insights. By producing explanations at a higher throughput, these methods allow for the aggregation of multiple individual explanations to form a comprehensive global understanding in a time that would be otherwise unfeasible. Achieving this with model-agnostic methods can be prohibitively expensive, particularly if the dataset is large and the model’s inference cost is high.

Similar considerations extend to the knowledge of data distributions. Without this information, one can only query the model in a space far larger than the actual data manifold of interest. This leads to uncovering behaviors that may not be significant or interesting, as the model is unlikely to be queried in those areas, thereby requiring more time and computational resources to generate effective explanations.

3.5 A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF POPULAR FEATURE ATTRIBUTION SCORES

There is a quite large collection of feature attributions scores in the literature, the objective here is to present only the most significant ones and the ones in the end most widely used by the community. Interestingly, some of the scores that we will discuss can be seen as local surrogations with specific interpretable model structures.

3.5.1 Permutation Importance

Permutation Importance is a model-agnostic, straightforward yet effective technique for assessing the **global** importance of individual features in a predictive model. It operates on a simple principle: a feature is deemed important if its random permutation leads to a substantial decrease in the model’s performance.

To formalize this, consider a predictive model $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where d represents the number of features. For a validation dataset $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$ and corresponding target values $\mathcal{Y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N\}$, the performance measure $P : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ can be defined. This measure could be accuracy, log-likelihood, or any other metric that quantifies the model’s performance. The initial performance is given by $P_{\text{original}} = P(f(\mathcal{X}), \mathcal{Y})$.

The feature importance is evaluated by permuting each feature and measuring the resulting performance. Specifically, for the i -th feature, we create a permuted dataset $\mathcal{X}_i^{\text{permuted}}$ and calculate $P_{i,\text{permuted}} = P(f(\mathcal{X}_i^{\text{permuted}}), \mathcal{Y})$. The importance I_i is then determined as $I_i = P_{\text{original}} - P_{i,\text{permuted}}$.

While the Permutation Importance method is intuitive and easy to implement, it has some limitations. The primary output, which states that “permuting this feature results in an $I_i\%$

drop in performance”, while useful, may not be sufficiently informative for all applications. Moreover, the method is designed to assess only first-order importance. Extending it to higher-order importance is possible but would lead to exponential increases in computational cost.

3.5.2 Sobol Indices: Understanding Feature Contributions to Variance

Sobol indices provide model-agnostic global explanations. They aim to assess how much a specific feature contributes to the total variance of the model on the data manifold. It all stems from the observation that any function $f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p)$ can be decomposed into a sum of functions of increasing dimensionality¹:

$$f(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p) = f_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p f_i(x_i) + \sum_{i<j} f_{ij}(x_i, x_j) + \dots + f_{1,2,\dots,p}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p) \quad (3.2)$$

We can then move to decomposing the variance of f into contributions from each term. To evaluate $\text{Var}(f)$ given its Sobol decomposition, we square f and then take the expectation:

$$\mathbb{E}[f^2] = \mathbb{E} \left[\left(f_0 + \sum_i f_i(x_i) + \sum_{i<j} f_{ij}(x_i, x_j) + \dots + f_{1,2,\dots,p}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_p) \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.3)$$

Assuming that each term $f_i(x_i)$, $f_{ij}(x_i, x_j)$, etc., is orthogonal with respect to the others and the variables x_i are independent, the cross-terms vanish in the expectation. Under these assumptions, we find:

$$\mathbb{E}[f^2] = f_0^2 + \sum_i \mathbb{E}[f_i(x_i)^2] + \sum_{i<j} \mathbb{E}[f_{ij}(x_i, x_j)^2] + \dots \quad (3.4)$$

Now, being the variance of f defined as:

$$\text{Var}(f) = \mathbb{E}[f^2] - \mathbb{E}[f]^2 \quad (3.5)$$

By using the previous equations, the variance can be decomposed as follows:

$$\text{Var}(f) = \sum_i V_i + \sum_{i<j} V_{ij} + \dots + V_{1,2,\dots,p} \quad (3.6)$$

where $V_i = \mathbb{E}[f_i(x_i)^2] - (\mathbb{E}[f_i(x_i)])^2$, $V_{ij} = \mathbb{E}[f_{ij}(x_i, x_j)^2] - (\mathbb{E}[f_{ij}(x_i, x_j)])^2$, and so on.

Continuing from the variance decomposition, the Sobol index S_i quantifies how much each individual variable x_i contributes to the total variance of the function f . It is defined as the ratio of the variance contribution of the variable x_i to the total variance of f .

¹It is this observation that also justifies the development of Generalised Additive Models in chapter 4, where one restrict the class of functions to have only first order components and not any other higher order.

$$S_i = \frac{V_i}{\text{Var}(f)} \quad (3.7)$$

This provides a simple yet powerful interpretation: S_i essentially tells us what fraction of the total variance in the output f can be attributed to the variable x_i .

It is important to note a significant limitation: Sobol indices assume that input variables x_i are independent of each other. In real-world datasets, this assumption may not always hold true. Despite this limitation, Sobol indices still offer valuable insights. Specifically, attributing a certain fraction of the total variance of the model to each feature provides an informative perspective on feature importance, even if it is not universally applicable.

3.5.3 Providing Local Explanations with Surrogate Models

Surrogate models play a crucial role in the field of XAI, particularly in providing local explanations for complex, black-box models. These models serve as simpler, interpretable approximations that elucidate how complex models make decisions for specific instances. Unlike global explanation methods that aim to understand the model’s behavior over a wide range of inputs, local surrogate models focus on single specific data instances.

One of the most popular such approaches is LIME, which stands for “Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations” [114]. LIME is a model-agnostic framework for providing **local** explanations. For a given complex model $f(\cdot)$ and a data instance x_0 , LIME aims to understand how f operates in a local neighborhood \mathcal{X} around x_0 .

The main idea is to construct a surrogate model $g(\cdot)$ parametrized by θ to approximate f within this local region. Specifically, $g(\mathcal{X}) \approx f(\mathcal{X})$. LIME generally employs a linear model for g , which makes the coefficients straightforward to interpret. Each coefficient quantifies the impact of a slight change in a given feature on the model’s prediction within \mathcal{X} :

$$\min_{\theta} \sum_{x_i \in \mathcal{X}} w(x_i, x_0) (f(x_i) - g(x_i; \theta))^2 \quad (3.8)$$

where $w(x_i, x_0)$ is a weight function that assigns larger weights to instances x_i that are closer to x_0 , and θ represents the coefficients of g .

The LIME explanation content consists of these optimized coefficients. They serve as a localized measure of feature importance and are particularly useful for understanding how f operates in the vicinity of x_0 .

While LIME has its appeal due to the intuitive concept of fitting a linear model in the neighborhood of data, it leaves open some critical questions. For example, how should one set the neighborhood size appropriately, determine the number of data points to consider, or choose a suitable similarity function for computing w ? Unfortunately, these hyperparameters can significantly impact the reliability and clarity of explanations. Moreover, while some efforts have

been made to use multiple LIME explanations for offering a global view, combining these local approximations lacks a strong theoretical justification.

The Local Rule-Based Explanation (LORE) method approximates locally black-box models, while diverging from LIME’s typical reliance on linear models [56, 55]. LORE utilizes decision trees for local approximation, enabling the extraction of decision rules that delineate the decision boundary near the instance under examination. This facilitates the construction of both factual and counterfactual explanations. The decision trees’ ability to capture nonlinear interactions offers a higher degree of expressiveness compared to linear models. However, this increased expressivity might lead to greater complexity in the surrogate model. To address this, heuristics are employed to maintain a balance between expressivity and model complexity.

Like LIME, LORE and other rule-based approximation methods like Anchor [116] encounter challenges when the instance to be explained lies significantly distant from a decision boundary. In such scenarios, the neighborhood generated for explanation tends to be skewed towards a single class or generally unbalanced, impacting the efficacy of the explanation.

The limitations of most well-known local explainers naturally lead us to explore other methods, such as Shapley values, that offer alternative ways to set up the neighborhood and weights.

3.5.4 Shapley Values

Shapley values [129] are based on a sophisticated theoretical framework aiming to define and attribute importance fairly. Initially formulated in the context of coalitional game theory—a mathematical field that studies in abstract how players can achieve results when they preform alliances—Shapley values aim to solve a specific problem: Assuming a team has collectively earned a payoff, how should it be fairly distributed among members? This is not always a trivial task as often it can happen that the whole is greater than the parts, and the contribution of each player to the final result can depend on synergistic or antagonistic non-linear relationships with the rest of the team members.

We can define a set of N *players* as generic entities that can form groups or alliances called *coalitions*. These coalitions are orderless subsets of the set of players. A score called *payoff* is associated to each coalition thanks to a *value function* $v(\cdot)$. This score is a real value which can represent different things in different problems, For example, the amount of money made by a business joint venture or the cost of passengers sharing a taxi.

A set of players and a value function $v(\cdot)$ defined on all the subsets of players (coalitions) is what defines a *game*. In order to clarify these concepts it is useful to consider a concrete example. Let’s consider that we have three players: Albert, Juliette and Michele. Figure 3.6 shows all the possible coalitions they can form.

Let’s suppose that Albert possesses a left glove, while Juliette and Michele have a right glove each. A single glove is worthless but a pair of right and left gloves can be sold for 15 euros. This

Figure 3.6: All possible coalitions formed by Albert, Juliette, and Michele.

implicitly defines the value function $v(\cdot)$ for all possible coalitions, i.e., associate each coalition with a payoff, thus defining a game (see Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: Illustration of the glove game, highlighting the value function $v(\cdot)$ across different coalitions of Albert, Juliette, and Michele.

Suppose that all the players decide to join in a big alliance S and the coalition receives its payoff. Now the big question becomes: how should we split the 15 euros among the players $\{\text{Albert, Juliette, Michele}\}$? What is the fair way of distributing the money? How can we take into account the synergies?

Notably the problem requires to find a set of payoffs ϕ_i to each player i in such a way that

$$\sum_i \phi_i = v(S) \quad (3.9)$$

In other words, we should find a decomposition that sums up exactly to $v(S)$, nothing more and nothing less. This is also called the *Efficiency* property, sometimes referred to in economical context as “no money left on the table”.

The brilliant intuition that Lloyd Shapley had in order to tackle this problem is to focus on the **process** that leads to the formation of coalitions. So how do coalitions form? As illustrated in Figure 3.8, starting from the empty set, each player joins the coalition sequentially “one player

at a time”, enlarging the coalition until all players are included. In other words given an order of players we can define a coalition entry process.

Figure 3.8: Sequential coalition entry process illustrating 'one player at a time' joining, as conceptualized in the example.

If we carefully look at this process, we can more intuitively define what is the contribution of a given player when it enters a coalition. More specifically we can define the contribution of player i as the difference in value of the coalition when the player i is present versus the case when is *not* present. This is called **marginal contribution** as it refers to the incremental or additional value that a player brings to a coalition when they join it. More formally, in a cooperative game with a coalition C and a value function $v(C)$, the marginal contribution of a player i upon joining C is defined as follows:

$$\text{Marginal Contribution of Player } i \text{ to } C = \nabla_i(C) := v(C \cup \{i\}) - v(C) \quad (3.10)$$

This operational definition of a player’s value as its marginal contribution in a coalition entry process is compelling as it measures a **context-dependent** value that depends on the **increment** of the value function. Also importantly it can be shown that given a set of coalitions \mathcal{C} defined by a specific order of players joining the game we have that $\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \nabla_i(c) = v(S) - v(\{\}) = v(S)$, giving us the first hint of the *efficiency* property².

In simpler terms, the marginal contribution serves as the foundational operational definition of “what is important” in cooperative settings. It quantifies the change in payoff when a new player joins a coalition, effectively measuring its importance or value in that specific context. Figure 3.9 illustrates marginal contributions in our example.

Figure 3.9: Illustration of the marginal contributions of players in the example cooperative game.

Once we have discussed what the value of a player is, some important questions still remain unanswered: How can we say that it is fair? Why did we consider this specific player joining order and not another one? Which order or orders should we consider? The **fairness** in Shapley values is encoded in the step of not favouring one order with respect to another, but actually to consider all of them equally. By equally weighing every possible permutation of player orderings, the Shapley value framework ensures that each player’s value is consistently recognized,

²Assuming without loss of generality that $v(\{\}) = 0$.

proportionally to every context they might join in. This process allows to take into account all the possible constructive or destructive synergies that can form and attributes them to the respective players.

Figure 3.10 shows all the possible permutations in our illustrative example.

Figure 3.10: Visualization of all possible permutations of player orderings in the glove example. Players enter one at a time, the value of the coalition is shown below each coalition while on the right is highlighted the marginal contribution of each single player.

Given a set of all possible orderings \mathcal{O} , we can define the Shapley value ϕ_i for a player i as the mean of its marginal contributions (i.e., the mean of the values on the right side of the picture). Mathematically, this can be expressed as follows:

$$\phi_i = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{O}|} \sum_{o \in \mathcal{O}} \sum_{\substack{c \in \text{Coalitions}(o) \\ i \notin c}} \nabla_i(c) \quad (3.11)$$

If one does the calculations, it is easy to see that for our example we have

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{Albert} &= \frac{0 + 0 + 15 + 15 + 15 + 15}{6} = 10, \\ \phi_{Juliette} &= \frac{15 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0}{6} = \frac{5}{2}, \\ \phi_{Michele} &= \frac{0 + 15 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0}{6} = \frac{5}{2} \end{aligned}$$

This solution yields interesting implications:

- **Albert:** His Shapley value of 10 euros is a strong incentive to participate, emphasizing his critical role due to his unique left glove.

- **Juliette and Michele:** Each receiving a Shapley value of 2.5 euros ensures they are rewarded for participation. Their equal values also indicate their roles are interchangeable.
- **Coalition:** The Shapley values encourage full participation, provide a fair distribution based on contributions, and ensure economic efficiency by fully distributing the total value (no money left on the table).

To provide a comprehensive view of how coalitions form, we can create a visual representation using a graph (see Figure 3.11). In this graph, each node corresponds to a possible coalition. Edges between nodes signify the transition from one coalition to another due to a player joining it. Specifically, an edge from node p to node q indicates that a player has entered coalition p , transforming it into coalition q . To make it easier to track the origin of these transitions, edges are color-coded. Each color corresponds to a particular permutation of the player sequence, adhering to the color scheme used in previous figures. This allows us to understand which permutations lead to the formation of specific coalitions.

One key aspect of this graph is the multiplicity of paths that connect different coalitions. For example you can see that from the coalition $\{\text{Albert, Michele}\}$ you can go to $\{\text{Albert, Juliette, Michele}\}$ in two ways: with the yellow ordering $(\text{Michele, Albert, Juliette})$ or with the red ordering $(\text{Albert, Michele, Juliette})$. The number of such paths is influenced by the size of the coalition. These paths represent different sequences of players joining the coalition, leading to the same end state. This multiplicity underscores an inefficiency in the intuitive formulation of Shapley values of equation 3.11: some marginal contributions are counted multiple times due to differing player sequences that lead to the same coalition.

To make this inefficiency more apparent, the graphs in Figure 3.12 highlight in red the sub-graphs of the marginal contributions needed for computing the Shapley values of each player.

Figure 3.12: Graphs highlighting the specific marginal contributions for each player, with multi-edges illustrating the potential for computational inefficiency addressed by appropriate normalization.

Figure 3.11: Graphical representation of coalition formation, with color-coded edges indicating different player sequence permutations. Note that the colors correspond to the coalitions depicted in Figure 3.10.

By recognizing this inherent multiplicity—arising from the various sequences of player entries—we can optimize the computation of Shapley values. Specifically, the marginal contributions can be normalized by counting the number of paths that include them. Consider a coalition S from the set of all possible coalitions N that a player i may join. Arranging the sequence from left to right, there are $|S|$ players preceding i and $|N| - |S| - 1$ players following i . The number of permutations leading to this specific entry sequence for the player is $|S|! \times (|N| - |S| - 1)!$. To average over all sequences, one would sum all such terms and di-

vide by $|N|!$. This optimization reduces the computational complexity from $O(|N|!)$ to $O(2^{|N|})$, which is a significant speedup for large N , albeit still computationally challenging.

This leads us to the final equation for Shapley Values:

$$\phi_i = \frac{1}{|N|!} \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} |S|! \times (|N| - |S| - 1)! [v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)] \quad (3.12)$$

Often represented equivalently like this:

$$\phi_i = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}} \frac{|S|! \times (|N| - |S| - 1)!}{|N|!} [v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S)] \quad (3.13)$$

Remarkably, Shapley Values is the only coefficient decomposition that uniquely satisfies several key properties, which contribute to their wide applicability in various fields:

1. **Symmetry:** This property asserts that players who contribute identically to all possible coalitions should receive the same payoff. In essence, this property captures the idea of fair treatment for equal contributions.
2. **Dummy Player:** A player who does not contribute to any coalition should have $\phi_i = 0$, effectively excluding players who do not bring any marginal utility to the game.
3. **Additivity:** For two separate games with value functions v_a and v_b , the Shapley Values of a combined game $v_c = v_a + v_b$ should be the sum of the Shapley Values for the individual games. In notation, $\phi_i^c = \phi_i^a + \phi_i^b$. This property is essential for dividing complex problems into smaller, more computable components. For example you can get the Shapley values of a random forest by combining the Shapley values of its decision trees.
4. **Efficiency:** Specifically, $\sum_i \phi_i = v(N)$, which allows for a theoretically sound way to group features and assign importance to each group by summing their respective ϕ_i values.

These properties not only make Shapley Values unique in the context of coefficient decomposition but also offer a versatile and theoretically sound framework for applications ranging from machine learning to economics.

3.5.4.1 Shapley Interaction Values

We have just seen how Shapley values offer an effective means for calculating the average marginal contribution of single players in a cooperative game, implicitly including in ϕ_i the effects of synergies or antagonisms between players. The question that arises is: can we construct an index that captures more explicitly these synergies and antagonisms for pairs of players?

To intuitively approach the concept of interaction, consider the following cases in a game v with N players [47]:

- $v(ij) > v(i) + v(j)$: Here, there is a *positive* interaction, or one could say that there is a *complementary* effect between players i and j . In this case, the union is greater than the sum of the parts.
- $v(ij) < v(i) + v(j)$: In this scenario, the players have a *negative* or *redundant* interaction.
- $v(ij) = v(i) + v(j)$: It seems natural to consider that i and j do not interact, meaning they have *independent* roles in the game.

This leads us to the introduction of the Shapley interaction value [94, 54], a generalisation of the Shapley value framework designed to isolate and quantify the interaction between pairs of players i and j . This way, instead of having just a list of one Shapley value for each player, we end up with a symmetric matrix that captures both individual and pairwise contributions.

The Shapley interaction value between two different players i and j is defined as:

$$\Phi_{i,j} = \sum_{S \subseteq N \setminus \{i,j\}} \frac{|S|! \times (|N| - |S| - 2)!}{2(|N| - 1)!} \nabla_{ij}(v, S), \quad (3.14)$$

where $i \neq j$.

Here, $\nabla_{ij}(v, S)$ generalises the concept of marginal contribution from a single player to two players, quantifying the change in total value when players i and j join a coalition S :

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{ij}(v, S) &= [v(S \cup \{i, j\}) - v(S \cup \{i\})] - [v(S \cup \{j\}) - v(S)] \\ &= v(S \cup \{i, j\}) - v(S \cup \{i\}) - v(S \cup \{j\}) + v(S) \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

This can be understood as marginal contribution of j in the presence of i minus the marginal contribution of j in the absence of i .

The interaction index $\Phi_{i,j}$ can be interpreted as a kind of average value of the added value given by putting i and j together, all coalitions being considered. When $\Phi_{i,j}$ is positive (resp. negative), then the interaction is said to be positive (resp. negative).

Now, if you are curious about a player's individual residual contribution after accounting for pairwise collaborations, you can look at:

$$\Phi_{i,i} = \phi_i - \sum_{j \neq i} \Phi_{i,j} \quad (3.16)$$

Finally, all these values together will sum up to give the total value or worth of the entire set of players, as shown below:

$$v(N) = \sum_{i=0}^{|N|} \sum_{j=0}^{|N|} \Phi_{i,j} \quad (3.17)$$

³Notice that if you re-label i as j and j as i the formula remains the same.

Figure 3.13 shows the Shapley interaction values for our illustrative example. The Shapley interaction matrix shows the interplay between the players Albert, Juliette, and Michele. Juliette and Michele have a negative pairwise interaction, emphasizing their roles as competitors in the game. In contrast, Albert shows positive interactions with both Juliette and Michele, which underscores his inclination to form beneficial coalitions with them. The meaning of the self-interaction value for each player is not immediately straightforward but indicates what value remains for each player after all pairwise interactions are taken into account. In a sense we can see that most of the values here comes from interactions. Overall, these Shapley interaction values highlight the cooperative synergy between Albert and the other players, while also exposing the inherent antagonism between Juliette and Michele in this game.

Figure 3.13: Illustration of the Shapley interaction values in the glove example, showcasing individual and pairwise contributions.

While the formulation described up to now is for pairs of players, the procedure can be further generalised to compute arbitrary order of interactions of coalitions S [53] with the following formula:

$$I_{\text{sh}}(v, S) := \sum_{T \subseteq N \setminus S} \frac{(n - |T| - |S|)! \times |T|!}{(n - |S| + 1)!} \nabla_{S^v}(T) \quad (3.18)$$

In conclusion, Shapley interaction values offer a focused lens to explicitly understand how pairs of players, and even larger groups, interact within a coalition. This provides a more granular understanding of game dynamics and can be very useful in applications ranging from machine learning to economics.

3.5.4.2 Shapley Values for Machine Learning

When applying Shapley Values to machine learning the only thing to do conceptually is to decide what will be the game, i.e., answering to the following questions: what are the players? what

does it mean for a player to be missing? what is the value function?

In machine learning the features in a dataset are considered as players and the value function is typically the output of the model⁴. Mathematically, $v(S) = f(x|_S)$, where $x|_S$ denotes the input vector restricted to the features in S .

But what does it mean for a player to be absent in this context? Typically machine learning models which are trained with p features still need p features for inference (with some exception). This opens the door for two choices:

- **Missing:** when a feature is missing we will replace that value with a ‘missing’ flag [118]. Different models deal with missing values in different ways, sometimes replacing them with a single specific value (often the mean or the median), other times trying to synthesise a plausible value for that feature given the value of the others known features. Other times the models simply do not have a component that deals with missing values so it is required to replace the missing value with a predefined “baseline” value, with the idea that this baseline should represent a signal-less value. This is sometimes referred to as Baseline Shapley [141]. This is for example typically used in images, where “missing” pixels (or groups of them, called superpixels) are put to either black or to an average color.
- **Marginalization:** In this case one tries to measure what would be the expected value of the function. Mathematically, this can be represented as $v(S) = \mathbb{E}[f(x)|x_S]$. This is usually implemented by applying the function of all those data points that match x_S (or are close enough) and then taking its average

By formalizing these concepts, Shapley values offer a way to decompose the prediction $f(x)$ into contributions from each individual feature, maintaining the foundational Shapley principles of fairness and value attribution in a machine learning setting.

3.5.4.3 Example of Shapley Values for Machine Learning

To practically demonstrate how Shapley Values work in machine learning, we present here an illustrative example using a simple dataset: the Titanic survival dataset. The task involves predicting the survival probability of a Titanic passenger based on a simplified description encompassing three features: sex (male or female), passenger class (1st, 2nd, or 3rd), and age. The dataset is split into training (70%) and test (30%) subsets. A Random Forest model, denoted as $f(\cdot)$, is trained on the training split and achieves an accuracy of 78% on the test set.

Now, let’s consider a specific prediction for a single data point in the test set: $f(\text{class} = 1st, \text{age} = 25, \text{sex} = female) = 0.865777$

⁴Usually for classification logodds are used instead of probabilities, as probabilities saturates close to 0 and 1 while logodds are more linear.

To apply Shapley values, we must compute the “value of the game,” which, in this context, is the survival probability returned by the model. As said in the previous section, what in the game-theoretic context were called players are now referred to as the feature values of the instance. The coalitions that we need to evaluate are displayed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Coalitions of features for the Titanic dataset.

Class	Age	Sex	Classifier Output
1st	25	female	0.865777
?	25	female	
1st	?	female	
1st	25	?	
?	?	female	
?	25	?	
1st	?	?	
?	?	?	

It is important to note, as mentioned in the previous section, that machine learning models typically require all data points to be known in order to produce a prediction. Consequently, we must choose between synthesizing plausible values from a learned data distribution (the **Missing** strategy) or using marginalization.

In the following example, we will demonstrate the Missing strategy, as it is more commonly used in everyday practice and is easier to illustrate. When employing the Missing strategy, we replace somehow the missing values. This can be done in various ways, the most straightforward being by replacing the missing values with some fixed “baseline” values. In this case we choose a slightly more sophisticated way by imputing the missing values using mode finding, which involves synthesizing the most plausible value from the training dataset’s distribution based on known information. The survival probability is then computed by applying the classifier to this imputed data. This process is detailed in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Original and Imputed Coalitions with Classifier Outputs for the Titanic Dataset. In the imputed columns, the imputed values are highlighted in *italic*.

Original Coalitions			Imputed			Classifier Output
Class	Age	Sex	Class	Age	Sex	Survival Probability
1st	25	female	1st	25	female	0.865777
?	25	female	<i>3rd</i>	25	female	0.451359
1st	?	female	1st	<i>56.8728</i>	female	0.841973
1st	25	?	1st	25	<i>female</i>	0.865777
?	?	female	<i>3rd</i>	<i>20.9418</i>	female	0.419148
?	25	?	<i>3rd</i>	25	<i>male</i>	0.158027
1st	?	?	1st	<i>45.5612</i>	<i>male</i>	0.196156
?	?	?	<i>3rd</i>	<i>28.4238</i>	<i>male</i>	0.145955

We can apply this game definition to explicitly demonstrate the coalition entry process and the marginal contributions of each player (as we did earlier with the glove game example), now representing the marginal contribution of knowing a certain feature value. This is depicted in Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14: Coalition entry process and marginal contributions of age, class, and sex on survival probability in the Titanic dataset.

Averaging the marginal contributions for each feature, as shown on the right side of the figure, yields the following results:

$$\phi_{\text{age}} = 0.115627,$$

$$\phi_{\text{class}} = 0.341901,$$

$$\phi_{\text{sex}} = 0.262293$$

This sums to 0.719822, exactly equating the difference $f(\text{age} = 25, \text{class} = 1\text{st}, \text{sex} = \text{female}) - f(\text{age} = ?, \text{class} = ?, \text{sex} = ?)$. Thus, we can say that in the absence of any information, survival probability is low (0.145955, i.e. 15%). However, specific details about this individual positively contribute to increasing survival probability. Being in first class raises the probability by 34%, being female adds 26%, and being 25 years old contributes an additional 11%. This analysis aligns well with historical accounts of the Titanic tragedy, where first-class passengers were on a floor that was closer to the lifeboats and women and children were given priority.

It is important to note that while in this example we decided to decompose the output probability (a choice that might seem more intuitive), a better statistical practice is often to decompose the logodds of the probability. This is because probabilities typically involve multiplications, and summing in the logarithmic space corresponds to multiplication in the probability space. Additionally, the probability scale saturates near zero and one, which can lead to misleading attributions of relevance; for instance, a change from 0.99 to 0.999 is a tenfold increase in likelihood, yet it might appear as a minor absolute increase of 0.009.

Figure 3.15: Shapley interactions on a specific instance of survival prediction of the Titanic disaster.

To convert the probability to logodds, we use the following formula:

$$\text{LogOdds}(p) := \log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$$

Applying this to our data, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_{\text{age}} &= 0.577, \\ \phi_{\text{class}} &= 1.73, \\ \phi_{\text{sex}} &= 1.31\end{aligned}$$

These values, when interpreted in the logodds framework, provide a qualitatively similar understanding to our previous probability-based analysis but with more nuanced insights, particularly in cases of extreme probability values.

For completeness, we include a plot of Shapley interaction values (Figure 3.15). This plot reveals interesting interactions among the features: a positive interaction between being 25 years old and being in the first class is noted in supporting survival, whereas the interaction between gender and age shows somewhat antagonistic characteristics (Figure 3.15).

3.5.4.4 Shapley Values Approximations: KernelSHAP

While Shapley values offer a useful theoretical framework to fairly assess the significance of each player in a game, the computational burden of equation 3.13 often makes it impractical to use—especially when there are many players.

A key insight is that both LIME and Shapley Values fall under the same category known as ‘additive explanations’, as mentioned in [82]. Methods in this category aim to approximate a complex, black-box model f at a specific point x_0 by using a simpler linear model g . This results in a set of coefficients ϕ_i that quantify the influence of each feature. When summed, these coefficients approximate the output $f(x)$ from the original model. This means that the formulation of LIME is general enough to also include Shapley values, provided the right choices are made for the weighting kernel and regularization.

To put this into mathematical terms, one can formalise the problem by using a binary input space where a vector z contains either 1s or 0s, indicating whether a player is participating in a coalition. For example, in a game with three players, a vector $\{0, 0, 0\}$ would represent an empty coalition, while $\{1, 1, 1\}$ would represent a full coalition⁵. These vectors can be organized into a player presence indicator matrix Z . To continue with our illustrative example, Figure 3.16 shows the matrix Z and its associated coalitions.

$$Z = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \{\} \\ \{\text{Michele}\} \\ \{\text{Juliette}\} \\ \{\text{Juliette, Michele}\} \\ \{\text{Albert}\} \\ \{\text{Albert, Michele}\} \\ \{\text{Albert, Juliette}\} \\ \{\text{Albert, Juliette, Michele}\} \end{pmatrix}$$

Figure 3.16: Player presence indicator matrix Z representing coalition participation for a three-player game, as part of the discussion on Shapley Values Approximations.

From here one can setup a linear system for recovering the additive explanations in the form of:

$$Z\Phi = y \tag{3.19}$$

Yet what sets additive explanations apart is the choice of regularisation and a kernel function, that is how one should weight different observations. While LIME uses a kernel that gives more importance to instances closer to x_0 and sometimes uses an L1 regularisation for enforcing sparsity, Shapley values can be approximated without any regularization as described in [82] by using the following kernel function:

$$w(S) = \frac{|N| - 1}{\binom{|N|}{|S|} \times |S| \times (|N| - |S|)} \tag{3.20}$$

⁵Functions that operates on these representations are often referred to as boolean functions.

where $|S|$ is the sum of non-zero elements in the row z of Z and $|N|$ is the number of total players.

The way this is set up still has a complexity similar to the previous definition. However, the advantage here is that we can estimate accurate Shapley values using only a small subset of different coalitions. KernelShapley has been proven to be more sample-efficient compared to standard Shapley sampling (as per equation 3.13).

In a recent study [26], researchers discovered that speeding up the process is possible by focusing on non-random sampling. Specifically, one should evaluate coalitions with the highest kernel values. This approach reveals a consistent pattern for optimally ranking coalitions to achieve quicker estimations. Initially, the procedure focuses on coalitions comprising a single player and coalitions that lack only one player. Subsequently, it examines coalitions with two players and those that are missing two players, continuing in this pattern.

The plots in Figure 3.17 show a practical example featuring a 50-player game. The plot on the left displays how weights, calculated via the Shapley Kernel formula, vary with coalition size. On the right, another plot guides you through the optimal sequence for considering different coalition sizes to achieve faster estimations. In this second plot, the X-axis indicates the ranking for which coalition sizes to consider first, and the Y-axis shows the actual sizes

Figure 3.17: Comparative plots for a 50-player game, illustrating the variation of weights by coalition size (left) and the optimal sequence for considering different coalition sizes for faster estimations (right), in the context of KernelShapley.

3.5.4.5 TreeShap

As discussed in 3.4.3, specifying more details and structure to the black-box model allows for even greater computational efficiency by taking advantage of that specific structure. This applies to computing Shapley Values for decision trees and their ensemble counterparts, i.e., Random Forests. The TreeShap algorithm [80] provides a faster method for calculating marginalized Shapley values and Shapley interaction values in these contexts. This boost in speed is achieved by leveraging the inherent structure of the tree models. In particular, the algorithm keeps track of the number of data points following specific paths within the tree, enabling a more efficient computation of marginalized values. Consequently, the computational complexity decreases to

a low-order polynomial, dependent on factors like the number of trees and their maximum depth. The use of GPUs has further speed up this process, as shown in [90].

This result is particularly notable because Random Forests and related models, such as boosted decision trees, are among the most robust and widely-used techniques for tabular data [45]. Therefore, with Random Forests—a commonly used black-box model known for its quick training and robust performance—we now possess an extremely fast method for computing Shapley Values. Furthermore, this technique can efficiently interpret the prediction for each data point across an entire dataset.

3.5.5 Gradient Methods

In this section, we will go deeper with methods for computing feature attribution scores that use the model’s gradient projected onto the input. These methods are particularly relevant for neural networks, which have become the go-to models for image and textual data. Though the methods previously mentioned are model-agnostic and can be applied to neural networks, methods that leverage the gradient (and sometimes the internal structure of the model) offer the advantage of speeding up the computation of attribution scores.

3.5.5.1 Simple Gradient

The simplest yet insightful method for understanding neural networks involves projecting the gradient of the output function back onto the input space [17, 132]. This technique is not only quick but also intuitively illustrates how altering specific input elements can maximize changes to the output. The mathematical representation of this is:

$$\phi(x_0) = \nabla f(x_0) \tag{3.21}$$

However, this method has its drawbacks:

- In the realm of vision models, it is unclear what it means when the method suggests that changing a specific pixel would increase the prediction. Pixels are often highly correlated, and the explanation can appear “noisy.” Actually, when you try to alter the input based on the gradient, the results resemble adversarial attacks. In such cases, the input appears largely unchanged to the human eye, but the neural network perceives a significant difference. While this might technically be a “valid” explanation from the model’s perspective, it is important to consider that an explanation should also be useful and intuitive to humans.
- Another issue is the presence of “noisy gradients.” Gradients can fluctuate dramatically with minimal changes to the input, making them unreliable. A worthwhile explanation

should ideally remain stable, at least within the neighborhood of the instance being explained.

- When applied to natural language data, it becomes unclear what it means to shift a token (or its embedding) in accordance with the gradient.

3.5.5.2 Smooth Grad

In an attempt to resolve some of the disadvantages of the Simple Gradient, particularly the problem of “noisy gradients”, the Smooth Grad method was introduced [136]. This method embraces the counterintuitive concept of “adding noise to remove noise.” Specifically, it evaluates the gradient not just at the instance x_0 , but also at points in its vicinity. This is achieved by adding an ε term of random normal values to x_0 , evaluating the gradient at these new points multiple times, and then averaging the results. The mathematical representation of Smooth Grad is as follows:

$$\phi(x_0) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \nabla f(x_0 + \varepsilon_i) \quad (3.22)$$

where n is the number of times the gradient is evaluated with different ε values parameterized by i .

This process produces a more stable explanation around x_0 . However, it is not always straightforward to determine the appropriate variance value for ε . Despite this challenge, the Smooth Grad method is versatile enough to be applied to any gradient-based approach.

3.5.5.3 Scaled Gradients

Another approach to enhance the interpretability of neural networks involves using scaled gradients [71]. The premise is to multiply the gradients by the input values. The rationale behind this is to weigh the gradient information according to the actual signal present in the input. The mathematical representation for scaled gradients is the following:

$$\phi(x_0) = x_0 \odot \nabla f(x_0) \quad (3.23)$$

This concept was later extended to not just multiply the gradients by the input, but by the difference between the input and a certain baseline value [131]. The mathematical representation for scaled gradients with a baseline is:

$$\phi(x_0) = (x_0 - x_{\text{baseline}}) \odot \nabla f(x_0) \quad (3.24)$$

This difference better represents the “signal”, although defining what “signal” means can be ambiguous. The introduction of a baseline raises a complex question: what makes a good baseline in various scenarios? We previously encountered this challenge when discussing the

application of Shapley values to machine learning. Determining an appropriate baseline is problematic, largely because it is usually hard to find a “ground truth” explanation to which one can refer for making informed decisions.

3.5.5.4 Integrated Gradients

An intriguing extension of the scaled gradients approach is known as Integrated Gradients [142]. This technique starts by selecting a reference baseline and then integrates the input gradient along the straight path connecting this baseline to the point x_0 that needs to be explained. The mathematical representation for Integrated Gradients is as follows:

$$\phi(x_0) = (x_0 - x_{\text{baseline}}) \odot \int_0^1 \nabla f(x_{\text{baseline}} + \alpha(x_0 - x_{\text{baseline}})) d\alpha \quad (3.25)$$

Here, α is a crucial component of the formula, serving as a scaling factor. It ranges from 0 to 1 and is used to parameterize the integration path. As α varies, it effectively scales the difference between the baseline and the input x_0 , allowing for the calculation of gradients at various points along the path from the baseline to x_0 . This integration over α accumulates the gradients at different scaled versions of the input.

The final explanation possesses an efficiency property similar to that of Shapley values, in that the sum of the attributions corresponds to the model’s output for the input x_0 . This is a natural consequence of fundamental integral calculus, where integrating the derivative of a function along a path results in the difference between the function’s values at the endpoints of that path.

Remarkably, the link between Integrated Gradients and Shapley values is not merely conceptual; it has a firm grounding in the literature on non-atomic cost game attributions in economics, developed by Aumann and Shapley [14].

3.5.6 Limitations and Considerations of Feature Attribution Methods

Feature attribution methods, have become instrumental in interpreting machine learning models. However, their effectiveness is contingent upon an accurate understanding of their nature and limitations.

Firstly, it is essential to distinguish between factual and counterfactual explanations in these methods. Factual explanations describe the influence of features in their current state, whereas counterfactual explanations hypothesize changes that could alter the model’s decision. This distinction is often misunderstood, leading to inappropriate interpretations.

Moreover, SHAP values, as approximations, are heavily influenced by the specifics of the ‘game’ set up for analysis. The choice of handling missing values, focusing on probabilities, logodds, or loss, plays a crucial role in the interpretation of these values.

Common misconceptions also plague practitioners. Many interpret these explanations as direct reflections of real-world phenomena, not recognizing them as representations of the data-model interaction. Additionally, SHAP values are sometimes mistakenly treated as counterfactuals, leading to misinterpretation of their intended purpose as indicators of feature contribution under the current data.

3.6 UPCOMING DISCUSSIONS: A ROADMAP

We have just provided a foundational overview of the XAI landscape, setting the stage for more in-depth discussions in this thesis. Here is a roadmap for what we are going to discuss:

- In the next chapter, we delve into “White-Box models by design” with a focus on Construable Neural Additive Models (CNAM). These models offer a unique approach to balancing performance with interpretability constraints.
- Following that, in Chapter 5, we explore the role of post-hoc explanations in “Black-Box” models. Specifically, we examine how these explanations can measure a model’s complexity in terms of its understandability and assess the faithfulness of surrogate models.
- We then turn our attention to specialized domains, investigating the reliability of feature attribution scores applied to images in computer vision (see Section 6.1) and text in natural language processing (see Section 6.2.2.2).

This roadmap will guide us through a series of studies designed to deepen the understanding of XAI, from theory to application.

4 Balancing Interpretability and Performance in White-Box Additive Models

In Chapter 3, we talked about why white-box models are useful, especially when you need to fully understand how a decision was made. This chapter digs deeper into the challenge of making a model that is both easy to understand and good at its job. We are going to focus on additive models, which are a type of white-box model that does well on both counts.

Why additive models? The answer comes from functional decomposition, explained in previous chapter (see equation 3.2). The idea is that you can break down any function into simpler parts that are easier to understand. This is also backed up by the Sobol index in Section 3.5.2. So, in an additive model, the function is just the sum of its parts, like $f = f_1(x_1) + f_2(x_2) + \dots + f_p(x_p)$. This makes it a lot easier to understand what the model is doing, as one just has to inspect each f_i without having to worry about complex interactions between variables.

We will introduce here Constrained Neural Additive Models (CNAM), a way to build additive neural networks which are both interpretable and good at their tasks. CNAM finds a balance between being easy to understand and being effective, which makes it a useful tool for a lot of different problems.

The rest of this chapter will go into the details of how CNAM works, what it is good at, and where it falls short. While it is not a one-size-fits-all solution, it is a solid option if you are trying to make a model that is both understandable and effective.

4.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter we define *explainability* as the ability of a system to give an explanation to the user, that is a report of (part of) the causal reasoning that leads to a particular outcome. We refer to *interpretability* instead of the less demanding property of a system of being inspectable in its parts in a meaningful way. In this sense, interpretability is a prerequisite for explainability.

XAI has evolved in different directions based on the requirements stated by the stakeholders of the explainable systems. For example, in order to build tools that are as widely applicable as possible some researchers have prioritized the development of “black-box explainers” [24]. In this context, no assumption is made on the model and we are only left with the input-output

relationship. In that case we have to rely on post-hoc approaches. These typically involve approximating the original model in an appropriate neighbourhood of data with an interpretable model (a so-called white-box) and then inspecting that to provide explanations, as suggested by [82, 114] (this approach is also known as surrogating). The surrogation paradigm is a very powerful one as it allows in principle to explain any black-box model, even deep neural networks, as long as the surrogating models are powerful enough to act like them. In virtue of this, if we want to enhance the explanation of black boxes, we first need good interpretable models by design so that we can later use them for surrogating.

To put it in other terms:

- we are interested in explaining black-box models as these are widely used;
- interpretability is a prerequisite for explainability, by the argument stated above;
- we should aim for models which are interpretable because these make ideal surrogate models for explaining other models.

This opens up the question of what it really means for a model to be interpretable. While with an imperative-style approach (where the program is hard-coded by a human) the interpretability is kept in each sub-component, with the ML approach (as it is usually employed) the only solutions explored are those that solve the task regardless of the final form of the model.

One key way to leverage the power of ML while ensuring interpretability is to focus on the structure of the model, in particular additive architectures. As discussed earlier, the decomposition of complex functions into simpler parts is inherently easier to understand. By designing models that are additive by nature, we promote interpretability from the outset. Moreover, a way to further enhance this approach is to guide the model search not only based on task performance but also considering measures that reflect interpretability. In this sense, we can imagine that an appropriate regularization term in the target loss could optimize both dimensions (i.e., interpretability and performance).

Just as the appropriate measure for predictive performance varies from task to task, the appropriate constraints for interpretability are also application-dependent. These constraints often penalize complexity and favor sparse representations, and they should be iteratively refined in collaboration with domain experts [120].

Generalised Additive Models (GAM) and Neural Additive Models (NAM) are well-studied classes of models that have powerful predictive performance while retaining an interpretable structure. This chapter addresses a new formulation for fitting GAM, named Constraining Neural Additive Model (CNAM), such that appropriate interpretable constraints can be enforced to jointly maximize performance and interpretability. In order to benchmark this model against other approaches we use a novel interpretability metric that is called SHAP-Length [85], which

exploits the well-known SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) first introduced by [82] and revisited in previous chapter (see Section 3.5.4).

The main contributions in this chapter are as follows:

- a novel formulation of NAM, CNAM, such that interpretability constraints can be enforced and jointly optimised alongside task-related performance metrics;
- an extensive benchmark of CNAM on 56 binary classification datasets against 13 different models;
- an illustrative use case of CNAM on a classification dataset;
- an illustrative use case of CNAM on a regression dataset.

The rest of the chapter is organized as follows. In section 4.2, we discuss related work in the field. In section 4.3, we describe the structure and properties of CNAM. In section 4.4, we experiment first with a benchmark study for explicitly exploring CNAM interpretability-performance tradeoff on binary classification tasks and then go deeper with two illustrative use cases: an astrophysics classification task and a socio-economic regression task. Finally in section 4.6, we draw conclusions and delineate future work.

4.2 RELATED WORK

The history of learning from data can be traced back to early work in the 19th century where, motivated by the desire of predicting astronomical data and minimising reconstruction errors, theoretical foundations and closed-form solutions for Linear Models (LM) were developed, which minimised the Mean Squared Error (MSE) as proposed by [2, 49]. The target y is modeled as \hat{y} from a set of features x_i and the task is to find a set of real coefficients β_i such that

$$\hat{y} = \sum_i \beta_i x_i$$

and the $\text{MSE} = 1/N \sum_j (\hat{y}_j - y_j)^2$, is minimised, being N the number of samples in the dataset.

Much later, Nelder and Wedderburn [97] unified some scattered views of modeling a certain target with an LM and introduced Generalised Linear Models (GLM), where the target y is transformed with the so-called *link function* $g(\cdot)$ with static coefficients α_i such that

$$g(y) = \sum_i \alpha_i x_i \quad (4.1)$$

This new modelling allows (among other things) to have linear *classifiers* by choosing the logistic sigmoid as the link function, leading to what is known as Logistic Regression (LR).

A further generalisation of LM was developed at Bell Labs by Hastie and Tibshirani [63, 64]. The condition of having a static coefficient α_i is relaxed and the relationship is allowed to be a non-linear function $f_i(\cdot)$ of the univariate feature such that

$$g(y) = \sum_i f_i(x_i) \quad (4.2)$$

This new formulation is appealing because it is more expressive than GLM while keeping a relatively simple and understandable structure. When the model is fitted one can indeed easily visualise each f_i (also called a *shape function*) as a function of the x_i values, naturally providing both a global view of the behaviour of the model on a dataset and a local explanation for the prediction of a single data point.

From a practical point of view, initially the functions f_i were based on Regression Splines of degree d of the form $f_i(x_i) := \sum_{k=1}^d \beta_k b_k(x_i)$ where each b_k is a different basis function (e.g., a different spline, like in Spline-GAM [87]) or other Kernel Expansions of the feature x_i . On the one hand, this allowed the injection of expert knowledge when designing the model. On the other hand, the fitting procedure was slow and sometimes did not converge properly. These fitting methods were then shown to be outperformed by [78] with a procedure of bagging and boosting binary decision trees leading to a class of models called Explainable Boosting Machines (EBM). For optimisation of speed and memory EBMs compress the representation of the function f_i with a lookup table, a data structure that bins the feature values and maps each bin to the height of the shape function.

EBMs were then further generalised to allow also pairwise interactions (EB2M) of the form $f(x_i, x_j)$ by Lou et al. [79] and proved to be of value with an application in healthcare [28].

A parallel development has attempted to model the shape functions with neural networks. Potts [110] pioneered the so-called Generalized Additive Neural Networks (GANN), where each f_i was represented as a small neural network. The optimisation process followed an iterative approach and did not make use of backpropagation. GANN were successfully used for example with the aim of improving the performance of credit scoring applications [149]. Agarwal et al. [3] proposed Neural Additive Models (NAM), a reinterpretation of GANN with more neurons, a new activation function ExU (designed to better capture sudden changes in the target function) and a sophisticated training procedure that included dropout, weight decay, output penalty and feature dropout. They reported competitive task performance compared to EBMs and other models on four datasets. It is worth noting that NAM can be a building block for other models, for example as the backbone of autoencoders. The main drawback of NAM is the need for a careful setup of many hyperparameters and the long training time that is required for the convergence of these models. Moreover with their formulation it is more difficult to introduce expert knowledge in the system and to explicitly require a part of a shape function to have a specific form.

In an effort to put the human in the loop, Wang et al. [151] built GAM-Changer, a framework where fitted GAM can be inspected and changed when deemed appropriate. This enables a domain expert to interact with the system and give some tools on how to correct the model where few statistics are available but human knowledge can be of help. While the user does receive feedback on the performance of the modified model, there is currently no way of fine-tuning the changed model keeping fixed the human interventions.

With the aim of overcoming drawbacks of current state of the art models, in this chapter we introduce the new CNAM, a way of building GAM based on neural networks but with a specific structure such that it is possible to initialise each shape function as an arbitrary curve and to enforce constraints on parts of the network. This is important because it allows us to:

1. leverage the power and speed of EBM which quickly converges to a good solution;
2. leverage the expressiveness of differentiable programming, opening the possibility of jointly optimising performance and interpretability-related metrics.

To conclude this section, Table 4.1 summarises the main properties of the most outstanding related models in the literature. As we will see in the rest of the chapter, CNAM is a promising tool for human-in-the-loop solutions and can in principle be integrated into GAM-Changer enabling a complete feedback-loop between a human and a machine.

Table 4.1: Summary of related models in the literature. CNAM is the new model proposed in this doctoral dissertation.

	<i>LM</i>	<i>LR</i>	<i>GLM</i>	<i>Spline-GAM</i>	<i>EBM</i>	<i>EB2M</i>	<i>NAM</i>	<i>CNAM</i>
Classification tasks		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Regression tasks	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Can be backbone of Autoencoders	✓						✓	✓
Can use prior knowledge on target			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Can use prior knowledge on data				✓				✓
Pairwise interactions						✓		
Arbitrary initialisation	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓
Constrainable	✓	✓						✓
Explicitly balancing interpretability-performance								✓

4.3 MODEL STRUCTURE

We can graphically represent CNAM as illustrated in Fig 4.1. The important novelty of CNAM is the construction of the shape functions f_i as a sum of carefully initialised differentiable versions of the unit step, which we will call *Differentiable Step* (DS). It is worth noting that only a few shape functions are expected to take non-zero values, thus effectively discarding some features from the final score by *Regularisation (Few Features Selected)*. The parametrisation

of the DS is what will allow CNAM to be initialised to any arbitrary shape, in particular this property will be used to initialise the model to the solution of EBM (more on this in section [4.3.2](#)).

Figure 4.1: Schematic view of the structure of CNAM (for classification) and how constraints are inserted. For regression the model is the same with the difference of not having a logistic sigmoid non-linearity at the end.

Once initialised, the structure of CNAM is transparent enough that each component has a clear interpretation and this facilitates the formal definition of appropriate regularisers for the problem at hand. As introduced in section [4.1](#), having a model that is flexible enough to enforce different constraints (e.g., sparsity) is key for targeting specific interpretability needs of different use cases. An enumeration of different desirable constraints will be the objective of the following section.

4.3.1 Desirable Constraints

We now proceed to list desirable constraints that could be useful in different situations. These can be appropriate when prior knowledge exists and can help the model to generalise better where data is scarce:

- **Monotonicity** of the shape functions (e.g., in a banking context we might want to enforce that the bigger the “Loan amount term” the lower should be the probability of granting the loan). More formally: for any x_i, x_j such that $x_i \leq x_j$ we have that $f(x_i) \leq f(x_j)$ (positive monotonicity) or $f(x_i) \geq f(x_j)$ (negative monotonicity).
- **Smoothness** of the shape functions. This could be useful for several reasons: Smooth functions tend to have fewer and less abrupt changes in direction, making them easier to

describe with simple trends (e.g., “the target value steadily increases as the feature value grows”). They are also less likely to be overly influenced by minor variations in the data, making them more robust to noise. Finally, the simpler trends of smooth curves make them more suitable for translating into natural language explanations, which are often more intuitive for users [6, 98].

- **Few** shape functions (useful for problems where the number of features is so large that would be impractical to manually assess every shape function). In other words this entails having a sparse representation following the principle of Ockam’s razor: “if two models describe the same event, the model with less assumptions (i.e., the model that relies on fewer variables) is preferable”. It is possible to mathematically enforce some sparseness of a linear combination of terms x parametrised by the dot product with w resulting in $w \cdot x$ by minimising the L_1 Norm of w , that is: $\min \sum_i |w_i|$
- **Local freezing** of some part of the shape function (e.g., to help optimise fairness measures). For example if we had a categorical variable describing some protected attribute one might want to enforce that the score for the protected attribute match some formal description of fairness.

It is important to note that the desirable constraints listed above are not an exhaustive list and are context-dependent. Furthermore, some of these constraints may conflict with maximizing task performance or even among themselves. For instance, while enforcing monotonicity of a shape function may improve the model’s interpretability, it may negatively impact its task performance. Similarly, enforcing sparsity of shape functions may help with interpretability, but at the cost of some loss in predictive accuracy.

Another approach that could be considered is to measure the agreement of feature importances as indicated by a human expert with what the model currently predicts. While this could help the model quickly converge to a well-generalizing solution, it should be kept in mind that human ranking could introduce biases that are not present in the data. Developing a suitable metric for measuring such agreement is a topic for future research.

Despite these considerations, the main motivation behind this approach is that once the desirable constraints are defined, the optimization procedure can explore different solutions that aim to satisfy all the given constraints. In the following section, we will discuss how to precisely define each component of CNAM and how to define appropriate regularizers that enforce the desirable constraints.

4.3.2 Model construction

CNAM specifies the structure of how each shape function can be constructed in a rather straightforward way. Intuitively, we develop the idea that each shape function f_i is a sum of j *step functions*, an approximation of indicator functions as follows:

$$f_i(x_i) = \sum_j \text{step}_j(x_i) \quad (4.3)$$

This way the model can be rewritten as

$$g(y) = \sum_i \sum_j \text{step}_j(x_i) \quad (4.4)$$

As introduced previously, we want $\text{step}(\cdot)$ (the DS) to be a soft version of an indicator function that adds or subtracts a specific (learnable) quantity at a certain position in the shape function. We parametrise DS with three parameters: pos_x , pos_y , speed . DS can then be defined as follows:

$$\text{step}(x_i) := \text{pos}_y * \sigma(\text{speed} * (x_i - \text{pos}_x)) \quad (4.5)$$

where

- $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the Logistic Sigmoid function, that is: $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$;
- pos_x is the position on x where the shape is centered (see Fig 4.2a);
- pos_y is the maximum height of the step (see Fig 4.2b);
- speed is a parameter that specifies how quickly the step grows (see Fig 4.2c).

When many carefully initialised DS are added up they can form a curve of arbitrary shape (see Fig 4.2d).

Then, without loss of generality, we can aggregate all the shape functions f_i with a linear layer parametrised by a vector α to produce the final prediction (log-odds in case of classification), as follows:

$$g(y) = \sum_i \alpha_i \cdot f_i(x_i) \quad (4.6)$$

The previous formulation can be useful for enforcing some regularisation like the L_1 norm on α_i in order to favour a sparse representation (i.e., when few shape functions are desired).

This formulation is well-suited for binary classification tasks and regression tasks. However, we acknowledge that extending our model to other tasks requires additional considerations. One possible approach for non-binary classification is to use a one-vs-rest fashion, where a separate model is trained for each class. This approach increases the complexity of the system, but it can be effective for multiclass classification problems.

Figure 4.2: The effect of changing the parameters of the differentiable steps (DS) on forming a f_i . This illustration aims to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how the behavior of the DS alters when adjusting each parameter. Specifically, modifying the pos_x parameter translates the step function horizontally, reflecting a shift along the x -axis where the shape is centered. Adjusting the pos_y parameter alters the maximum height of the step, effectively changing the level at which the step stabilizes. Lastly, the $speed$ parameter influences the rate at which the step reaches its maximum height; a higher speed results in a sharper transition, making the step appear more pronounced. The objective is to offer an illustrative sense of the dynamic behavior of the DS with respect to parameter variations, emphasizing the horizontal translation by pos_x , vertical adjustment by pos_y , and the steepness or gradualness of the transition controlled by $speed$.

4.3.3 Enforceable Constraints

With this formulation we can now begin to impose some of the constraints discussed in section 4.3.1 by specifying additional loss terms to be jointly optimised or by imposing some structural changes. Let us see how the list of possible enforceable constraints enumerated in section 4.3.1 can be implemented:

- **Monotonicity** of the shape functions: This can be achieved by imposing pos_y and $speed$ to be always greater (or smaller) than zero. This can be done by applying the function $\max(x, 0)$, also known as ReLU [48, 95], to them.
- **Smoothness** of the shape functions: This can be achieved by incentivising small values for the $speed$ parameters of the various DS of a given shape function. This can be done by minimising the L_2 norm of the $speed$, that is to add to the final loss function the com-

ponent $\lambda \sqrt{\sum_i speed_i^2}$. The parameter λ controls the amount of regularisation. Notice that with this formulation we can have smooth functions that are still able to model big jumps if necessary, something that spline-based GAM failed to achieve because the splines implicitly encode a prior of global smoothness. On the other hand, enforcing an L_2 on the *speed* still allows local speeds to be very high if appropriate.

- **Few shape functions:** this can be enforced by imposing sparsity (i.e., L_1 regularisation) on the final linear layer that aggregates the shape functions f_i . That is, we can represent without loss of generality the models as $g(x) = \alpha_1 * f_1(x_1) + \dots + \alpha_p * f_p(x_p)$ and then incentivise a sparse representation by adding to the final loss the L_1 norm of α : $\lambda_2 \sum_i^p |\alpha_i|$, where λ_2 controls the amount of regularisation. This is similar to what Tibshirani [146] proposed with Lasso, but it is now possible to apply it to close-to-optimal EBM solutions, something that up to now it was not possible to do.
- **Local freezing:** we can exclude parts of the model from the optimisation process by setting the gradient of a certain step to 0. This prevent any further updates on that parameter and thus any change on that part of the function.

4.3.4 Parameter Initialisation

As already anticipated earlier, one of the key features of CNAM is the ability to be initialised as solutions of faster solvers (e.g., EBM) easily. This is important because if we try to optimise the model from a typical random initialisation (e.g., following the principles delineated by Glorot and Bengio [52]) we observed empirically that the training can be unstable and result in suboptimal solutions with respect to EBM. On the other hand if we optimise the model while starting from the solution found by EBM, then CNAM is able to end up finding solutions that have similar or higher performance while also optimising the interpretability constraints (thus finding a solution that exhibits a better balance between performance and interpretability). This will be shown later with the experiments in section 4.4.

For the specific initialisation we set the initial value of *speed* to a large value (we found 100 to be heuristically a good guess) to better approximate the unit step. The translation parameter pos_x can be set as the x -positions of the lookup table of the shape function of EBM. The height of the shape function (described by pos_y) is finally set to the y -position of the EBM by first initialising all the pos_y to 0 and then adjusting the pos_y from the right-most to the left-most using Algorithm 1. An illustration of how this algorithm works can be seen in Fig. 4.3.

That said, the random initialisation can still be useful for some use cases where it is not straightforward to train an EBM (e.g., as components of an Autoencoder). We still suggest to initialise the parameter pos_x for shape i as the quantiles of the univariate distribution of feature i . On the other hand for classification and regression purposes we consistently found in our

preliminary experiments that EBM already converges to a close-to-optimal solution and initialising CNAM to that vastly improves the final model across both performance and intelligibility metrics.

Figure 4.3: Example of applying Algorithm 1 to some random dummy data with the aim of initialising CNAM as a good approximation of EBM.

Algorithm 1 Initialise CNAM as EBM

Require: y_{EBM}

$y_{CNAM} \leftarrow y_{EBM} * 0$

▷ Initialise all as zero

$y_{CNAM}[-1] \leftarrow y_{EBM}[-1]$

for $k = 2, k \leq \text{Length}(y_{EBM}) + 1, k++$ **do**

$y_{CNAM}[-k] \leftarrow y_{EBM}[-k]$

▷ Set the height to the desired one

$y_{CNAM}[-k+1] \leftarrow y_{CNAM}[-k+1] - y_{CNAM}[-k]$

▷ fix the effect on the following bin

end for

return y_{CNAM}

4.3.5 Optimisation

Once we have initialised the CNAM parameters, we can optimize the final loss, which includes both task-performance and task-interpretability terms, using a gradient-based optimizer such as ADAM [72]. This technique allows us to iteratively adjust the parameters of CNAM toward a solution that minimizes the target loss, even without an explicit closed-form formula for it. To control for overfitting, we periodically evaluate against a validation set and employ an early stopping criterion [27].

4.4 EXPERIMENTS

CNAM can be used both for binary classification or regression. We first benchmark the model with different regularization parameters on 56 binary classification datasets (see Section 4.4.1). Subsequently, we perform a deep dive into two specific datasets, a classification task (see Section 4.4.2) and a regression task (see Section 4.4.3), to provide a more in-depth analysis of the model’s behavior. We implemented CNAM as an open-source software¹, using Python and pytorch [106] as the deep learning backend infrastructure, structuring the code using pytorch-lightning library.

In our experiments, we explore the tradeoff between performance and interpretability by varying the weights of the weighted loss function according to the specific application domain. Although we lack theoretical convergence guarantees, our empirical observations suggest that by trying different coefficients, we can obtain a diverse set of solutions that effectively navigate the performance-interpretability tradeoff. Later in the subsections, we demonstrate this practically with different choices of regularization parameters as the added term for the loss.

4.4.1 Binary classification benchmark

In this section we focus our attention to the task of binary classification and we benchmark CNAM against other classifiers across 56 tabular datasets taken from [101]. We measure both task-performance and task-interpretability scores. The datasets are related to different domains and include both real data as well as simulated data and spans both in size and class imbalance. The basic properties of each dataset are reported in Table 4.2.

In order to compare the results we rank the models for each dataset sorting them with respect to the specific metric value they scored. Once this ranking is obtained, we average the rank across all the datasets. We selected three measures of classification performance:

- **Accuracy**: the fraction (percentage) of correctly classified instances.
- **F1-Score**: the geometric mean of precision and recall.
- **ROC AUC**: the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (i.e., under the ROC curve), that is the curve of true positives versus false positives at all classification thresholds.

In this chapter, we utilize the SHAP-Length (SL) metric to measure model interpretability in terms of model complexity. SL offers a concise yet powerful model-agnostic way to quantify the cognitive load required to understand model predictions. While we provide an overview of SL here, a detailed exploration of its conceptual underpinnings and calculation is presented

¹CNAM is available online at <https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/ettore.mariotti/cnam>

Table 4.2: Basic properties of each dataset tested in the benchmark study.

Dataset	# Instances	# Features	Class imbalance
analcadata aids	50	4	0.000000
analcadata asbestos	83	3	0.011758
analcadata bankruptcy	50	6	0.000000
analcadata boxing1	120	3	0.090000
analcadata boxing2	132	3	0.005739
analcadata creditscore	100	6	0.211600
analcadata cyyoung8092	97	10	0.255181
analcadata cyyoung9302	92	10	0.344518
analcadata fraud	42	11	0.145125
analcadata japansolvent	52	9	0.001479
analcadata lawsuit	264	4	0.732840
appendicitis	106	7	0.364543
australian	690	14	0.012132
backache	180	32	0.521605
biomed	209	8	0.079691
breast	699	10	0.096375
breast cancer	286	9	0.164507
breast cancer wisconsin	569	30	0.064940
breast w	699	9	0.096375
buggyCrx	690	15	0.012132
bupa	345	5	0.000412
clean1	476	168	0.016966
cleve	303	13	0.007940
colic	368	22	0.068053
corral	160	6	0.015625
credit a	690	15	0.012132
crx	690	15	0.012132
german	1000	20	0.160000
glass2	163	9	0.004554
heart c	303	13	0.007940
heart h	294	13	0.077792
heart statlog	270	13	0.012346
house votes 84	435	16	0.051795
hungarian	294	13	0.077792
irish	500	5	0.012544
labor	57	16	0.088950
lupus	87	3	0.038182
molecular biology promoters	106	57	0.000000
monk1	556	6	0.000000
monk2	601	6	0.098895
monk3	554	6	0.001577
mux6	128	6	0.000000
parity5	32	5	0.000000
pima	768	8	0.091254
prnn crabs	200	7	0.000000
prnn synth	250	2	0.000000
profb	672	9	0.111111
saheart	462	9	0.094470
sonar	208	60	0.004530
spect	267	22	0.345762
spectf	349	44	0.207560
threeOf9	512	9	0.004944
tic tac toe	958	9	0.094181
vote	435	16	0.051795
wdbc	569	30	0.064940
xd6	973	9	0.114332

in Chapter 5. This metric returns the number of SHAP attributions of each data point such that the set of attributions ϕ_i captures a given fraction (we settled at 90% here) of the overall

explanation mass $\sum_i |\phi_i|$. More formally: $SL_{90\%} :=$ the smallest i such that $\frac{\sum_i^{\text{sorted}}(|\phi_i|)}{\sum_i |\phi_i|} \leq 0.9$. This intuitively captures the length of the “compressed” explanation of each prediction, that is what a user would have to read in order to get a rough sense of what is the impact of different features. These lengths are then averaged across all the data points of the dataset in order to return a single interpretability score per dataset-model pair. It is important to note that SL might not always be the ideal measure of interpretability. Indeed, the best interpretability metric depends on the context, user preference, and the specific domain of the task. A model with a lower SL will typically have more sparse explanations, so the lower the SL, the less cognitive load burden on the user. This is a key consideration when choosing an interpretability metric, as the goal is to provide users with concise yet meaningful explanations that help them understand the model’s behavior and decision-making process.

As stated before, given the scores of each model on each dataset we can rank each model on the same dataset according to the various metrics. Once we have computed the ranking of all the metrics for all the models across all the datasets we can average them and delineate the Pareto front with the best solutions. The Pareto front is the set of all the Pareto-efficient solutions, that is all those solutions in multi-objective problems where no other solution is better than them in one of the objectives.

We tested CNAM against a pool of 12 different models, most of them implemented by the *scikit-learn* package [108]: Explainable Boosting Machines with pairwise interactions (EB2M) and without interactions (EBM-GAM), rf100 (Random Forest with 100 trees), rf1k (Random Forest with 1000 trees), svm (Support Vector Machine), XGB (eXtremely Gradient Boosting trees), lr (Logistic Regression), small-tree (a decision tree with maximum tree depth of 4), big-tree (a decision tree unconstrained), 3-nnc, 5-nnc, 10-nnc (respectively 3-, 5-, and 10- nearest neighbours classifiers).

In order to evaluate the capabilities of CNAM we evaluated three different variations of the proposed model, each with different regularisation coefficients. The regularisation was set up such that a sparsity constraint (L_1 norm on the α) is added to the classical cross entropy loss: $loss = crossentropy + \lambda_1 * \sum_i |\alpha_i|$. This way λ_1 becomes a macroscopic hyperparameter that favours model simplicity at the potential cost of task performance. We benchmarked CNAM with $\lambda_1 = 0$, $\lambda_1 = 0.1$, $\lambda_1 = 1$ in order to show how CNAM behaves with no regularisation, small regularisation and strong regularisation.

Every model is evaluated with 5-fold stratified cross validation. For each single dataset the models are ordered from the best to the worst thus producing a ranking (lower values thus correspond to better models). The ranking is then averaged across all the datasets and the results are reported in Figs. 4.4 and 4.5. Fig. 4.4 reports for the sake of clarity and readability only the mean of the computed rankings. In Fig. 4.5 the interested reader can see further details in the form of box plots that help understand what is the distribution of the rankings.

Figure 4.4: A benchmark of the performance-interpretability tradeoffs regarding different models on 56 datasets. The x-axis represents the relative Rank of interpretability (measured as SHAP-Length) while the y-axis corresponds to the relative Rank of performance (measured as ROC AUC, Accuracy, F1-Score). The best models lie in the lower-left part of the plots. The dotted blue lines highlight the Pareto front, i.e. the set of non-dominated solutions. Various instantiations of CNAM on average lie on that Pareto front, even without regularisation, CNAM scores better than EBM (without pairwise interactions).

The results suggest that CNAM unconstrained is equivalent to (if sometimes marginally better than) EBM-GAM. This makes sense as by design CNAM is initialised as a good approximation of EBM-GAM. Instead, when a regularisation of the form discussed above is applied, we can see how the different models actually lose classification performance but gain in interpretability, returning models on the Pareto front of the best tradeoffs. This is important because it is an indication that the model can not only retain competitive task performance but can successfully explore the tradeoff between competing constraints in a way that the result lies on the set of Pareto-efficient solutions. This is important because it demonstrates that CNAM offers a spectrum of solutions, ranging from near EBM-GAM levels of performance to significantly more interpretable models. This flexibility empowers users to choose the solution that best prioritizes their needs, whether that’s maximum performance or easily explainable results. Moreover, CNAM reg 1 turns up as the second best from the point of view of interpretability (see the plot related to “Explanation Length” on the bottom right side of Fig. 4.5), only behind small-tree while it is much better from the performance viewpoint (i.e., CNAM reg 1 is always better ranked than small-tree in the other pictures in Fig. 4.5).

Finally, it is worth noting that in a specific application a user should experiment with different regularisation parameters (and also specific regularisations fit to the specific domain) according to his or her needs.

4.4.2 Illustrative example on how to address a classification task: MAGIC dataset

In order to gain more intuition of the behaviour of CNAM on a specific dataset we provide as an application the use of CNAM for the MAGIC Telescopes classification dataset [23], a

Figure 4.5: A box plot with the results of the benchmark for the different models across the different statistics.

real-world dataset (taken from the UCI repository [42]) that is much larger than all of those included in the previous benchmark study. In this dataset the task is to distinguish between two different kind of particles (gamma-like vs hadrons) given a representation of the image captured by the telescope. From a physical point of view, a particle enters the atmosphere and produces an elliptic flash of light that is captured by the camera of the telescope. The image is then described by the following 10 numerical features, some of which describe an ellipsoidal shape fitted on the pixels:

- **fLength**: major axis of ellipse.
- **fWidth**: minor axis of ellipse.
- **fSize**: log 10 of the sum of content of all pixels (photon count).
- **fConc**: the ratio of sum of two highest pixels over fSize.
- **fConc1**: the ratio of highest pixel over fSize.
- **fAsym**: distance from highest pixel to center, projected onto major axis.
- **fM3Long**: 3rd root of third moment along major axis.
- **fM3Trans**: 3rd root of third moment along minor axis.
- **fAlpha**: angle of major axis with vector to origin.
- **fDist**: distance from origin to center of ellipse.

The dataset² has 19020 instances (12332 gamma and 6688 hadron), with a class imbalance of 0.542. In this task, the Accuracy metric is misleading because misclassifying a hadron (background) as a gamma (signal) severely impacts the experiment’s reliability. False positives pollute the signal region (ON region), reducing the signal-to-noise ratio and making it harder to confidently detect true astrophysical sources. Since IACT source detection depends on comparing gamma ray excess in the ON region to a non-source (OFF) region, a more sensible metric is ROC AUC. This allows us to evaluate classifier performance across different thresholds, helping us find a balance between reducing false positives (critical for a reliable ON/OFF comparison) and correctly identifying true gamma events.

For illustrative purposes we will fit CNAM with different regularisation parameters, namely λ_1 (encouraging sparsity, that is the shape functions tend more often to 0) and λ_2 (encouraging smooth shapes), drawing them randomly from a log-uniform distribution $Y = \log(X)$ where $X = U(-6, 1)$. Each candidate configuration is evaluated with a 5-fold stratified cross-validation with the ROC AUC score (performance) and $SL_{90\%}$ (interpretability). For comparison

²The interested reader can download the dataset from <https://doi.org/10.24432/C52C8B>

we will also fit other competitive models: EBM-GAM (as it is CNAM initialisation), EB2M and Random Forest with 1000 trees (as both models demonstrated high performances on the previous benchmark study). In Fig. 4.6 is shown how each model scores in the performance-interpretability space.

Figure 4.6: Performance-Interpretability tradeoff on the MAGIC Telescopes dataset. CNAM configurations are colored by the amount of λ_1 regularization, with blue indicating high regularization and green representing low regularization. More interpretable models with lower SL (x-axis) and better performance (y-axis) are situated in the upper-left corner of the figure. It is important to note that λ_2 also influences the results, but we have omitted its visualization for the sake of clarity.

It is interesting to notice how EB2M and Random Forest both perform significantly better in terms of average ROC AUC than EBM-GAM and CNAM, suggesting that higher-order interactions between features are relevant for the specific task. That said, CNAM solutions have very similar performances as EBM-GAM, while being more interpretable (having a smaller $SL_{90\%}$).

To understand how the model behaves globally (global explanation) it is possible to visualise each univariate shape function of CNAM as a function of the feature values. Indeed in Fig. 4.7 it is possible to see such an explanation.

The blue histogram describes the empirical distribution of data (with counts mapped on the right axis of each plot) while the two lines in each subplot show the shape functions of the most interpretable (CNAM best SL) and of the best-performing CNAM solution (CNAM best ROC AUC) of the Pareto front which is depicted in Fig. 4.6.

As it is, it is not straightforward how to make a comparison of the two different solutions as they might have a different fit intercept on the final linear layer. For better appreciating the difference between the solutions, Fig. 4.8 shows them scaled (the contribution of CNAM best SL is marked on the left axis, the one of CNAM best ROC AUC is marked on the right axis).

Figure 4.7: Visual representation of each shape function of CNAM on the MAGIC Telescopes dataset. Each shape function demonstrates the contribution of a given feature value to the final prediction, which is the sum of the partial scores. The blue solid line represents the most interpretable CNAM instance (CNAM best SL), identified as having the shortest Shap Length (SL), while the dotted red line indicates the best-performing instance (CNAM best ROC AUC), which has the highest AUC (Area Under The Curve) ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristics) curve score among models trained with varying λ_1 and λ_2 regularization parameters. The data distribution is visualized as a histogram in the background, with the counts reported on the right-axis of the plot.

Both models rely heavily on the $fAlpha$ feature in a remarkably similar way, but while **CNAM best ROC AUC** also takes into account other quantities, **CNAM best SL** sacrifices the use of some features (like $fDist$, $fConc$, $fConc1$, $fAsym$) in order to gain more interpretability while keeping performance reasonable. This could be useful information for the data scientist working on the task, as he or she might decide to refine the measurement of $fAlpha$ or introduce new features that describe a similar physical phenomenon. It could be argued that by reducing

Figure 4.8: A modified version of Figure 4.7, with each shape function adjusted for scale and without the histograms in the background for ease of comparison between the CNAM best SL and CNAM best ROC AUC models. In each plot, the left axis represents the log-odds contribution of the CNAM best SL (blue solid line), while the right axis corresponds to the contribution of the CNAM best ROC AUC (red dotted line).

the reliance on some features it is possible to obtain a more interpretable model at the price of some performance, but this can still be useful for directing the attention of the user to relevant information that can enhance globally the pipeline of the experiment (that is, measuring new things, discover biases or problems in simulations and in general design better experiments).

Still, as remarked earlier, the significantly higher performance of Random Forest and EB2M suggests that restricting the modelling to only the univariate components (as EBM-GAM and CNAM do) might be inappropriate for this specific task. The final choice of which class of models to use depends on the data and the impact that such an intelligent system has on the

world. While a physicist might be comfortable with not knowing why a given event was labelled as either gamma-like or hadron (thus opting for a black box with higher performances), a doctor might trust more on a less performing yet more interpretable model for a diagnostic system that should guide his or her decision process.

4.4.3 Illustrative example on how to address a regression task: California Housing dataset

In order to show how CNAM can be used not only for solving and gaining insights in classification problems but also for regression tasks, in this section we go in depth with the California Housing dataset [69]. This dataset, derived from the 1990 U.S. census, describes each California district based on 7 numerical features and aims at predicting the median house value of that district. It has 20640 instances. The features are the following:

- **MedInc**: the median income in a district.
- **HouseAge**: the median age of the house in a district.
- **AveRooms**: the average number of rooms per household.
- **Population**: the population of the district.
- **AveOccup**: the average number of household members.
- **Latitude**: the latitude of the district.
- **Longitude**: the longitude of the district.

The target to be modelled is the median house value for each California district (in 100k \$). We fit the model following the setup described earlier in the classification experiment. One significant difference is the performance metric, which in this context is the R^2 score. The R^2 score, also known as *coefficient of determination*, is a regression metric that represents the target proportion of variance that has been explained by the features and is defined as $R^2(y, \hat{y}) = 1 - \frac{\sum_i y_i - \hat{y}_i}{\sum_i y_i - \frac{\sum_i y_i}{n}}$. In linear settings, it is equivalent to the square of a correlation coefficient. The focus is on finding different solutions that explore the tradeoff between the two quality metrics (i.e., R^2 and $SL_{90\%}$). We also fit an LR model (for its simplicity), EBM-GAM, EB2M and Random Forest that will serve as baselines for comparison, as we did in the previous illustrative example (Section 4.4.2).

Fig. 4.9 summarises graphically the result of the experiment. Interestingly, CNAM offers a set of solutions belonging to the Pareto front of optimal solutions in terms of $SL_{90\%}$ and R^2 score. Notably, we found solutions that have a similar R^2 score as LR while being almost twice

as interpretable. Conversely, we also find solutions that have the same interpretability as LR while performing significantly better ($R^2=0.75$ vs $R^2=0.6$, i.e., an improvement of 25%).

Figure 4.9: Performance-Interpretability tradeoff on the California Housing dataset. CNAM configurations are colored by the amount of regularisation, blue means high regularisation while green means low regularisation. As a reminder, the best models would be in the upper-left corner of the figure.

In Fig. 4.10 we plotted the shape functions of the three CNAM configurations chosen from the Pareto front of the earlier experiment, similarly to what was done in Fig. 4.7. The solid blue line (**CNAM best SL**) is the model that has the same R^2 score of LR while being roughly twice more interpretable in terms of $SL_{90\%}$. The red dotted line (**CNAM best R^2**) is the model that reached the highest R^2 score while the green dash-dotted line (**CNAM Smooth**) is a configuration where smoothness was encouraged thanks to the regularisation of the *speed* parameters. It is possible to see how the shape functions of **CNAM best SL** are more often close to zero, de facto ignoring features such as HouseAge, AveBedrms, Population, giving less importance to the geographical location (Latitude and Longitude are less prominent) and instead relying a lot mainly on MedInc. **CNAM best R^2** is more jagged and uses more features in a precise way, this way it can closely model what the data has to say and can achieve a relatively higher R^2 . **CNAM Smooth** has an in-between representation with the characteristic of being smoother. It can be argued that the smoothness of the shape functions gives an overall easier-to-describe global explanation.

Figure 4.10: The shape functions of three different models fitted on the California Housing dataset with different constraints. The dotted red line represents the solution that only maximised the performances on the task (R^2 score). The blue solid one is the model that balanced complexity and interpretability (measured with $SL_{90\%}$). The green dot-dashed line instead is the result of a model with a penalty that encouraged a smooth representation (a useful property for example when verbalising the plot is of interest). Note: for better readability we excluded from the plot data points with extreme values (i.e., districts with vacation resorts with a high number of empty rooms and few resident households).

4.5 LIMITATIONS

In the experiments, we employed the SHAP-Length metric to assess the interpretability of models with diverse structures. Future developments might yield alternative metrics better suited for specific use cases or expert preferences, allowing for more tailored evaluations.

CNAM's applicability to various data types presents some challenges and considerations. The key requirement for maintaining interpretability is the use of interpretable features. Adapt-

ing CNAM to other tasks involving different data types, like images, text, or time series, requires representing these data types in tabular format through feature engineering. A coherent explanation of the model’s predictions might be difficult to derive when applying CNAM directly to pixel-level data in images or to neural network embeddings of text or time series data.

In the context of data fusion, the key to preserving interpretability in a CNAM model lies in the effective transformation of unstructured data into an interpretable tabular format. Through representation learning or feature engineering techniques, unstructured data can be converted into a tabular form with interpretable features, allowing for the effective application of CNAM to data fusion tasks.

Finally, CNAM is restricted to univariate feature modeling, which disregards higher-order feature interactions. Although this simplification allows for easy-to-understand, interpretable models, it inevitably constrains the expressiveness of the model when faced with complex interactions between features. Balancing this trade-off remains a challenge and a potential direction for future research. Feature engineering techniques that explicitly encode known interactions or domain-specific knowledge could be incorporated into the tabular data before applying CNAM. Alternatively, research could explore the development of constrained higher-order interaction terms that maintain some level of interpretability, although this would require a careful design for finding out the right balance between expressiveness and understandability.

4.6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This chapter has introduced CNAM, a constrainable NAM designed for both performance and interpretability. While it can be initialized to match an arbitrary function (like a near-optimal EBM), its key advantage lies in its ability to move away from that initial solution in a controlled way. The model’s decomposable nature aids inspection, and its structure allows constraints to be applied in a way that directly enhances interpretability. Crucially, by adjusting regularization coefficients, users can directly explore the trade-off between performance and interpretability, finding solutions that are tailored to their needs. Our benchmark on 56 classification datasets demonstrates that CNAM consistently finds models that offer both competitive performance and significantly improved interpretability compared to the EBM baseline. The provided illustrative examples further highlight CNAM’s ability to balance these objectives across different task types.

It is worth noting that CNAM is available as open source software³.

As future work, more specific constraints could be designed to accommodate specific needs. For example, it would be of interest to give the model the ability to express an explanation of its behavior with natural language, rather than just with the visual modality. Another promising direction would be to enhance the human-computer interaction via integration with GAM-changer

³<https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/ettore.mariotti/cnam>

[151]. This way, both the model and the user could benefit from a feedback loop that iteratively refines the desired objectives in terms of performance and interpretability. In addition, exploring more intelligent search techniques, for instance by resorting to multi-objective metaheuristics, would be a valuable direction for future research to further improve the model’s capability in the search for better tradeoffs in the Pareto space.

Efficiently creating counterfactual explanations [139] using CNAM by exploiting the specific structure of the model is another potential research direction. Additionally, it would be intriguing to explore whether a differentiable version of diverse and compelling counterfactuals properties (as proposed in [38]) could be formalized and subsequently incorporated into CNAM.

Finally, enabling pairwise interactions could significantly boost the task performance, albeit at the cost of harder interpretability.

DISCLAIMER

Most of the content in this chapter was extracted from the following publication (see further details on its reproduction policy in Chapter 1):

Ettore Mariotti, José María Alonso Moral, and Albert Gatt. *Exploring the balance between interpretability and performance with carefully designed constrainable Neural Additive Models*. Information Fusion, 2023. ISSN: 1872-6305, 1566-2535. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2023.101882>.

5 Complexity and Surrogate-Faithfulness Metrics Based on Shapley Values

The increasing complexity of machine learning models brings a pressing need for tools that go beyond measuring performance. We need ways to assess how readily we can understand a model’s decision-making process and how much trust we can place in simpler ”surrogate” models that aim to explain complex ones. Shapley values, introduced in Chapter 3 Section 3.5.4, offer a powerful foundation for addressing these challenges.

This chapter explores two metrics built upon Shapley values:

- A novel metric, called SHAP Length Complexity, aimed at quantifying the complexity of understanding a given model based on the distribution of its Shapley values. This allows stakeholders to gauge how intuitively interpretable a model is, providing valuable insights for both deployment and further refinement.
- A metric designed for evaluating the faithfulness of global surrogate models relative to their black-box counterparts, which we call ShapGap. By quantifying how well the surrogate model approximates the original, this metric serves as a reliable indicator of the trust one can place in the interpretability offered by the surrogate.

The connection between these metrics lies in their shared goal of improving explainability. SHAP Length Complexity reveals the complexity barrier of a model itself, while ShapGap helps us understand how well a surrogate model captures the complexity (or lack thereof) within the original black-box model. Both have practical implications in XAI, supporting informed choices about model selection and surrogate model development, ultimately fostering more transparent and trustworthy AI systems.

5.1 SHAP LENGTH COMPLEXITY

There are different approaches to XAI. While some researchers try to develop model-agnostic tools that are as widely applicable as possible (post-hoc explanations) [57, 82, 114], others instead push for the development of intrinsically interpretable models, arguing that white-box models can be as powerful as the so-called black-box models [7, 119, 120].

We thus have lots of models which are explainable to different degrees, but what we lack is a model-agnostic way of capturing the interplay between (a) the simplicity of the model (regarding Ockham’s razor principle) and (b) its empirical performance on one or more tasks. In practice, typically what is done is to measure the complexity of a specific model by looking at some model-specific properties (for example the number of nodes in a decision tree). This is fine when we restrict our explorations to just one class of models, but it is problematic when we want to explore and compare different families of models (e.g., is it fair to compare the number of nodes in a tree to the number of non-zero coefficients in a linear model?).

In this section we present a metric for evaluating model understandability that is model-agnostic, intuitive, computationally efficient and mathematically grounded. This can enable a fairer comparison between different models on specific datasets. In addition, it enables the possibility of multi-objective optimisation guided by automated metrics for both performance and understandability. And last but not least, it can push the development of more explainable models.

5.1.1 Complexity as a proxy for understandability

Automatic metrics of understandability typically measure model-specific complexity as a proxy for understandability [4], e.g., the number of rules in an expert system, the number of non-zero coefficients in a linear model, the number of nodes in a decision tree, etc. This way of doing might work while dealing within just one class of models but becomes difficult to compare across different classes of models. Molnar et al. [92] proposed to overcome this issue by creating a metric for complexity based on functional decomposition. They count the number of features used by a pipeline with permutation-based evaluation and estimate the interaction effects with accumulated local effects. While being a good approach (for example for multi-objective optimisation) it is not straightforward to see how such approach is related to understandability. Furthermore, the way with which their complexity metric is set up is somewhat arbitrary and not intuitive.

Zhou et al. [155] developed a hybrid survey-based evaluation method to find out how a linear model and a tree are understandable. In addition, they created a meta-model that fits the human evaluation using some attributes of the underlying model. Unfortunately, this approach does not allow the use of the new metric out of the scope of the conducted experiments. Moreover, the reported results (and the generated meta-model) highly depend on the population on which the survey was conducted.

This underscores the need for a novel metric that overcomes these limitations and addresses the following key points:

- Model Agnosticism: The metric should be universally applicable regardless of model type

- Computational Efficiency: in order to be practically useful, its computation should be feasible in a reasonable amount of time
- Theoretical Foundation: The metric should have a sound basis in established principles.
- Intuitive Alignment: The metric should reflect how humans intuitively perceive complexity.

5.1.2 Model-agnostic Automatic Metrics: SHAP Length and SHAP Interaction Length

Having underscored the critical limitations of existing metrics and outlined the essential characteristics of an ideal metric for explainable AI, we now turn our attention to the practical realization of these principles. We propose two novel metrics: SHAP Length and SHAP Interaction Length. These metrics are designed to embody the desired qualities of model agnosticism, computational efficiency, theoretical grounding, and intuitive alignment with human cognition.

Understanding how humans process information is crucial for designing effective explanations. The principle of minimum cognitive load [145] highlights the importance of presenting information in a way that optimizes working memory usage. Since working memory is limited in capacity and duration [16], explanations that minimize the load on this system are more likely to be understood. With this in mind, we formulate our research hypothesis as follows: an explanation with a lower cognitive load has more possibilities to be digested by humans (and can thus be deemed as “understandable”) than one with a higher load.

To operationalize this concept, we build upon the foundation of SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values, a concept with roots in cooperative game theory. This framework offers a robust means to attribute contributions of individual features to a model’s prediction (for a detailed treatment of SHAP values, see Chapter 3.5.4). The use of SHAP values fosters model agnosticism while providing theoretically sound and fair attributions. Furthermore, efficient computational techniques like TreeSHAP and KernelSHAP make it feasible to compute these metrics across a wide range of model architectures.

5.1.2.1 Intuitive idea

For a user to understand the behaviour of a model by means of SHAP, he/she has to pay attention to every non-zero value of a given explanation. We can further generalise this notion to the user having to look at a subset of explanations whose aggregate contribution sum up to a certain threshold. The idea is that if for a specific prediction we have a few non-zero Shapely values, the user has to look at fewer *details*. The explanation is thus relatively more understandable than another where instead many features contribute to the output (see Fig. 5.1). We can also think about this as a lossy compression of the explanation, where the amount of information loss

Figure 5.1: Two different Breast Cancer instances classified by Random Forest and explained by SHAP whose output is compressed to a 95% mass threshold (see Section 5.1.2.2 for further details). Instance (B) is relatively easier to be understood wrt (A) in virtue of carrying a lower cognitive load (i.e., it involves fewer pieces of information) to a user. ©2022, IEEE.

can be controlled precisely. We can then extrapolate from the aggregation of many explanations on the same dataset that if the explanations associated with a model involve on average less features, then the model is less complex than one that involves more of them.

In the following sections we introduce two novel explainability metrics which are built upon SHAP:

- SHAP Length (SL): based on Shapley Values [82].
- SHAP Interaction Length (SIL): based on Shapley Interaction Values [81], where an importance score is given also to pairwise interaction effects.

5.1.2.2 Formal Definitions

Lundberg and Lee [82] introduced the use of SHAP as a numerical and visual explanation of the impact that each feature in a given data instance had on the associated prediction.

As introduced in section 3.5.4, the set $\Phi := \{\phi_i\}$ corresponds to the Shapley allocation of a coalitional game where i features are seen as players and the payoff is the difference between the model output and its average value (also called baseline).

Let us now consider the following useful definitions:

Definition 5.1.1 (Explanation mass). For a local SHAP explanation on an instance with p features $\{\phi_i, i = 1 \dots p\}$, we define explanation mass associated to each feature i to be $|\phi_i|$.

Definition 5.1.2 (Complete explanation). A subset of Shapley values $\Phi_c \subseteq \Phi$ is *complete* if $\Phi_c := \{|\phi_i| > 0, \forall i\}$. In other words, it is an explanation that describes all the i features that have contributed to the outcome (i.e., $|\phi_i| > 0$). For example, given a local explanation $\{\phi_1 = 0.4, \phi_2 = 0, \phi_3 = -1.2\}$, we have that the explanation $\{\phi_1 = 0.4, \phi_3 = -1.2\}$ is still complete. This is because it includes all features that actively drive the model's output, with zero-contribution features implicitly understood to have no effect.

Definition 5.1.3 (Explanation completeness). For a given subset $\Phi_{subset} \subseteq \Phi_c$, we call *completeness* the scalar

$$\Gamma(\Phi) := \frac{\sum_{i \in \Phi_{subset}} |\phi_i|}{\sum_{i \in \Phi_c} |\phi_i|}.$$

In other words, it is the fraction of explanation mass of a complete explanation that a given subset of explanands captures. Intuitively it represents the fraction of information that the subset has, compared to a complete one. Notice that $0 \leq \Gamma(\Phi) \leq 1$ and we can refer to it in a percentage form for convenience. As a practical example, in Fig. 5.2 the subset of explanands in the big red box has a completeness of $\Gamma(\{\phi_i \text{ for } i \in \text{red box}\}) = 95\%$.

Figure 5.2: Examples of different SHAP Length (SL) values for different explanation mass thresholds, respectively of 80%, 90% and 95% for instance #424 of Breast Cancer Dataset. For ease of visualisation, the value of each ϕ_i is reported rounded to the second digit. ©2022, IEEE.

Definition 5.1.4. The $p\%$ -complete explanation is the smallest set of Shapley values Φ such that $\Gamma(\Phi) \geq p$.

Definition 5.1.5. $SL_{p\%} := |\Phi_p|$ is the number of features in the $p\%$ -complete explanation. Similarly, $SIL_{p\%}$ is the cardinality of the $p\%$ -complete explanation (i.e., the number of involved features) in a SHAP interaction graph, where one can take only the lower (or upper) triangular matrix of the explanation, due to its symmetric nature, for efficient computing purposes.

5.1.2.3 Implementation Details

The algorithm for computing SL orders the absolute Shapley values from the largest to the lowest (normalised by the total). Then the SL value is the first index for which the cumulative sum is greater than or equal to the given threshold. A pseudocode version is given in Algorithm 2. SIL is computed with the same Algorithm 2 with the difference that it uses the flattened vector of the lower triangular matrix of Shapley interaction values. In general, it is computationally expensive to compute Shapley interaction values. Fortunately, it is possible to have a very fast exact implementation for tree ensembles that can leverage GPU hardware [90]. For practical purposes, we will compute both SL and SIL with Gradient Boosted Trees from the XGBOOST package (xgb) [30] which acts as a surrogate of the original model. The faithfulness of this surrogate is measured as the R^2 score between the prediction of the original model (log odds in case of classification) and the output of the surrogate.

Algorithm 2 SHAP Length (SL)

Require: $\{\phi_i\}$ for $i = 1 \dots p$, th

Ensure: $SL_{th\%}$

```

1: ExplanationMass  $\leftarrow |\phi_i|$ 
2: TotalMass  $\leftarrow \text{Total}(\textit{ExplanationMass})$ 
3: Ordering  $\leftarrow \text{ArgSort}(\textit{ExplanationMass})$ 
4: CumNormMass  $\leftarrow \text{CumSum}(\textit{ExplanationMass}[\textit{Ordering}])/\textit{TotalMass}$ 
5: for  $i = 0$  to  $p - 1$  do
6:   if  $\textit{CumNormMass}[i] > th$  then
7:      $SL_{th\%} \leftarrow i$ 
8:   return  $SL_{th\%}$ 
9:   end if
10: end for

```

5.1.3 Experimental Study

In this section we present some practical use cases to illustrate the validity and utility of SL and SIL. We explore how different models populate the performance-understandability tradeoff and how the proposed metrics relate to other well-known model-specific complexity metrics. In addition, we will compare several families of models, with different degrees of transparency, regarding a classification dataset and a regression dataset. We are looking for the models that have the best performance and the best understandability (i.e., the smallest complexity in terms of SL and SIL). For this it is useful to pay attention to the associated Pareto front (the ranking of models for which there is no other competitor which is better in either performance or understandability) for the datasets under consideration.

5.1.3.1 Balance between performance and understandability

We propose an empirical exploration of the performance-understandability tradeoff in terms of the balance between accuracy and complexity for different algorithms on a classification dataset (Breast Cancer [152]) and a regression dataset (Boston House¹). On the one hand, the Breast Cancer dataset corresponds to a binary classification problem in the medical domain, with a total of 569 data instances (212 instances associated with Malign class and 357 instances associated with Benign class) which relate 30 real-valued features. On the other hand, the Boston House dataset includes 506 data instances that relate 13 real-valued features with the target of predicting housing prices.

The following algorithms are tested:

- k-Nearest neighbours (i.e., 10-nearest and 5-nearest, with $k=10$ and $k=5$ respectively),
- Decision Tree (dt),
- Fuzzy Decision Tree Classifier with s-shaped fuzzy partitions (fuzzy_tree) [100],
- Decision Tree with a maximum depth of 2 (dt_depth_2),
- Fuzzy Decision Tree Classifier with a maximum depth of 2 (fuzzy_tree_depth_2),
- Explainable Boosting Machines (ebm),
- Explainable Boosting Machines without interaction values (ebm_0) [99],
- Logistic Regression with L2 regularisation (lr_l2),
- Logistic Regression with L1 regularisation (lr_l1),
- Random Forest (rf),
- Support Vector Machine (svm),
- Gradient Boosted Trees (xgb).

For the regression experiments we used the regression version of the above-mentioned models (except for Fuzzy Decision Trees which are only available in Python for classification) with the addition of Linear Regression with L2 (lr_l2) and L1 (lasso) regularisation. Each model is trained with default parameters and evaluated with 10-fold cross-validation using the Python package scikit-learn [107]. It is worth noting that the xgb-based surrogate reported mean R^2 score of 0.997 and 0.982 on the Breast Cancer [140] and Boston House [62] datasets, respectively.

¹<http://lib.stat.cmu.edu/datasets/boston>

Reported results for the Breast Cancer dataset are summarised in Fig. 5.3. It is interesting to appreciate quantitatively the tension between understandability and performance which is reported also elsewhere in the literature [59]. In particular, we can see how decision trees (including in this category `fuzzy_tree_depth_2`) and nearest neighbour approaches produce by far the simplest models but at the cost of the smallest performance. The Pareto front with the non-dominated models in terms of SL and F1-score (see the plot in the left of Fig. 5.3) includes `dt_depth_2` (the simplest and least accurate model), `dt`, `10-nearest`, `rf`, `fuzzy_tree`, `xgb`, `lr_l1` and `lr_l2` (the most complex and accurate model). Interestingly, `fuzzy_tree` turns up as a compromise solution. Notice that `fuzzy_tree` is close to `rf` and `xgb` regarding both performance and complexity while it is a single model versus ensemble models. Moreover, `fuzzy_tree` can be endowed with linguistic interpretability which is likely to be appreciated in a number of applications.

Figure 5.3: An empirical exploration of performance-understandability tradeoff of different algorithms on the Breast Cancer dataset. Each metric has been computed with 10-fold Cross-Validation. Performance is measured as the F1 Score. Understandability is associated with the $SL_{90\%}$ and $SIL_{90\%}$. The best models would be in the bottom-right part of each plot. ©2022, IEEE.

The Pareto front with the non-dominated models in terms of SIL and F1-score (see the plot in the right of Fig. 5.3) is slightly different. It includes: `dt_depth_2` (the simplest and least accurate model), `dt`, `10-nearest`, `xgb`, `lr_l1` and `lr_l2` (the most complex and accurate model). It is worth noting that `xgb` dominates `rf` and `fuzzy_tree` when interactions come into play. Indeed, SHAP interaction graphs are harder to interpret and this is reflected in the fact that SIL values are higher than SL values. F1-score computes the harmonic mean of precision and recall; thus giving the relation between true positives (TP), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN), which is especially informative in the case of unbalanced classification datasets:

$$F1 - score = 2 * \frac{precision * recall}{precision + recall} = \frac{2}{2 * TP + FN + FP}$$

As observed in Fig. 5.4, SL and SIL are highly correlated. This means we can rely on SL (which is easier to compute) as an estimate for SIL.

The same behaviour is observed in the Boston Dataset dataset (see Fig. 5.6) but in this case the non-dominated models are only `dt_depth_2` (the simplest model) and `rf` (the most accurate

Figure 5.4: Correlation graph with SL versus SIL. Here is shown the value for each of the 10 folds for each model trained on the Breast Cancer.

model). In this regression problem we measure performance as the negative mean square error (Negative MSE) as follows:

$$\text{Negative MSE} = -\frac{1}{N} * \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

where N is the number of test data instances, \hat{y}_i is the predicted output for instance i and y_i is the actual output for the same instance.

5.1.3.2 Multi-objective optimisation

As a use case we present an exploration of a grid-search for decision regressor trees and linear regression with L1 and L2 regularisation (also known as elastic net) on the Boston House Dataset. We choose these models as they are considered interpretable. We deem interesting to evaluate which part of the complexity-performance space they occupy.

The parameter grid for trees spanned the depth of the trees from 2 to 12 and a regularisation parameter $ccp-\alpha$ from 0 to 1. The parameters of Linear Regression instead were the penalty coefficient α spanning from 0 to 1 and the “L1 amount ratio”, which controlled how much the L1 regularisation was wrt L2, also spanning from 0 to 1.

Fig. 5.5 summarises the reported results. Each point is a different configuration evaluated with 4-fold cross-validation. Interestingly, for this dataset it seems that regression trees can be better both in performance and understandability compared to linear regression. By comparing it to Fig. 5.6, we can see how in the space of understandable models we could find solutions that can be competitive to other black-box approaches.

Figure 5.5: Complexity (90% SL)/Accuracy (Negative MSE) tradeoff of an exhaustive grid search of decision trees on the Boston House Dataset (4-fold cross validation). ©2022, IEEE.

Figure 5.6: An empirical exploration of the performance-understandability tradeoff of different algorithms on the Boston House dataset. Each metric has been computed with 10-fold Cross-Validation. Performance is measured as negative MSE. Understandability is associated with the $SL_{90\%}$ and $SIL_{90\%}$. The best models would be in the bottom-right part of each plot. ©2022, IEEE.

5.1.3.3 Relationship to popular complexity measures associated with white-box models

For these novel metrics (SL and SIL) to be valid we would expect them to be somehow proportional to some other intuitive, well-established (yet model-specific) metrics commonly used in the literature to measure complexity. In particular, we explored on the Boston House dataset the family of regression trees with the same hyperparameters grid-search used in [5.1.3.2](#), evaluating 1000 configurations with 4-fold cross-validation. In [Fig. 5.7](#) we compare $SL_{98\%}$ with the number of nodes (plot on the left) and with the number of leaves (plot on the right) in a regression tree.

Figure 5.7: SL is proportional to the complexity of the tree measured as the number of nodes (roughly equivalent to "concepts") and the number of leaves (equivalent to the length of a rule list). Notice that #Nodes and #Leaves are very similar to each other up to a scale factor due to the specific details of the tree construction. ©2022, IEEE.

The number of nodes is a measure of how many concepts the tree needs for doing well the regression task while the number of leaves translates to how long would be an equivalent list of rules. Both number of nodes and leaves are widely used in the literature to measure the complexity of trees. Notably, SL tends to saturate while the other metrics do not, this is because SL has an upper bound determined by the number of features in the dataset, while the complexity

metrics of a tree are unbounded because a tree can in principle become arbitrarily large. We can see that the two metrics are proportional to each other such that a higher SL corresponds to a higher complexity metric. This means that if we used any of these metrics for choosing the least complex model we would have probably have had the same outcome. This allows for more meaningful comparisons of interpretability across a wider range of model types.

5.2 MEASURING FAITHFULNESS OF SURROGATE MODELS

Surrogate models, which are interpretable white-box (WB) models trained to approximate the behavior of black-box (BB) models, have emerged as a popular approach for providing explanations in XAI [114]. These surrogate models are particularly relevant in use cases where BB models are unavailable due to security or practical concerns or when stakeholders require explanations to support their decision-making processes. For instance, in healthcare, a BB model may predict the likelihood of a patient having a specific disease based on various symptoms and test results. A surrogate model that provides the same prediction but with a different rationale could lead medical professionals to focus on the wrong symptoms or tests, resulting in incorrect treatment or mismanagement of the patient’s condition. In finance, a BB model might predict the probability of default for loan applicants based on their credit history, income, and other financial factors. A surrogate model that matches the BB model’s predictions but with different reasoning could lead to unfair lending decisions or increased financial risk for the lending institution.

However, evaluating the faithfulness of these surrogate models remains challenging. Traditional fidelity measures such as accuracy focus on the similarity of the final predictions between the BB model and surrogate WB model. This can lead to a significant limitation, as a surrogate model might be considered faithful even if it provides the same prediction as the BB model but with a completely different rationale. In critical applications like the ones mentioned above, this can be dangerous, as decision-makers might act on unfaithful explanations, leading to suboptimal or even harmful outcomes [68].

In this section, we address this limitation by introducing a novel metric called ShapGAP, which assesses the faithfulness of surrogate models by comparing their reasoning paths with those of the original BB models, using SHAP explanations as a proxy. ShapGAP measures the average L2 distance between the SHAP explanations of BB and WB models, providing a more comprehensive evaluation of surrogate model faithfulness that goes beyond the similarity of final predictions. The main contributions are:

- We propose ShapGAP, a novel metric for evaluating surrogate model faithfulness that considers the reasoning paths of the models by comparing their SHAP explanations.

- We demonstrate the effectiveness of ShapGAP through experiments with real-world datasets, comparing it against traditional fidelity measures.
- We highlight the potential dangers and ethical concerns of relying on unfaithful explanations in critical applications, drawing on philosophical arguments for truthfulness and ethical AI.

5.2.1 Proposed Approach: ShapGAP

For giving context, it's appropriate to recall some preliminary concepts before defining ShapGAP. We define a BB model as a function $f_{bb} : X \rightarrow Y$, where X is the input space and Y is the output space, and a WB model as a function $f_{wb} : X \rightarrow Y$. As a reminder, SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) provides a model-agnostic way to quantify the importance of each feature in a model's prediction. For a deeper look, see the earlier discussion in this chapter or Chapter 3.5.4.

Given a dataset D with n instances, we compute the SHAP values for each instance x_i in D for both the BB and WB models. Let $S_{bb}(x_i)$ and $S_{wb}(x_i)$ represent the SHAP values for instance x_i for the BB and WB models, respectively.

To define a generic version of ShapGAP, we use a distance function $d(\cdot, \cdot)$ that measures the dissimilarity between the SHAP explanations of the BB and WB models for instance x_i . The ShapGAP metric is then the average of these distances across all instances in the dataset:

$$\text{ShapGAP}(D, d) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n d(S_{bb}(x_i), S_{wb}(x_i)) \quad (5.1)$$

We can implement the distance function $d(S_{bb}(x_i), S_{wb}(x_i))$ using different distance measures, such as the L2 Euclidean distance and the Cosine distance. The L2 Euclidean distance, as shown in Equation (5.2), is more precise and faithful to the final probability values, as the SHAP explanations sum up to the output of the model. This choice emphasizes the importance of the exact contribution of each feature in the explanation and is more sensitive to differences in magnitude between SHAP values associated to BB and WB models.

$$\text{ShapGAP}(D, L2) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|S_{bb}(x_i) - S_{wb}(x_i)\|_2 \quad (5.2)$$

However, it is noteworthy to mention some limitations of the L2 Euclidean distance. This method is sensitive to outliers, which means that a single instance with a large disparity in SHAP values can significantly affect the overall distance. Therefore, L2 Euclidean distance might not represent the overall similarity well in the presence of outliers.

On the other hand, the Cosine distance (see Equation (5.3)) is more relaxed and focuses on the similarity in the direction of the SHAP explanations rather than their magnitude. This choice

allows for finding out surrogate models with similar reasoning paths, even if the magnitude of their feature contributions differs. By being more scale-agnostic with respect to the magnitude of the explanations, the Cosine distance might be better suited for cases where the focus is on the general structure of the explanation, rather than the exact values of the SHAP contributions.

$$\text{ShapGAP}(D, \text{Cos}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{S_{bb}(x_i) \cdot S_{wb}(x_i)}{\|S_{bb}(x_i)\|_2 \|S_{wb}(x_i)\|_2} \right) \quad (5.3)$$

By offering these two distance measures, the ShapGAP metric can accommodate different application requirements and preferences, providing more flexibility in the evaluation of surrogate model faithfulness.

To compute SHAP values, we use the widely adopted *shap* package², which offers efficient implementations for various types of models. For tree-like models such as random forests and decision trees, the package provides the fast TreeSHAP algorithm. Likewise, for linear models, an efficient method based on the coefficients of the model is available. In cases where the BB model is neither tree-based nor linear, the package offers a model-agnostic method called KernelSHAP, which can be applied to any model at the expense of increased computational cost. By leveraging these implementations, we can calculate the ShapGAP metric for a diverse range of surrogate models, ensuring that the metric remains flexible and adaptable to various application scenarios.

5.2.2 Experiments

In this section, we present the experimental setting for using and validating ShapGAP with both L2 and Cosine distance metrics, compared against Task Accuracy, Fidelity Accuracy (in the sense of model accuracy, i.e., the accuracy with respect to the labels predicted by the BB model), and the earlier introduced complexity metric ShapLength [85]. By examining ShapLength alongside ShapGAP, we can assess the trade-offs between faithfulness and simplicity in surrogate models. Additionally, this allows us to gain insights into the relative complexity of the original and surrogate models, an important indicator of how well the surrogate captures the behavior of the black-box model.

To align with the problem suggested in the introduction, we use two popular datasets: the Breast Cancer dataset [140], which contains 569 instances with 30 features, and the German Credit score dataset from UCI [42], which includes 1,000 instances with 20 features. Both datasets are widely used for benchmarking machine learning models in the context of binary classification. For surrogating we employ the Audit approach and perform a 10-fold cross-validation. Then, we compute the quality metrics on the test set. The reported results represent the average across all the folds. To explore various surrogate models, we train Decision Trees

²<https://github.com/shap/shap>

by varying two parameters: max depth, which can take values of 3, 4, or 5, and `ccp_alpha`, a regularization parameter for cost complexity pruning, which takes values of 0.001, 0.01, and 0.1. For the Bank credit score dataset, which contains categorical columns, we preprocess the data by one-hot encoding the categorical columns.

For the sake of experimental reproducibility, everything required for running the experiments is available online³.

Figure 5.8: Comparative analysis of surrogate models using Task Accuracy, Fidelity Accuracy, ShapGAP (L2 and Cosine distance), and ShapLength for the Breast Cancer dataset. The plot displays the performance of various Decision Trees (DT) and Logistic Regression models. The key findings show that although Logistic Regression has high Task Accuracy and Fidelity Accuracy, its large ShapGAP highlights the potential danger in using it as a global surrogate. Decision Trees with lower Fidelity Accuracy but smaller ShapGAP provide more faithful explanations.

³<https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/ettore.mariotti/shapgap/>

Figure 5.9: Comparison of Task Accuracy, Fidelity Accuracy, ShapGAP (L2 and Cosine), and ShapLength for different surrogate models (Logistic Regression and Decision Trees) on the Bank credit score dataset. Each point represents a surrogate model, with its position determined by the respective metrics. The plot illustrates how Logistic Regression achieves similar Task Accuracy to the black-box model but has higher ShapLength complexity and significantly higher ShapGAP compared to Decision Trees, indicating that its explanations may be less faithful to the black-box model.

5.2.3 Discussion

Our analysis of the results on both the Breast Cancer (Fig. 5.8) and German Credit (Fig. 5.9) datasets reveal some important insights about the relationships between Task Accuracy, Fidelity Accuracy, Complexity, and ShapGAP. In both experiments, Logistic Regression (LR) performs better in terms of both Task Accuracy and Fidelity Accuracy compared to Decision Trees (DT). However, when we consider the ShapGAP metric, the LR model exhibits a very high ShapGAP compared to DT models, indicating that its explanations are unfaithful to the BB model despite its superior accuracy.

In the Breast Cancer dataset, the LR model exhibits both high Task and Fidelity Accuracy, suggesting its potential as an effective global surrogate for the BB model. The additional advantage of lower complexity in the LR model strengthens this proposition. However, the high ShapGAP value warns against this, as it would lead to unfaithful explanations of the BB model.

In the German Credit dataset, it is interesting to observe that the LR model has similar Task Accuracy as the BB model but with higher complexity. One possible reason for this observation is that the simpler structure of the LR model, with its linear decision boundary, allows it to

effectively capture the underlying patterns in the data, but at the expense of using more features on average, as reflected in its higher ShapLength complexity. On the other hand, the more expressive nature of the Random Forest BB model, with its ensemble of DT models, enables it to capture complex relationships among features and potentially represent the patterns in the data with fewer features on average.

Given that a WB model such as the LR model performs almost on par with the BB model in terms of Task Accuracy, readers may wonder whether it is necessary to employ a more complex less interpretable BB model in this case. Indeed, this question was already posed by a few papers, such as [86, 119], which argue that if a WB model performs well on the task, it should be used directly for both prediction and explanation, discarding the BB model. Of course, this choice is also motivated by the nature of the task and its specific requirements. For high-stake scenarios, such as medical diagnosis, it might be more preferable to have slightly lower Task Accuracy but higher explainability, making the use of a WB model more appropriate. For other scenarios, like movie or song recommendations, the trade-off between accuracy and explainability might be less critical, and the choice between WB and BB models may depend on other factors. The decision ultimately depends on the value of having a certain percentage of accuracy improvement and the importance of explainability in the given context.

Overall, ShapGAP reveals that LR models behave in a very different way compared to DT models. While LR models can achieve higher accuracy, in some cases, it might be preferable to use DT models as global surrogates due to their explanations being more faithful to the BB model. This illustrates the value of the ShapGAP metric in guiding the selection of surrogate models based on the faithfulness of their explanations, in addition to their performance on the task.

5.2.3.1 Ethical Considerations in Surrogate Explanations

The ethical implications of unfaithful surrogate explanations in critical applications are manifold. Unfaithful explanations can lead to misinformed decision-making, adversely affecting individuals' lives and well-being, especially in sensitive domains like healthcare, justice and finance [18]. This misalignment can also hinder the identification and correction of AI model shortcomings, exacerbating existing societal inequalities [91].

Accurate and reliable surrogate explanations are vital for ensuring AI systems align properly with ethical principles⁴ guiding AI development. Such explanations enable users to understand and scrutinize model behavior, allowing them to make fully informed choices about the use of AI systems. Informed consent is a fundamental ethical principle that should be upheld in AI development and deployment, as it preserves users' autonomy and agency [46].

⁴<https://altai.insight-centre.org/>

Unfaithful surrogate explanations can erode trust in AI systems, which is essential for the successful adoption of AI technologies [127]. Legal and liability issues can arise due to misaligned explanations, making responsibility attribution for errors or adverse outcomes challenging [150]. Furthermore, unfaithful explanations can mask biases and discrimination, perpetuating societal inequalities.

AI developers have an ethical obligation to provide truthful and accurate explanations. In summary, ShapGAP offers a means to evaluate and compare surrogate models, promoting responsible development and deployment of Trustworthy AI by helping developers in their pursuit of more faithful explanations. Ensuring truthfulness and accuracy in AI explanations is essential for preserving human values, promoting fairness, and fostering transparency and accountability in agreement with ethical guidelines [150].

The contents of this chapter were adapted from the following publications (see further details on their reproduction policy in Chapter 1):

Ettore Mariotti^a, Jose M. Alonso-Moral^a, Albert Gatt^b. *Measuring Model Understandability by means of Shapley Additive Explanations*. In IEEE World Congress on Computational Intelligence, Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE), pages 1-8, IEEE, July 2022. DOI: [10.1109/FUZZ-IEEE55066.2022.9882773](https://doi.org/10.1109/FUZZ-IEEE55066.2022.9882773).

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6 Evaluating the Faithfulness of Post-hoc Feature Attribution Explainers for Neural Networks in Vision and Language

Interpreting neural networks can be challenging. These models can be very large and their inference can be quite costly, both in terms of computational resources and time. To address this, lots of work has been done toward developing feature attribution methods, a class of explainers introduced in Section 3.5. These methods help pinpoint the parts of the input that were most influential in determining the model’s prediction or outcome.

While the wide variety of feature attribution methods offers flexibility, it also creates a dilemma: how do we choose the best one for a given task? Unfortunately, we do not have established benchmarks or universally accepted metrics. The core difficulty lies in the lack of a ground truth for feature attribution – there is no definitive way to say what the “correct” explanation should be.

This chapter addresses this issue by focusing on assessing the *faithfulness* of feature attribution methods. We will explore the concept of faithfulness – the degree to which an explanation accurately reflects the neural network’s internal logic. Unlike plausibility, which focuses on how convincing an explanation seems to humans, faithfulness emphasizes alignment with the model’s behavior, even if counterintuitive. This distinction is crucial, as plausible but incorrect explanations can be misleading and erode trust in AI systems [68].

To assess faithfulness, we draw inspiration from the Focus framework [11]. Unlike many other human-annotated evaluation metrics (which are likely biased toward *plausibility*), Focus design a simple sanity-check where a pseudo ground truth is obtained by construction minimizing human involvement. In the context of image classification, Focus constructs image mosaics incorporating images belonging to both the target class and various non-target classes. A *faithful* explainer, when presented with such a mosaic, should primarily focus its attributions on the images genuinely belonging to the target class. This provides a form of pseudo ground truth for evaluation. Our work initially extends Focus for computer vision. We introduce the use of confusion matrices to provide a more holistic measure of faithfulness for post-hoc feature attribution methods. Next, we carefully adapt this methodology to the natural language processing

(NLP) domain, where unique characteristics like discrete tokens and variable-length inputs require some substantial modifications to the approach.

By exploring these adaptations, we study the impact of hyperparameter choices within attribution methods on their faithfulness. Our overall goal is to empower researchers and practitioners with tools to critically assess explanation methods within both computer vision and natural language domains. This work aims to advance the development of transparent and accountable AI systems through the objective and quantitative evaluation of explainability techniques.

6.1 EVALUATING THE FAITHFULNESS OF IMAGE-BASED METHODS

As hinted before, the wide array of feature attribution methods offers flexibility in explaining image classification models, but choosing the most reliable one for a given task remains challenging. To address this, we extend the Focus framework [11] to assess the faithfulness of these methods. Recall that faithfulness measures how accurately an explanation aligns with the model’s internal decision-making process.

The Focus framework provides a clever way to create a pseudo ground truth. By constructing image mosaics containing images from both target and non-target classes, we can expect a faithful explainer to focus primarily on the target-class images. Importantly, the original Focus paper quantifies faithfulness using precision – how many of the highlighted image regions actually belong to the target class. Our contribution generalizes this concept by introducing the “Attribution Confusion Matrix”. This matrix allows us to calculate a wider range of metrics like accuracy, recall, and F1 score, providing a more comprehensive and nuanced evaluation of feature attribution methods in the image domain.

6.1.1 Mosaic Construction for Faithfulness Evaluation

Our approach reimagines feature attribution scores as a means for classifying input segments as “relevant” or “non-relevant” to the model’s decision. This perspective draws inspiration from the Focus framework [11]. We leverage the insight that within a mosaic – a composite image strategically constructed by combining images from both the target class and various non-target classes (see Figure 6.1) – a faithful explainer should primarily highlight elements belonging to the target class.

6.1.1.1 Building the Attribution Confusion Matrix

We redefine key quantities in classification evaluation for feature attribution. To formalize this, let us first define T as the set of images belonging to the target class within the mosaic, N as the set of images not belonging to the target class, and α_i as the feature attributions. Therefore, for each mosaic, we define:

Figure 6.1: (a) Example of a mosaic made up of images from the Dogs vs. Cats⁴ dataset. On the right, the explanations for the target class *dog* obtained with: (b) LRP (c) LIME (d) GradCAM. Purple areas correspond to positive attributions and orange to negative ones. Notice that GradCAM only provides positive attributions. The model used was a ResNet-18 architecture pre-trained on ImageNet and fine-tuned on the Dogs vs. Cats dataset. ©2023, IEEE.

- True Positive evidence (TP) = $\sum_{i \in T} |\max(0, \alpha_i)|$
- False Positive evidence (FP) = $\sum_{i \in N} |\max(0, \alpha_i)|$
- True Negative evidence (TN) = $\sum_{i \in N} |\min(0, \alpha_i)|$
- False Negative evidence (FN) = $\sum_{i \in T} |\min(0, \alpha_i)|$

6.1.2 Adapting Metrics from Classification

The previous indicators are combined into an Attribution Confusion Matrix, enabling the evaluation of feature attribution performance, akin to the classic confusion matrix in classification tasks. Thanks to this link to the confusion matrix, we can borrow and extend metrics developed for the classification case to evaluate feature attribution. We propose redefining each metric X as Attribute-X. Thus, we can define:

- Attribute-Accuracy = $\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$
- Attribute-Precision = $\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
- Attribute-Recall = $\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
- Attribute-F1 = $\frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP+FP+FN}$

The use of metrics adapted from classification can facilitate the evaluation of feature attribution models in a standardized and interpretable manner. We acknowledge that certain metrics may hold greater relevance in specific scenarios. For instance, in certain medical applications, we could prioritize feature attribution methods which minimize the number of false positives (i.e., high Attribute-Precision) to avoid unnecessary treatments or prioritize attribution

which minimizes false negatives (i.e., high Attribute-Recall) to avoid non-diagnosed pathological cases. This allows practitioners to identify the most suitable option for their particular requirements. It is worth noting that the original *Focus* metric [11] is equivalent to Attribute-Precision, thus inheriting its strengths and weaknesses.

6.1.3 Experiments

To be consistent with the previous *Focus* experiments [11] and for the sake of reproducibility, we use the same models. Specifically, two different architectures: VGG16 [133] and ResNet-18 [65]. The models were fine-tuned on the following datasets: the Dogs vs. Cats¹ dataset (binary problem), the MAMe [102] dataset (29 categories of art mediums and techniques) and the MIT67 [112] dataset (67 indoor scenes). The first two datasets were combined with pre-training on ImageNet [121] and the third one with the Places365-Standard dataset [154]. We evaluate the proposed metrics on each model using 4 feature attribution methods:

1. LIME [115]: based on the Tulio et al implementation². For each explanation, 1000 samples are used, and only the 6 superpixels with the largest attribution in absolute value are considered.
2. LRP [15]: we use the implementation of Nam et al [96]. The different rules used per layer are: the z^B -rule [93] on the first layer, the $LRP - \epsilon$ [15] rule on fully connected layers, and the $LRP - \alpha\beta$ [15] with $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 0$ on convolutional layers.
3. GradCAM [128]: based on the Gildenblat et al implementation³.
4. Integrated Gradients (IG) [143]: the implementation used is from Kokhlikyan et al. [73]. We use 30 steps to approximate the integral and the black image is used as a baseline.

Notice that while LIME, LRP and IG provide both positive and negative relevance, GradCAM only generates positive attributions. These methods were chosen due to their popularity in the research community, and their diverse approaches to explainability.

To assess attribution faithfulness, we carefully construct mosaics for each dataset and target class. For the Dogs vs. Cats dataset, we build 100 mosaics per class (200 total); for MAMe, 100 mosaics per class (2,900 total); and for MIT67, 10 mosaics per class (670 total). Each mosaic is a 448x448 image grid containing two target-class images and two randomly selected non-target-class images. To preserve the model’s training context, images are not resized. It is important to acknowledge that the reliability of attribution methods is directly affected by the accuracy

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/c/dogs-vs-cats/>

²<https://github.com/marcotcr/lime>

³<https://github.com/jacobgil/pytorch-grad-cam>

of the underlying model. A high-performing model (e.g., Dogs vs. Cats model) reinforces the plausibility of the assumption that attributions are genuinely associated with labels.

The source code to reproduce all experiments is available online⁴.

Table 6.1: Mean and standard deviation of the four metrics computed: Attribute-Precision, Attribute-Accuracy, Attribute-Recall and Attribute-F1. Each metric is shown grouped by column and each row shows the results for a combination of a feature attribution method, a specific architecture and a target task. For each model, the metric obtaining the highest mean is highlighted in bold. Note that since GradCAM does not provide negative relevances both $TN = 0$ and $FN = 0$, thus Attribute-Precision and Attribute-Accuracy coincide.

			Attribute-Precision	Attribute-Accuracy	Attribute-Recall	Attribute-F1
Dogs vs. Cats	VGG16 acc: 0.9893	LIME	0.9935 (± 0.0724)	0.9913 (± 0.0435)	0.9863 (± 0.0746)	0.9855 (± 0.0859)
		LRP	0.9526 (± 0.0877)	0.9343 (± 0.0835)	0.9011 (± 0.1707)	0.9141 (± 0.1290)
		IG	0.4973 (± 0.0912)	0.5038 (± 0.0011)	0.5039 (± 0.0015)	0.4963 (± 0.0471)
		GradCAM	0.9446 (± 0.0577)	0.9446 (± 0.0577)	-	-
ResNet-18 acc: 0.9878	LIME	0.9913 (± 0.0739)	0.9853 (± 0.0786)	0.9796 (± 0.1131)	0.9776 (± 0.1154)	
	LRP	0.9741 (± 0.1018)	0.9729 (± 0.1012)	0.9690 (± 0.1142)	0.9707 (± 0.1066)	
	IG	0.4937 (± 0.0802)	0.5018 (± 0.0006)	0.5019 (± 0.0008)	0.4944 (± 0.0419)	
	GradCAM	0.9725 (± 0.0320)	0.9725 (± 0.0320)	-	-	
MAMe	VGG16 acc: 0.8069	LIME	0.7987 (± 0.2603)	0.8048 (± 0.2373)	0.9490 (± 0.1757)	0.8359 (± 0.2333)
		LRP	0.7827 (± 0.2015)	0.7913 (± 0.1967)	0.9103 (± 0.2200)	0.8311 (± 0.2001)
		IG	0.5354 (± 0.1050)	0.5043 (± 0.0023)	0.5065 (± 0.0035)	0.5152 (± 0.0512)
		GradCAM	0.8665 (± 0.1123)	0.8665 (± 0.1123)	-	-
ResNet-19 acc: 0.8220	LIME	0.8020 (± 0.2520)	0.7987 (± 0.2422)	0.9632 (± 0.1508)	0.8443 (± 0.2205)	
	LRP	0.8864 (± 0.1268)	0.8913 (± 0.1237)	0.9866 (± 0.0786)	0.9292 (± 0.0989)	
	IG	0.6076 (± 0.1213)	0.5027 (± 0.0015)	0.5041 (± 0.0024)	0.5452 (± 0.0526)	
	GradCAM	0.8941 (± 0.0938)	0.8941 (± 0.0938)	-	-	
MIT67	VGG16 acc: 0.6948	LIME	0.7800 (± 0.2585)	0.7823 (± 0.2319)	0.9390 (± 0.1823)	0.8218 (± 0.2280)
		LRP	0.6012 (± 0.1918)	0.6132 (± 0.1898)	0.6886 (± 0.2231)	0.6367 (± 0.2022)
		IG	0.5262 (± 0.0809)	0.5076 (± 0.0043)	0.5118 (± 0.0057)	0.5157 (± 0.0401)
		GradCAM	0.8248 (± 0.1076)	0.8248 (± 0.1076)	-	-
ResNet-18 acc: 0.7619	LIME	0.9543 (± 0.1102)	0.9302 (± 0.1347)	0.9611 (± 0.1282)	0.9492 (± 0.1220)	
	LRP	0.9136 (± 0.1434)	0.9169 (± 0.1417)	0.9736 (± 0.1240)	0.9397 (± 0.1307)	
	IG	0.6980 (± 0.0910)	0.5034 (± 0.0017)	0.5042 (± 0.0020)	0.5829 (± 0.0334)	
	GradCAM	0.9302 (± 0.0749)	0.9302 (± 0.0749)	-	-	

6.1.4 Results and discussion

The evaluation results are presented in Table 6.1. A key finding in this experiment is that all considered metrics appear equally impacted by model performance. The differences between metrics for the same attribution method stay consistent across models, regardless of their accuracy on the downstream task (Attribute-Precision and Attribute-Recall, for example). Among methods capable of identifying both positive and negative relevance (LIME, LRP, IG), LIME consistently achieves the highest scores for all measures on the Dogs vs. Cats task (where models exhibit high performance). LRP follows closely, demonstrating comparable Attribute-Precision scores, but lower Attribute-Recall values (indicating more false negatives). IG, on the other

⁴<https://github.com/HPAI-BSC/Attribution-Confusion-Matrix>

hand, produces seemingly random results across all metrics. It's worth noting that IG results can fluctuate based on baseline image choice and the number of steps used. In the MAME results (where models have lower accuracy) LIME demonstrates decreased performance across all metrics compared to its results on the simpler Dogs vs. Cats task. This decline is likely linked to the drop in model performance. Additionally, variance increases in all metrics, particularly Attribute-Precision, suggesting an unreliable amount of false positives. Despite this, both LIME and LRP maintain high mean values in terms of Attribute-Recall.

For the MIT67 task, with the VGG16 model, LIME outperforms LRP across all metrics, demonstrating significantly higher Attribute-Precision, Attribute-Accuracy, Attribute-Recall, and Attribute-F1. In contrast, for the ResNet-18 model, LIME retains higher Attribute-Precision, Attribute-Accuracy (on par with GradCAM) and Attribute-F1, while LRP excels in Attribute-Recall.

A consistent relevant finding across the experiments is the high Attribute-Recall score of LIME and LRP (obtaining a mean greater than 0.9 in all experiments except one). That being said, underperforming models often yield lower precision scores than recall scores, indicating higher reliability of negative relevances with respect to positive relevances. However, in the case of LIME, this feature might be a consequence of the superpixels selection of LIME, since the explanation will only provide negative results, as long as these superpixels have high relevance in absolute value (being among the top 6 most attributed superpixels). This could be important for some case studies, which could motivate their use in contrast with methods which only provide positive relevance.

GradCAM generates only positive relevances, so Table 6.1 displays Attribute-Accuracy and Attribute-Precision, because other metrics would be misleading (*e.g.*, the Attribute-Recall score would be always 1 since the false negatives always are 0 by definition). GradCAM performs well in all tasks, ranking as the top method in half of the experiments, also obtaining a small variance in general. However, in cases where negative relevance is important, GradCAM applicability is limited.

The Attribute-Precision score sometimes encounters numerical problems. This issue arises when all the attributions are negative, leading to a denominator of zero in Attribute-Precision. Consequently, this error propagates to Attribute-F1. Conversely, Attribute-Accuracy only suffers from this issue when all the attributions are zero. This is reasonable, as the accuracy of an all-zero explanation remains ambiguous.

The proposed approach enables a comprehensive comparison of existing methods and can serve as a tool for developing and testing new methods in the Computer Vision (CV) field. Our framework has broader implications for the validation of tools in specific use cases where the relevance of false negatives and false positives is distinct (*e.g.*, systems that provide support in analyzing images in medical domains). This is directly applicable to assessing explainers

on transformer-based models on vision tasks and also other domains like NLP, e.g., sentiment analysis.

6.2 EVALUATING THE FAITHFULNESS OF METHODS FOR EXPLAINING NLP MODELS AND TASKS

Adapting the Focus framework and its associated Attribution Confusion Matrix to the domain of NLP presents unique challenges. However, doing so offers an efficient, reproducible, and cost-effective way to assess the faithfulness of XAI explanations in this domain.

Our focus is on evaluating how closely explanations generated by feature attribution methods in NLP match known input elements that drive specific classifications. We also delve into the impact of hyperparameter choices on the faithfulness of these methods. This framework empowers researchers and practitioners to both optimize hyperparameters and rigorously assess the faithfulness of XAI techniques, advancing the development of transparent and trustworthy AI systems. The key contributions of this work are:

1. **Automatic Faithfulness Assessment for NLP:** We present a novel method for automatically evaluating the faithfulness of XAI methods specifically tailored to NLP tasks.
2. **Comprehensive Benchmark:** We provide a comprehensive benchmark of six Explainable AI (XAI) methods, including different variants where applicable, across three distinct sentence classification tasks.

6.2.1 Related work

Despite the common use of deep learning models in both the CV and Natural Language Processing (NLP) fields, the techniques for evaluating the faithfulness and reliability of XAI methods differ. In the rest of this chapter, we focus specifically on approaches for assessing the faithfulness of explanations generated by XAI methods in NLP.

Let us first categorize the evaluation methods into two types: categorical and numerical evaluations. Categorical evaluations involve axioms that explainability methods must fulfil (e.g., Completeness or Implementation Invariance Sensitivity [142]). Numerical evaluations enable instead the ranking of Feature Attribution methods according to a given desirable property. Randomization tests, for example, measure the difference between the explanation obtained with a randomized and non-randomized model [1], or the difference between the explanation of the correct class and the explanation for a random class [135].

Some other methods try to measure the faithfulness of an XAI method to the model's behaviour, by perturbing the input according to their explanation and then examining output variations [8, 15, 22, 117]. While in CV such perturbations often take the form of pixel manipulations,

Figure 6.2: Example of the structure of two *text mosaics*. The first row corresponds to a mosaic of length two, that is, composed of two sentences. The second row corresponds to a mosaic of length four. In both cases, the sentences of the target class are highlighted in yellow.

similar methods are used in NLP by manipulating (*e.g.*, replacing, deleting or zeroing the embeddings of) tokens [76, 111]. However, these modifications quickly generate instances that are mostly outside of the original data distribution. In some cases, they result in infelicitous strings (*e.g.*, a sentence without a verb).

In order to avoid the Out-of-Distribution (OOD) problem, Kim et al. [70] propose a variation, where instead of deleting the tokens corresponding to OOD words or zeroing their embeddings, they are sampled from a distribution inferred by a Masked Language Model, *e.g.*, BERT [40]. However, since these models only expect a part of the input to be masked, the re-sampling is performed on up to 20% of the total number of tokens.

Rather than changing the original instances in the dataset, Zhang et al [153] proposed, in the CV domain, a “Pointing game” where a human labeler identifies a specific region of the image and measures how much the explanation matches the annotation. This technique was later adapted to the NLP domain [109]. While this technique overcomes the lack of ground truth, this assumption may not always align with the model’s prediction process. Consequently, this approach is more suited for evaluating plausibility (*i.e.*, how much it resonates with human intuition) rather than the faithfulness of the explanation (*i.e.*, how much it is true to the actual computation). Indeed, it has been shown that models can rely on patterns or artifacts in the data that humans could miss. For example Ribeiro et al. [114] noted that an image classifier trained on distinguishing husky vs wolf was not focusing on the region corresponding to the animal, but rather on the snow present in the background of the picture. In this case a pointing game would have assigned a very low score to a faithful explainer (*i.e.*, one that would point to the snow as an evidence). In order to overcome this limitation, the approach by Arias-Duart et al. [11] relaxed the assumption of the pointing game with a construction that by design excluded the human involvement in the ‘pointing’ definition. To do this, they created an *image mosaic* (see illustrative example in Figure 6.1): a composite grid of images where half belong to a target class and the other half to various other classes. These images are randomly selected, ensuring a diverse representation, yet they are not resized. The primary assumption is that when such a mosaic contains images from both target and non-target classes, the model’s positive attributions – meaning the degree to which the model attributes parts of the image to the target class – should predominantly appear on the images that actually belong to the target class. This is a more relaxed assumption of the pointing game, as it is not stating precisely a ‘segmentation

mask’ of the ideal explanation, it is just stating that the evidence should fall on the specific parts of the mosaics (which we know by construction, rather than by human annotation). By constructing this ground truth, the faithfulness of Feature Attribution methods can be measured by analyzing the attributions’ location. In this paper, we draw inspiration from this work and propose a novel metric to assess the faithfulness of the Feature Attribution methods for NLP. We call it *TextFocus* score.

6.2.2 Methodology

In this section we introduce *TextFocus*: we explain how we build the *textual mosaics* (Section 6.2.2.1) and how the *TextFocus* score is computed (§6.2.2.2).

6.2.2.1 Textual mosaics

We focus on text classification tasks. Thus, we have a list of sentences, with each one having a single label (*e.g.*, negative or positive, offensive or non-offensive). Using a subset of these sentences, we build what we call *textual mosaics*.

A *textual mosaic* is a string composed of N sentences, with half belonging to the target class A , and the other half to other classes. The target class is the one that the Feature Attribution method is requested to explain. For each mosaic, we first randomly sample $N/2$ sentences from the target class, then randomly select $N/2$ sentences from the other classes. The sentences in the textual mosaic are then arranged in random order. Each sentence is separated by a [SEP] token, with the mosaic beginning with a [CLS] token and ending with a [SEP] token. We chose to use this construction to align with the input expected by many widely-used pretrained language models. Figure 6.2 illustrates two examples of *text mosaic* configurations; in the first row, one sentence corresponds to the target class (sentence 1) and the other to a non-target class (sentence 2). The second row shows a *text mosaic* of length four, with two sentences of the target class (sentences 1 and 4) and two of a non-target class (sentences 2 and 3).

An actual example of a mosaic of size $N = 4$, from a sentiment analysis task, is shown in Figure 6.3. The two target class sentences are highlighted in yellow (see the top part of the picture). Each token is displayed in order from top to bottom and each sentence is separated from the next by a dashed line. Bars are used to represent token attributions: positive attributions (which favour the target class) are on the right side, while negative attributions (which go against the target class) are on the left. Finally, each token is also assigned a distinct colour, indicating the sentence to which it belongs.

The construction of the textual mosaic gives us the possibility of making the following **key assumptions**, which this work builds upon:

Figure 6.3: Attributions for a textual mosaic of size 4, with sentences in the target class highlighted in yellow. Sentences are divided by a dashed line, and attributions are color-coded by sentence. Attributions on the right favour the target class (in this case the negative class) and attributions on the left go against the target class.

- Evidence for the target class should lie somewhere in the target class sentences, but not on the others.
- Evidence against the target class should be found in sentences not belonging to the target class.

When constructing the mosaics, we deliberately use validation data for which the model’s prediction aligns with the true label. By doing so, we can be more confident that the model has indeed detected some form of ‘evidence’ supporting its classification. This focused approach serves to minimize confounding factors, thereby enabling a more accurate evaluation of the capabilities of XAI methods to identify and localise this ‘evidence’.

This is done with the intention of having a more clean measurement of faithfulness, in virtue of dropping those data points where the model gets confused and might find evidence for other classes. This behaviour would jeopardise our measurement of faithfulness, as the evidence the model finds might be not related to the label provided by the dataset. We performed a sanity check to gauge the impact and soundness of this choice in Section [6.2.4.5](#).

6.2.2.2 A quantitative metric: TextFocus

Given the aforementioned construction, we need a quantitative metric to measure how accurately an XAI method is able to correctly assign positive attributions to features of a sample of the target class, and negative attributions to features of samples in the non-target classes.

One key distinction between *textual mosaics* and *image mosaics* is that the former has a variable number of tokens, unlike the latter, which typically has a fixed number of pixels. To prevent the TextFocus metric from being affected by sentence length, we normalize the amount of attribution for each sentence beforehand. In addition, when computing *textual mosaics*, we disregard the effect of special tokens such as [SEP] and [CLS], because they are structural placeholders in the mosaic.

More formally, let S_i be the set of tokens in sentence i of the mosaic, with j being the token index not including special tokens. $\alpha_{i,j}$ is the attribution of token j in sentence i according to some XAI method. We define M as the set of sentences of the whole mosaic, with $C \subset M$ the set of sentences belonging to the target class.

In Section 6.1, we introduced a principled way of identifying True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), True Negatives (TN), and False Negatives (FN) from mosaic constructions [10]. This allows us to adapt metrics from the classification literature to the evaluation of Feature Attribution methods.

More formally:

$$TP := \sum_{i \in C} \frac{\sum_j \max(0, \alpha_{i,j})}{\|S_i\|} \quad (6.1)$$

$$FP := \sum_{i \in M \setminus C} \frac{\sum_j \max(0, \alpha_{i,j})}{\|S_i\|} \quad (6.2)$$

$$TN := \sum_{i \in M \setminus C} \frac{\sum_j \min(0, \alpha_{i,j})}{\|S_i\|} \quad (6.3)$$

$$FN := \sum_{i \in C} \frac{\sum_j \min(0, \alpha_{i,j})}{\|S_i\|} \quad (6.4)$$

The *TextFocus* score can then be computed as:

$$\text{TextFocus}(M) := \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (6.5)$$

This way, *TextFocus* gives us a measure of the overall accuracy of an XAI attribution method in NLP by calculating the proportion of the correctly attributed importance, considering both target and non-target class sentences, in relation to the total attributions of the entire mosaic.

This allows us to assess the *faithfulness* of different attribution methods, to compare their performance, and to evaluate the impact of different hyperparameter choices.

6.2.3 Experiments

To test *TextFocus* we assessed six different Feature Attribution methods (see Section 6.2.3.1). To evaluate them, one needs a trained model to be explained and a set of mosaics to compute the *TextFocus* (see Section 6.2.3.2).

6.2.3.1 Feature attribution explanation techniques

We implemented the six evaluated methods using Captum.⁵ Some of them require computing the gradients with respect to the input. However, since NLP models take discrete, non-differentiable tokens as input, instead of computing the gradients with respect to the input, we compute the gradients with respect to the token embeddings. The evaluated methods are the following:

- **Gradient:** This method uses the gradients of the inputs computed with respect to the target class, as Feature Attribution map. The technique was first used to explain predictions in CV by [132]. We aggregate attributions on a token embedding using the mean, allowing for both positive and negative attributions, in contrast to the L2 or L1 norms employed in other contexts [13, 75].
- **Gradient X Activation:** This method consists in multiplying the result of the gradient by the input activation [39].
- **Integrated Gradients (IG):** This method computes the integral of gradients along the straight line joining a baseline x' and the input x in the input space [142]. The approximation of the integral is made by summing up all the steps from the baseline x' to input x . This technique is based on Aumann-Shapley values, a game-theoretic approach to cost-sharing found in the economics literature [14].
- **DeepLIFT:** [130] assigns relevance with respect to a baseline by backpropagating a relevance score via the Rescale Rule. We use the gradient formulation proposed by [9].
- **Gradient SHAP:** This method adds Gaussian noise to each input sample multiple times and each time selects a random point along the path between the baseline and the input. It computes the gradient of outputs with respect to those selected points, and the final SHAP values represent the expected value of the gradients multiplied by the difference between the inputs and baselines. SHAP values are approximated under the assumption that input features are independent and that the explanation model is linear between the inputs and the given baselines. However, these assumptions can be challenged when this method is

⁵<https://captum.ai/>

applied to language tokens. The implementation adopted here is inspired by the work of [83] and follows the implementation of the SHAP package.⁶

- **LIME** [115]: This method produces Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations. To do so, it generates perturbed instances of the original dataset by deleting random tokens from the instance to be explained. These new instances and their predictions are used to train a linear model which approximates locally the original model. Importantly in fitting the linear model each sample is weighted proportionally to the similarity to the original instance computed by the model’s embedding cosine similarity. The coefficients of the linear model comprise the final attribution scores.

Some of these methods (i.e., IG, DeepLIFT, and Gradient SHAP) fulfill the Sum-to-Zero property (also called *Completeness* in [142] and [9]), which states that the attributions of the method α_j have to sum up to the difference between the value of the function f of the input x and the *baseline*, namely:

$$f(x) - f(\text{baseline}) = \sum_j \alpha_j \quad (6.6)$$

This property can be used to assess a necessary condition for the convergence of the method, i.e., computing the absolute convergence error δ as follows:

$$\delta := (f[\text{input}] - f[\text{baseline}]) - \sum_j \alpha_j \quad (6.7)$$

And then the relative percentage error is:

$$\text{ErrorPerc} := \frac{\delta}{(f[\text{input}] - f[\text{baseline}])} * 100 \quad (6.8)$$

Accordingly, to ensure accuracy and fair comparison between methods, we iteratively increase the number of steps/samples until the *ErrorPerc* is under a fixed threshold (in our experiment 1%). It is important to note that a small δ does not guarantee a correct solution; it is a necessary, yet not sufficient, condition to be met.

In addition, it is worth noting that some of these methods require baselines for their computation. Ideally, the baseline should represent a reference input whose “signal” is absent, so that it can be compared to the input being analysed. While in CV those baselines are usually black images (where all the pixel values set to 0), in NLP a zero input embedding is meaningless. Therefore, in this domain, different types of special tokens (i.e., [PAD], [MASK], [UNK], [SEP] or [CLS]) can be used as baselines.

Since the choice of the baseline can affect the output and performance of the Feature Attribution method [20], we will evaluate the performance of each method according to the considered baselines. Notice that we will delve deeper into this issue later in Section 6.2.5.1.

⁶<https://github.com/shap/shap>

6.2.3.2 Datasets and models

In the experiments, we will concentrate on the task of text classification. We will use three models based on DistilBERT [123]. Each model is fine-tuned for the following datasets:

- **SST-2** is a binary sentiment classification dataset containing parts of movie reviews (with a mean length of about 20 tokens) excerpted from `rottentomatoes.com` and labelled on Amazon Mechanical Turk [137]. The Stanford Sentiment (SST-2) dataset is composed of 11,855 sentences labeled as positive or negative.
- **IMDB** [84] is also a binary sentiment classification dataset of highly popular movie reviews collected from `imdb.com`. The dataset consists of a total of 50k sentences, half of which are for training and half for testing. The length of the Internet Movie Database (IMDB) sentences is much greater than the SST-2 sentences (mean length of about 300 tokens).
- **Emotion** [124] is a multi-class classification dataset of 20k English tweets scraped from Twitter and labeled with six basic emotions: anger, fear, joy, love, sadness and surprise.

DistilBERT models fine-tuned for each task are found in the official repository of HuggingFace [7, 8, 9]. The SST-2 model reaches an accuracy of 98.9% on the test set, while the IMDB model reaches an accuracy of 92.8%. On Emotion, the model has an accuracy of 92.5%.

For the SST-2 and Emotion datasets we use mosaics with $N = 4$, similar to [11], since larger sizes would result in higher computational complexity and memory demands. However, for the IMDB mosaics, we use $N = 2$. This is due to the input size limitation of DistilBERT, which is of 512 tokens. In order to prevent truncating the sentence (and thus potentially losing information), when constructing *textual mosaics* from IMDB we select sentences with lengths of less than 256 tokens.

6.2.4 Sanity checks

In order to assess the overall robustness of the mosaic design we performed several sanity checks.

6.2.4.1 Randomisation test

We perform the first experiment with *TextFocus* to analyze its behaviour when applied to a random model. With a randomly initialised model, we expect an XAI method to compute token attributions which are unrelated to the labels, since the model has not been trained to make

⁷<https://huggingface.co/distilbert-base-uncased-finetuned-sst-2-english>

⁸<https://huggingface.co/lvwerra/distilbert-imdb>

⁹<https://huggingface.co/sabre-code/distilbert-base-uncased-finetuned-emotion>

Figure 6.4: Histogram of *TextFocus* scores obtained with Integrated Gradients (IG) using a trained model (blue) and a randomized model (orange) on 2k textual mosaics on SST-2.

associations between input tokens and output labels. So, we would expect attributions from the random model to be distributed randomly.

We computed the *TextFocus* distribution on 2k text mosaics from SST-2 with the Integrated Gradients (IG) method and an [UNK] token as a baseline. Figure 6.4 shows the evaluation of two models: randomized (orange) and non-randomized (blue). The latter corresponds to the fine-tuned DistilBERT model which was introduced in section 6.2.3.2.

The random model produces a normal distribution centered around 0.51. The results suggest that, as expected, the model relies on patterns that are not localised according to the data labels. On the other hand, the average *TextFocus* score of the trained model is 0.91, which indicates that the Feature Attribution method is able to successfully assign the majority of attributions to the correct tokens within mosaic sentences.

6.2.4.2 Assessment of the impact of mosaic structure

One natural question that arises in the construction of textual mosaics is whether the way we build these mosaics influences the explanation of the model classifications, particularly when compared to analyzing the sentences individually. We explored this using mosaics of length n , made by repeating the same sentence n times.

We study the order of the tokens in the mosaic as a possible confounding factor. In particular, if the position k of the token in the sentence j , affects its feature attribution a_{jk} , then we should observe a different attribution $a_{j'k}$ for the same token in a different position.

To validate this, we compute the Sentence Attribution Stability (SAS) and rank each token within a mosaic sentence by its attribution. Comparisons are made using Rank Biased Overlap

Figure 6.5: Distribution of SAS scores across mosaic sizes and separator tokens. Higher scores indicate better attribution stability. The consistently high average underscores the robustness of our methodology, irrespective of mosaic design choices.

Figure 6.6: *TextFocus* distribution for the three methods requiring baselines (*i.e.*, Gradient SHAP, IG and DeepLIFT). Each method is depicted with a box-plot of a different colour. On the x-axis the different special tokens used as baselines. In (a) results for the SST-2, in (b) for the IMDB case and in (c) for the Emotion dataset.

(RBO), akin to the approach in [125]. For more details about SAS definition and implementation, we refer the reader to Algorithm 3. The intuition behind SAS is that if order in the text mosaic matters, then token attributions of each sub-mosaic component should vary enough to change their relative ranking (which can be measured in terms of RBO), even though each sub-mosaic component content is identical (only the position in the mosaic changes).

We perform this experiment using 1,000 SST-2 sentences, DistilBERT and Integrated Gradients with an [UNK] baseline. As illustrated in Figure 6.5, the sanity check is supported by the notably high distribution of SAS scores (around 0.9) that remains consistent across different mosaic sizes. The reduced variance with increasing mosaic size is likely attributable to the increased stability from more pairwise comparisons. Intriguingly, the mosaic structure remains

robust irrespective of the mosaic separator token chosen, though there is a higher score for the [SEP] token.

Algorithm 3 Sentence Attribution Stability (SAS)

```

1: function ComputeSAS(sentences, attributions)
2:   Initialize an empty list: sorted_sentences = []
3:   Initialize an empty list: distances = []
4:   for each (sentence, attribution) in (sentences, attributions) do
5:     Replace tokens in the sentence with unique numeric identifiers
6:     Create tuples (numeric_token, attribution)
7:     Sort tuples by attribution in descending order
8:     Append sorted numeric tokens to sorted_sentences
9:   end for
10:  Define Pairs as all unique combinations of indices (i, j) for sorted_sentences
11:  for each unique pair (i, j) in Pairs do
12:    rbo = RBO(sorted_sentences[i], sorted_sentences[j])
13:    Append rbo to distances
14:  end for
15:   $SAS = \frac{1}{\binom{n}{2}} \times \sum \text{distances}$ 
16:  return SAS
17: end function

```

6.2.4.3 Variance of TextFocus

In Figure 6.9, we observed that some methods that behave in a random-like manner (e.g., DeepLIFT, Gradient SHAP, Gradient X Activation, and Gradient L2) exhibit smaller variance on the IMDB dataset compared to the Emotion or SST-2 datasets. We speculated that this might be due to the longer sentence lengths in the IMDB dataset. To investigate this further, we generated artificial mosaics with $N = 4$, where the length of each sentence is modeled using a Poisson distribution with mean λ . Assuming that the attributions from a random model follow a normal distribution centered at 0, we computed *TextFocus* for these synthetic attributions. After calculating *TextFocus* for these artificial attributions, we observed that the final *TextFocus* definition followed a Normal-like distribution centered at 0.5, with a standard deviation inversely proportional to λ (see Figure 6.7). Thus, we can conclude that longer sentence lengths lead to reduced variance.

6.2.4.4 Convergence Errors and Execution Time

Some methods in the experiments (Integrated Gradients, Gradient SHAP and DeepLIFT) fulfill the Sum-to-Zero property (also called *Completeness* [9, 142]), which states that the attributions of the method α_j have to sum up to the difference between the value of the function f of the input x and the *baseline*, namely:

Figure 6.7: Standard Deviation of *TextFocus* scores over 1000 synthetic mosaics, as a function of λ (the average sentence length).

$$f(x) - f(\text{baseline}) = \sum_j \alpha_j \quad (6.9)$$

This property can be used to assess a necessary condition for the convergence of the method: computing the absolute convergence error as follows.

$$\delta := (f[\text{input}] - f[\text{baseline}]) - \sum_j \alpha_j \quad (6.10)$$

And the relative percentage error.

$$\text{ErrorPerc} := \frac{\delta}{(f[\text{input}] - f[\text{baseline}])} * 100 \quad (6.11)$$

To ensure the accuracy of each method and fair comparison between methods, we iteratively increase the number of steps/samples until the percentage error is under a fixed threshold (in the experiment 1%). It is important to note that a small δ does not guarantee a correct solution; it is a necessary, yet not sufficient, condition to be met.

6.2.4.5 Correct labels vs wrong labels

In the construction of the textual mosaic we select those datapoints whose prediction agrees with the provided label. This is done with the intention of having a more clean measurement of faithfulness, in virtue of dropping those data points where the model gets confused and might find evidence for other classes. This behaviour would jeopardise the measurement of faithfulness, as the evidence the model finds might be not related to the label provided by the dataset. In order to check what is the effect of this step we set up a simple experiment on the Emotion dataset (the multiclass one) where we do the opposite: we evaluate *TextFocus* on those validation points whose prediction is different from the dataset label (See Fig. 6.8).

Interestingly the scores are still significantly high, indicating that there is some correct evidence found by the XAI methods in the mistaken predictions. More importantly, we can see that the distribution of *TextFocus* on the correct sentences (i.e., where the model agrees with the

Figure 6.8: The impact of evaluating *TextFocus* on the data predicted correctly vs incorrectly. On the datapoints where the model agrees with the label we have a more clean measurement of *TextFocus*. Data extracted from analysing 1600 mosaics on the Emotion dataset.

dataset label) is higher than the distribution of *TextFocus* on the wrong sentences (i.e., where the model disagrees with the dataset label). The variance on the correct labels is also smaller, indicating a more precise measurement.

6.2.5 Discussion

In this section, we discuss the results obtained from the evaluation of the different explainability methods. First, we study the role of the choice of baselines on the methods’ performance (Section 6.2.5.1). Second, we use *TextFocus* to assess the Feature Attribution methods, shedding light on the most faithful XAI methods and discussing the trade-off between the performance and execution time (Section 6.2.5.2). We share the code to replicate these experiments.¹⁰

6.2.5.1 The impact of the baseline choice

In this experiment, we analyzed the effect on the performance of the Feature Attribution methods, depending on the tokens chosen to construct baselines. To conduct this evaluation, we use the three explainability methods requiring baselines (i.e., Gradient SHAP, DeepLIFT and IG). A good baseline should represent the absence of a signal. BERT-like models [40] provide a natural choice for a baseline using special tokens such as [MASK], [PAD], or [UNK]. For the sake of completeness, we also tried [CLS] and [SEP]. Figure 6.6 shows the results of this experiment for each dataset: (a) SST-2, (b) IMDB, and (c) Emotion. Each colour corresponds to a different Feature Attribution method.

¹⁰<https://gitlab.nl4xai.eu/ettore.mariotti/TextFocus>

Figure 6.9: *TextFocus* score distributions for the six methods benchmarked, obtained from the evaluations of 1202 mosaics on Emotion (left side), 1746 mosaics on SST-2 (center) and 7014 mosaics on IMDB (right side). The baselines used for the methods requiring them are specified in square brackets. The similarity between the results (e.g., the rank is preserved) additionally suggests that choosing $N = 2$ or $N = 4$ does not significantly impact the results.

Interestingly, IG performs quite well across all the baselines. However, one can observe a higher mean and smaller standard deviation of the scores for the [UNK] token.

On the other hand, the results of the study suggest that both DeepLIFT and GradientShap often exhibit behaviour that appears random, making it difficult to identify a baseline that performs better than the others. For the next experiments, we have chosen to use the [MASK] token as the baseline for both DeepLIFT and GradientShap, as they yielded the highest scores on average.

6.2.5.2 Benchmarking feature attribution methods

We benchmark the six Feature Attribution methods introduced in Section 6.2.3.1: Gradient L2, GradientXActivation, IG, DeepLIFT, Gradient SHAP and Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME). For each method requiring a baseline, we pick the special token obtaining the best results on average in Section 6.2.5.1, that is, the [UNK] token for IG, [MASK] for Gradient SHAP and DeepLIFT. We run this evaluation on the DistilBERT models introduced in Section 6.2.3.2. For each mosaic, we compute *TextFocus* for all target classes. We analyze a total of 1,746 mosaics of size $N = 4$ for the SST-2 dataset, 1,202 mosaics of size $N = 4$ for the Emotion dataset and 7,014 mosaics of size $N = 2$ for the IMDB dataset (see Section 6.2.3.2 for further details). The *TextFocus* results¹¹ are shown in Figure 6.9.

IG, using the [UNK] token as a baseline, gets consistently good results in all the experiments: obtaining a high mean *TextFocus* of 0.918 in the SST-2 case, a mean *TextFocus* of 0.830 in the IMDB dataset, and a mean of 0.943 in the Emotion dataset. The second best method is LIME, getting a mean *TextFocus* 0.902 in the SST-2 dataset, 0.852 in the IMDB dataset, and 0.845 in the Emotion dataset. On the other hand, GradientShap, DeepLift, GradientXActivation and Gradient obtained scores that are very similar to chance behaviour, with a mean accuracy around 0.5

¹¹The experiments were run on a A100 Nvidia GPU.

in all the configurations in which we tested them. Therefore, according to the results, IG and LIME are methods able to assign more than 50% of the attribution to the correct sentences of the mosaic. According to these experiments, the *TextFocus* results are consistent across all datasets. It is worth noting that LIME’s reliance on random token sampling and lasso regularization often leads to repeatability issues. When applying LIME with the same model and the same input data in different runs, inconsistent attributions are common. This inconsistency arises because computational constraints limit the random sampling, and lasso regularization can cause different tokens to be deemed important in different runs, minimizing the importance of others.

6.2.6 Conclusions and future work

We introduced and tested a new score to assess the faithfulness and reliability of Feature Attribution methods in NLP. Of the six XAI methods evaluated with *TextFocus*, Gradient, GradientSHAP, DeepLIFT and GradientXActivation show a behaviour close to random.

IG with [UNK] baseline is the method achieving the best performance according to *TextFocus*. LIME also provides reliable explanations. Yet an inherent characteristic of the LIME method that should be taken into account is that despite obtaining reliable explanations, it is not deterministic. That is, depending on the tokens that are removed during the computation, the explanation may be slightly different. This feature may not be a disadvantage for some applications, but could be undesirable for others (*e.g.*, applications requiring high reproducibility).

As future work, we plan to extend *TextFocus* to encoder-decoder and decoder-only generative models. We also believe that our findings could be extrapolated to more complex challenges such as Language Generation and Question & Answering.

6.2.7 Limitations

The faithfulness scores following this evaluation framework may be affected by two main factors: *shared evidence* when a non-target-class label in the same mosaic contains evidence of the target class (imagine a movie review that is overall positive but critical in some parts), and *missing evidence* when no evidence of the target class is found in the sub-mosaics labelled with it (for example mislabeled sentences). These issues may stem from the inherent properties of data (*e.g.*, spurious correlations).

While this may cause inconveniences when using *TextFocus* to measure the Feature Attribution methods faithfulness, it can be an effective method for understanding how and why a model is confused. Similarly to how mosaics together with the *Focus* can uncover bias in vision models [12], future work could also use textual mosaics and *TextFocus* to discover unknown biases in NLP tasks.

We also performed an experiment to analyze whether the interaction between sentences of different classes within a mosaic affects the Feature Attributions, which may lead us to misleading conclusions. We swap the order of sentences within a mosaic without observing significant changes in the result. Even so, to mitigate this possible artifact, for every mosaic we randomize the position of the target class sentences.

The contents of this chapter were adapted from the following publications (see further details on their reproduction policy in Chapter 1):

Anna Arias-Duart^a, Ettore Mariotti^b, Dario Garcia-Gasulla^{6.2.7}, Jose Maria Alonso-Moral^b. *A Confusion Matrix for Evaluating Feature Attribution Methods*. In Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Workshop: Explainable AI for Computer Vision (XAI4CV), pages 3708-3713, 2023. DOI: [10.1109/CVPRW59228.2023.00380](https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPRW59228.2023.00380).

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^bCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

Ettore Mariotti^b, Anna Arias-Duart^b, Michele Cafagna^c, Albert Gatt^d, Dario Garcia Gasulla^b, Jose Maria Alonso Moral^b. *TextFocus: Assessing the Faithfulness of Feature Attribution Methods in Natural Language Processing*. Submitted and under review for IEEE Access, 2024.

^aCentro Singular de Investigación en Tecnoloxías Intelixentes (CiTIUS), Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.

^bBarcelona Supercomputing Center.

^cUniversity of Malta.

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7 Use cases of XAI in industry

In today's intricate and highly competitive business landscape, relying solely on human intuition for decision-making is no longer sufficient. Organizations have turned to machine learning algorithms to sift through the large amounts of data they collect in the hopes of making more informed decisions. Organizations are increasingly turning to machine learning algorithms, not just for decision-making, but for a multitude of applications such as demand prediction, task automation, and optimization, due to their powerful capabilities in pattern recognition and predictive analytics. These algorithms sift through the large amounts of data collected, aiming to drive more informed and precise decisions. However, their "black-box" nature presents a significant limitation. This lack of transparency and interpretability can erode user trust and complicates critical functions like risk management and regulatory compliance, as discussed in Chapter 2.

XAI is transforming the business landscape by offering more than just predictions—it provides understanding. Beyond helping end-users make better decisions, it facilitates critical organizational processes, from auditing machine-made decisions to optimizing operations based on understandable metrics. As businesses confront increasingly complex challenges, from supply chain inefficiencies to customer engagement, the need for AI that can be scrutinized, tested, and trusted has never been greater. Trust is particularly crucial in industries where mistakes could lead to significant financial or reputational losses.

In this context, this chapter explores the application of XAI in real-world settings, informed by a three-month secondment with INDITEX, a leader company in the textile industry. Challenges in three use cases were considered: the restocking problem, the sales prediction problem and demand scenarios for pricing optimization. These case studies serve as tangible illustrations of how XAI can be effectively integrated into business processes, complementing the foundational theories and methodologies laid out in Chapters 3 and 5.

7.1 USE CASE A: RESTOCKING

Restocking inventory in retail involves a complex set of decisions that balance supply chain logistics, store capacity, and customer demand. Traditionally, the decision to restock specific

products has been made by experts who consider a multitude of factors. However, given the volume of data available, the use of machine learning models can enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of these decisions. Specifically, we explored the application of machine learning models in deciding whether or not to restock a particular product. This is an integral part of inventory management, impacting both sales opportunities and resource utilization.

The ideal solution would be the adoption of XAI techniques. The advantage of XAI over “black-box” models in this case is twofold. First, an explainable model directs the attention of the human operators to specific patterns or data points they might have otherwise overlooked. Second, it educates the operators about rare patterns that may not be intuitively obvious.

Conversely, the explanations also serve as a form of quality control. Experts can analyze the reasoning behind the model’s suggestions and, if they find them to be inappropriate or illogical, choose not to trust the prediction. This adds an additional layer of trust and interpretability that is crucial for effective decision-making.

Upon evaluating various models, we discovered that both Explainable Boosting Machines (EBM) and its second-order variant, EB2M, delivered comparable predictive accuracy and ROC AUC metrics as the more opaque Random Forest algorithms (see Table 7.1). Additionally, Logistic Regression and Decision Trees were assessed, with the former demonstrating slightly lower accuracy than the latter but both not matching the Random Forest’s performance. According to the guidelines presented in Chapter 3, when interpretable models achieve comparable performance to more complex models, it is advisable to choose the simplest and most accurate interpretable option. So, we went with Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) using the EBM version. EB2M does consider more complex interactions, but since EBM gives the same results and is simpler, we settled for EBM. It is both effective and easier to interpret.

Table 7.1: Performances of different models evaluated on Use Case A with 10-fold cross validation.

Model	Accuracy	ROC AUC
Random Forest	0.98	1.00
Logistic Regression	0.92	0.98
Decision Tree	0.96	0.96
Dummy	0.59	0.50
EB2M	0.97	1.00
EBM	0.97	1.00

7.1.1 Using GAMs for White-Box Modeling

As previously discussed, we have chosen to model our task using GAMs, specifically implemented as EBMs. A comprehensive global explanation of this model is illustrated in Figure 7.1, where each shape function, denoted as f_i , represents the contribution of individual features.

Importantly, each shape function directly indicates how a single feature influences the final log-odds. A value above zero in these functions suggests evidence favoring the outcome of interest, such as restocking in our case, while a value below zero indicates evidence against it. This global perspective allows us to assess the overall behavior of the model by observing how each feature contributes. Intriguingly, we notice that certain features demonstrate roughly linear relationships, while others exhibit saturating non-linear trends. Moreover, occasional spikes in these functions warrant attention; they can be indicative of preprocessing steps like imputation of missing values, a common practice.

The visualization of these shape functions is useful beyond technical model assessment. It enables developers to identify potential issues or anomalies in the model, thereby facilitating a more robust and reliable modeling process. For the final users of the model and domain experts, this form of visualization is particularly valuable. It offers an intuitive understanding of how the model arrives at its predictions, and offer a way of assessing whether the mathematical model align with their mental model of the task. This alignment is crucial, as it enhances trust in the model's functionality and ensures that the model's decision-making process reflects a realistic and logical approach to the problem at hand. It is additionally interesting to have such transparency in order to monitor changes in discovered patterns as more data is available. These models are trained on and use all the data available to a certain point, and white-box modeling (or XAI more in general) can be a useful tool for tracking changes in patterns of data that get reflected in the model. By providing a clear, visual representation of each feature's influence, the EBM framework not only demystifies the model's internal workings but also fosters a collaborative environment where developers and stakeholders can jointly ensure the model's efficacy and reliability.

7.1.1.1 A Local Explanation

In this section, we will delve into an illustrative example of a local explanation, which exemplifies the practical analysis stakeholders might undertake when examining individual predictions made by our model.

The figure at hand, which can be referenced in Figure [7.2](#), breaks down the predictive decision for a particular data point. The model's prediction is influenced by various features, whose effects are represented in two colors: orange for positive contributions towards the prediction of restocking, and blue for negative contributions (thus evidence the model found that dissuaded to restock). The magnitude of these contributions gives us insight into how significantly each feature sways the prediction.

For the data point in question, the probability of the predicted class being 1 (do restock) is quite high at 0.908. Recalling that a GAM is a model of the form

$$GAM(x_1, \dots, x_p) = \text{intercept} + f_1(x_1) + \dots + f_p(x_p)$$

Figure 7.1: Global perspective of the model detailing each feature’s transformation to its contribution to the final log odds (the shape functions), and subsequently, the probability.

Figure 7.2: Local explanation of the model's decision-making for a single specific data point on the task of restocking. The top section presents a bar chart depicting individual feature contributions, with blue bars indicating features that discourage restocking and orange bars for those suggesting restocking. The bottom section displays shape function plots for significant features, illustrating their impact on the prediction relative to their values, marked by a red dot and vertical dashed line. This figure highlights the interplay between key factors such as immediate demand (broken stores today and warehouse stock) and longer-term sales trends, offering a balanced perspective in the model's predictive reasoning.

The prediction can be seen as a buildup of evidence for or against the class as highlighted in the value of each univariate component $f_i(x_i)$. This can be seen in the bar chart on the top of the Figure 7.2. In this case we have an intercept quite positive, which suggest a prior assumption that on average the model tends to suggest restocking rather than not. Below the bar graph, we can observe the shape functions $f_i(\cdot)$ for each feature zoomed in in the neighborhood of x_i . The shape function plots depict the relationship between the feature values and their effect on the model's prediction. The red dot on each plot pinpoints the actual value of the feature for the current data point, and the red dashed line helps contextualize where this value sits within the range of data the model has learned from. We can see that the top 3 features that model thinks are indicative of restocking are:

- **Percentage of Broken Stores Today:** We can see in the single shape function below the barplot how the value 0.4 for this feature is highly suggestive for restocking. From a business perspective this makes sense as usually a large number of stores with broken stock chain suggest that the product is having a large amount of sells

- **Purple Status:** A proprietary business-specific code that in this instance positively influences the decision to restock.
- **Warehouse Stock:** The model interprets a warehouse stock level of zero as a clear indicator for the need to restock, reflecting an immediate demand.

Conversely the top 3 features that the model see as opposing the restock are:

- **Sales to Purchase ratio:** With a value of 0.03, this feature suggests limited sales activity, thereby discouraging restocking.
- **Broken stores over 7D:** A lower count of broken stores over a week contrasts with the current day's data, indicating a recent spike in popularity rather than consistent demand, which may caution against immediate restocking.
- **Stores Breaking:** Similar to the seven-day metric, this feature indicates patterns of breaking stores and contributes to a more cautious approach towards restocking.

In summary, the model's prediction for restocking in this instance is primarily driven by the immediate demand indicated by today's percentage of broken stores and the absence of stock in the warehouse. However, it is tempered by factors such as the recent sales trend and the breaking pattern of stores over a longer period. This nuanced analysis, blending immediate signals with longer-term trends, exemplifies the model's ability to balance different aspects of the business environment, providing a well-rounded decision-making process. This approach ensures that restocking decisions are not only reactive to immediate needs but also consider broader sales dynamics, optimizing stock management in a way that is responsive yet strategic.

7.2 USE CASE B: WEEKLY SALES PREDICTION

In this second use case, our focus was on predicting weekly sales for specific products in the upcoming week. To support this, the dataset comprised 15,283 records split into training, validation, and test sets with sizes of 13,700, 1,523, and 1,060 records, respectively. Categorical variables were transformed using one-hot encoding, resulting in a total of 305 features. The data records were numbered with successive weeks, namely data for week i was used for predicting sales in week $i + 1$ in an auto-regressive fashion. This setup allowed for a sequential analysis of sales data across successive weeks.

7.2.1 Modeling Dynamics: White Box vs. Black Box

In preliminary experiments we realized that white-box models were not as performing as black boxes, and since the emphasis of this use case was more on having an accurate prediction rather than a faithful explanation we opted for modeling with Random Forests (RF). However, to better understand the decisions made by the RF model, we made use of Shapley values into the analysis (see Section 3.5.4 in Chapter 3), which thanks to the TreeShap implementation allowed to compute the impact values efficiently.

7.2.1.1 Initial Insights: A proxy variable

During the initial analysis of the first week's data, we found that the RF model appeared to be significantly influenced by a single variable. This was apparent when we calculated the average of the absolute Shapley values across all features, as shown in Figure 7.3.

Figure 7.3: Summary of the most significant features influencing first week sales predictions in Use Case B, derived from average absolute Shapley values.

Diving deeper into this variable's specific influence, we charted the Shapley values, as presented in Figure 7.4. This visualization revealed a nearly straight-line correlation between the

variable's value and its Shapley impact, hinting at the possibility of this feature acting as a strong proxy for the task, encapsulating substantial predictive insight.

Figure 7.4: Plot of the feature 'Expected starting distribution' against its impact on the target (measured in terms of Shapley Values), illustrating a linear trend and saturation, indicative of a proxy variable with considerable predictive power.

To verify the accuracy of this finding, we constructed a linear model using solely this influential feature. Surprisingly, the model performed remarkably well, even with a single-variable approach. The comparative performance of this model alongside others—such as MLP (a multi-layer perceptron), XGB (an extreme gradient boosting method), and a full-feature linear model—is illustrated in Figure 7.5, with each model's weekly performance plotted. Notably, the linear model that was trained exclusively on the identified proxy variable, despite being the least performing compared to the others, still demonstrates a surprisingly decent predictive capability with just this single feature.

Figure 7.5: Comparative performance graph of different predictive models over a series of weeks, with a notable single-feature linear model's efficacy.

One might wonder how a solitary feature could be so informative for such a sophisticated task. It appears that this feature inherently captures a multitude of expert-driven decisions, which closely align with the ultimate goal of the prediction.

7.2.1.2 Unraveling Grouped Feature Impact

One limitation of calculating feature importance using the mean of the absolute Shapley values for each column, as illustrated in Figure 7.3, is the potential to overlook certain patterns. For example, consider one-hot encoded categorical features. A categorical feature with k categories will be ‘spread’ across k columns. The Shapley values corresponding to these encoded columns are distributed among multiple columns. When evaluating each column independently, one might underestimate the overall importance. Fortunately, due to the linearity and additivity properties of Shapley values (see Section 3.5.4 in Chapter 3), one can compute the aggregate impact of a categorical feature by summing up the Shapley values across all related one-hot encoded columns.

One can extend this idea by defining **groups** of semantically related features and then calculating their collective importance. This approach is particularly useful for understanding the model’s behavior into a more manageable and simplified overview. Using this method, we succeeded in reducing the complexity from over 100 individual features to just a dozen overarching groups. This way of doing does not preclude us from delving deeper into each group to gain more detailed insights.

We report the results of such groupings for each successive week in Figure 7.6.

Last but not least, it is possible to identify groups of features that appear to have little influence on the model’s performance. The data science team utilized this information to focus their efforts on collecting various aspects of important groups and to deprioritize less significant features.

7.3 USE CASE C: RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PRICE AND SALES

The third use case aimed to explore the complex relationship between a product family’s pricing strategy and the market’s demand response. With this in mind, we developed a model to establish connections between a product’s attributes, including its price, and the volume of sales. The goal was to offer a simulation tool to other business departments for making informed pricing decisions for specific items. Given the nature of the task, performance was prioritized, even at the expense of some fidelity to real-world data.

The dataset was extensive, consisting of approximately 19 million rows and 39 features. Due to the scale and complexity of the task, we once again employed RF modeling, complemented with SHAP explanations.

Figure 7.6: Importance of groups as a function of time. With groupings, it is possible to better assess the importance of categorical features and, more generally, of semantically related features. The importance of these features would otherwise be dispersed across individual columns and might be overlooked by traditional plots.

Notably, the target variable exhibited a fat-tailed distribution, meaning its second-order moment might not be finite. This characteristic is evident from the histogram on a log-log axis, as displayed in Figure 7.7, which closely follows the behavior typical of power-law distributions.

Figure 7.7: The target variable in use case C exhibits a fat-tailed distribution, evident from its linear trend in a log-log histogram—a characteristic typical of power-law distributions. This requires special considerations in model development.

This poses challenges for classical modeling techniques, which often assume a thin-tailed target variable. To mitigate this, we opted to predict the logarithm of the target variable rather

than the variable itself. Additionally, we used the Mean Absolute Error for evaluation, avoiding metrics that incorporate squares, which can be disproportionately influenced by outliers in fat-tailed distributions.

Like in the previous section, we also conducted a group analysis by classifying semantically similar features into explanation blocks. Interestingly, even at this aggregated level, training the model on the logarithm of the target variable resulted in distinct differences not only in performance but also in how features were utilized.

The most insightful finding is illustrated in Figure 7.8, where the logarithm of the price is plotted against sales. Despite some product-specific variability, a general trend emerges: as the price of a product increases, its impact on sales tends to be negative. However, this pattern plateaus at higher price points, suggesting that either high-net-worth individuals become price-insensitive or that the model struggles to capture the behavior due to the sparse data in the fat-tailed distribution.

Figure 7.8: Impact of the logarithm of price on the logarithm of sales, visualized as a 2D histogram colored by frequency. The plot reveals a general downward trend, implying a negative correlation between price and sales. However, the trend plateaus at higher price points, suggesting either a diminishing sensitivity to price for high-cost items or limitations in the model due to sparse data.

7.4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The integration of XAI in the industry, particularly in the context of the textile giant INDITEX, provides a compelling illustration of how explainable AI can transform decision-making processes. This exploration across three distinct use cases - restocking, weekly sales prediction, and the relationship between price and sales - showcases the multifaceted nature of XAI and its practical applications.

7.4.1 Restocking: Balancing Interpretability and Accuracy

In the restocking use case, the decision to employ EBM, a type of GAM, was grounded in the critical need to balance interpretability and accuracy. This decision aligns with the guidelines presented in Section 3.2, which emphasize the importance of context in choosing between black-box and white-box models.

The restocking scenario in inventory management is a case where the stakes are relatively high. Poor decisions in restocking could lead to significant financial implications, such as lost sales opportunities or increased holding costs. Hence, the choice of a model that offers transparency and interpretability is essential. This need for **faithfulness** in explanations, where the explanation narrative mirrors the model's internal mechanics, is crucial in high-stake scenarios like restocking. EBM, being a white-box model, provides this level of faithfulness and transparency, allowing users to understand and trust its recommendations.

The decision to employ EBM in the restocking use case was also influenced by the comparable performance between EBM and more complex models like Random Forests or EB2M. As the decision chart in figure 3.3 suggests, when white-box models perform similarly to black-box models, it's advisable to opt for white-box models due to their added advantage in interpretability. This was exactly the case in our restocking scenario – EBM offered a similar level of predictive accuracy as the more opaque models but with the added benefit of being easier to interpret and understand.

7.4.2 Weekly Sales Prediction: Insights from Black Box Models

The weekly sales prediction scenario revealed a different facet of XAI. Here, we leaned towards a high-performing black-box model (Random Forest) due to the emphasis on accuracy. However, the incorporation of SHAP values to interpret the model's decisions demonstrated that XAI techniques could still extract meaningful insights from complex models. The discovery of a proxy variable with significant predictive power was a testament to this approach. It showed how XAI could uncover underlying patterns and relationships that might not be immediately

apparent, providing a more nuanced understanding of the model's behavior, the data and the task.

7.4.3 Price and Sales: Navigating Complex Relationships

In the third use case of exploring the relationship between price and sales, the primary focus was on constructing a reliable simulation tool capable of predicting potential sales volumes for specific products. Given the extensive nature of the dataset and the emphasis on building a robust simulation tool, the decision to employ a powerful black-box model was a strategic one. In this scenario, the usage of an efficient Random Forest implementation, known for its scalability and speedy performance on large datasets, was a pragmatic choice.

Once trained, we used the Shapley Values computed efficiently with TreeShap (described in Section 3.5.4.5). This approach allowed for a deeper understanding of the data and the underlying predictive dynamics, which might have been overlooked with other methods. In tasks where the primary objective is to gain insights into the prediction task, rather than ensuring transparency for stakeholders, this combination of a high-performance black-box model with effective post-hoc explanation tools proves to be highly effective.

One of the significant achievements of this approach was the uncovering of intricate relationships between variables and also where the source of useful information came from. This was a very valuable source of knowledge as it informed successive efforts of the research department on this task.

7.4.4 Overall Impact and Future Directions

Across all use cases, XAI has proven to be a powerful tool for enhancing understanding, trust, and decision-making in various business contexts. By providing transparency into AI's decision-making process, XAI empowers users, fostering an environment where AI and human expertise can synergistically coexist. The cases at INDITEX serve as a testament to the potential of XAI in transforming business operations, making them more data-driven, efficient, and transparent.

Looking ahead, the potential for XAI in various industries is immense. As businesses continue to face increasingly complex challenges and data-rich environments, the demand for AI systems that are not only powerful but also understandable and trustworthy will only grow. The insights gained from these use cases at INDITEX can serve as a foundation for further exploration and application of XAI in diverse industry settings, paving the way for a new era of AI-driven decision-making where transparency and understanding are at the forefront.

8 Conclusions

In this final chapter, we tie together the questions and research discussed throughout this thesis. Our main goal has been to explore the complexities of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI), understand its components, and grasp its practical applications. We now take time to reflect on our progress and the insights we have gained. As we move into our concluding remarks, we carry with us the knowledge that this work is but a part of a larger, ever-evolving field, one that continually challenges and pushes the boundaries of our understanding of artificial intelligence and its role within society.

8.1 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This thesis set out to develop and assess methods for creating inherently interpretable AI models and generating post-hoc explanations, with a focus on their industrial applications. Our work demonstrates the value of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) for both theoretical understanding and practical use. XAI, as our research illustrates, encompasses both technical challenges and the human factors that influence how explanations are received. We found that transparent 'white box' models can often rival the performance of more complex systems. Additionally, we introduced a novel method for fine-tuning white box models to optimize the balance between interpretability and efficiency. A key discovery was the importance of explanation fidelity. Model-agnostic tools, like those based on Shapley values, enable us to assess both the complexity of AI models and the accuracy of the explanations we derive from them.

An important focus of our research was to evaluate the accuracy of explanation methods for AI models working with images and language. Measuring the faithfulness of these explanations is a significant challenge. We developed new metrics to better assess the reliability of explanations across vision and language models, helping us identify the most effective techniques for different data types. A key finding was that methods successful with image-based models do not necessarily translate well to text. This highlights the need to tailor AI explanations to the specific data being used. Our work emphasizes the complexity of generating understandable AI explanations and the importance of continued research to refine our evaluation methods.

Our collaboration with INDITEX proved invaluable in understanding how XAI functions within real-world industry settings. This partnership highlights the value of using both inter-

pretable and opaque models strategically. When systems directly support human decision-making, transparency is essential. However, for broader or more complex projects, insights from ‘black box’ models can enhance data collection and reveal valuable patterns within the data.

While our work represents significant progress, limitations remain. Creating accurate feature attributions for vision and language models is particularly challenging due to their complexity. This area, highlighted by our research, demands further academic exploration.

The findings presented in this thesis directly contribute to answering the research questions posed in the introduction, which align with the objectives of the NL4XAI project, particularly those of Work Package 1. The interpretable-by-design models (Chapter 4) and the proposed metrics for assessing the complexity and faithfulness of explanations (Chapter 5) address the question of developing transparent and trustworthy AI models. The evaluation of post-hoc explanation methods in vision and language domains (Chapter 6) tackles the challenge of generating reliable explanations across different data types. The industry case studies (Chapter 7) demonstrate the practical applicability of XAI methods, answering the question of how explainable AI can be integrated into real-world scenarios. These contributions not only advance the state-of-the-art in XAI but also lay the foundation for future research in this rapidly evolving field.

In conclusion, this thesis contributes to the ongoing conversation within XAI. By connecting theory with practice, it emphasizes the importance of interpretability and explainability for building effective AI models. This work highlights the potential impact of XAI and its role in shaping the future of AI research and development.

8.2 FUTURE WORK

This research marks a step forward, but the field of XAI offers vast potential for further exploration and innovation. The findings of this thesis open doors to a multitude of exciting directions for future research endeavors.

To advance inherently interpretable models, rigorous testing against complex and diverse datasets is needed to assess their robustness in real-world applications. Additionally, we must focus on refining post-hoc explanations for black-box models, ensuring greater fidelity as AI systems become increasingly dynamic and complex.

Our industry collaboration with INDITEX highlights the significant potential of XAI within more industrial and commercial settings. Future research should investigate the full integration of XAI across various industry processes. This will allow us to analyze its impact on operational efficiency and the quality of decision-making.

Additionally, the complex relationship between model complexity and interpretability offers a fertile ground for continued research. Developing a predictive framework to optimize this

balance across different AI applications remains a significant and compelling challenge.

An interdisciplinary approach, drawing on insights from behavioral sciences, could significantly enhance our understanding of how users interact with, perceive, and trust AI explanations. This presents a rich opportunity for future research to uncover the complex interplay between human cognition and machine-generated explanations.

Domain-specific challenges demand customized XAI research. By tailoring explanations to the specific needs and constraints of different sectors, we can create more effective and nuanced explanation mechanisms, leading to significant improvements within various industries.

The aspiration for a unified theory of XAI could shape the future of research, integrating diverse findings and methods into a cohesive framework. Simultaneously, the societal and ethical implications of XAI demand careful consideration, as they heavily influence public trust and the regulatory landscape around AI.

The future of XAI research is multifaceted. It involves theoretical exploration, practical applications, and a commitment to ethical and socially responsible AI development. This thesis contributes to this ongoing journey, fueled by the collaborative and innovative spirit within the research community.

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A tese explora o problema da caixa negra na Intelixencia Artificial (IA) e a necesidade de sistemas de IA máis transparentes e explicables. A XAI busca abrir os sistemas de IA ao escrutinio, facendo o proceso de toma de decisións máis comprensible para os usuarios. Isto é crucial para construír confianza e asegurar unha implementación xusta e ética da IA en múltiples sectores. A tese formula a hipótese de que os modelos de IA transparentes (caixa branca) poden ser cruciais para explicar sistemas máis complexos e opacos. Os obxectivos inclúen: 1) Comprender a paisaxe da XAI, 2) Construír modelos interpretables por deseño, 3) Xerar explicacións post-hoc para modelos caixa negra, 4) Entender as implicacións para a industria.